

Support Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low- Risk Pesticide Use

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Executive summary of the deliverable

The current '**Inventory of IPM Tools**' is a collection of IPM tools and measures for the cultivation of wine grape, olive, apple, strawberry, wheat, maize, potato and onion. They should contribute to the cultivation in a way that reduces the dependency and use of pesticides while maintaining the farm-economic perspective for the grower.

The partners in the SUPPORT project have contributed by providing descriptions of IPM tools which they use in their daily work but have also supplied with others that are not widely used or are new and expected to be used within the next three to five years.

Some of the tools may be easily applicable (free or cheap/low labour input) while others are expensive (investments/labour hours). The material covers tools that are implemented to various extents.

The inventory is collected to provide an overview of the most relevant tools in the eight crops that were selected in the project. It will be used during the project in the various activities and meetings (focus groups, NCCs, NoPs and CoPs). It should serve as a source for uptake of new tools and support the stakeholder groups to discuss arguments for and against adoption of certain tools. It should also encourage further development of specific tools and push the innovation of new tools. Finally, the inventory and the whole SUPPORT project should pave the way for new EU policies on IPM inspired by input from multistakeholder involvement.

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	The General Assembly
CA	Consortium Agreement
SC	Scientific Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader
TL	Task leader
NCC	National Crop Cluster
CoP	Community of Practices
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
DoA	Description of the action

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of Inventory of IPM tools

Experiences from practical agriculture have shown that well-designed integrated pest management programmes (IPM) are a viable solution to reduce the dependency on the use of chemical pesticides, while maintaining an economically sound plant production. However, according to the EU Commission, the uptake of IPM practices by farmers and the reduction of pesticide use remain low. This is a challenge and support for adoption of IPM techniques by farmers is becoming very important to meet the political goals. This requires thorough understanding of the decision-making process of farmers and other involved stakeholders to improve strategies and policies that enable and stimulate the application of IPM.

1.1.1 EU policies on Integrated Pesticide Management

Since 2009 IPM has been an integral part of the EU-politics and is also expected to play an important role in forthcoming strategies and regulations.

The EU politics on IPM can be viewed in the link on the official EU-website:

“A cornerstone of the EU Directive is the promotion of IPM, for which the 8 general principles¹ are laid down in Annex III to the Directive (Sustainable use of pesticides)². IPM is one of the approaches for low-pesticide-input pest management, and IPM must be implemented by all professional users of pesticides.

- IPM involves an integrated approach to the prevention and/or suppression of organisms harmful to plants using all available information, tools and methods.
- IPM aims to keep the use of pesticides and other forms of intervention only to levels that are economically and ecologically justified, and which reduce or minimize risk to human health and the environment.
- Sustainable biological, physical, and other non-chemical methods must be preferred to chemical methods if they provide satisfactory pest control.”³

The EU Farm to Fork strategy⁴ aims at making food systems fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly, and IPM is an important element in this strategy.

Definition on Integrated Pesticide Management

“Integrated pest management means careful consideration of all available plant protection methods and subsequent integration of appropriate measures that discourage the development of populations of harmful organisms and keep the use of plant protection products and other forms of intervention to levels that are financially and ecologically justified and reduce or minimise risks to human health and the environment. 'Integrated pest management' emphasises the growth of a healthy crop with the least possible disruption to agro-ecosystems and encourages natural pest control mechanisms”³.

Every EU member state is obligated to work on the implementation of IPM following this definition, but the way of implementation may differ from country to country. An overview of the implementation in the individual member states can be found in deliverable D3.1., Policy analysis (K. Kounani & A. Kannavou, Agricultural University of Athens) in this project.

¹ Link to the [8 general principles](#)

² Link to the [Annex III to the Directive \(Sustainable use of pesticides\)](#)

³ Link to the [European Commission webpage](#)

⁴ Link to the [Farm to Fork Strategy](#)

1.1.2 The SUPPORT project

The SUPPORT project runs from 2023 to 2026, and involves partners from The Netherlands, Germany, Italy, France, Belgium, Switzerland, Poland, Romania, Greece, Spain and Denmark.

The goal of the project is to pave the way of adoption of IPM tools to reduce the use of pesticides.

SUPPORT responds to the above-mentioned challenge in this report by increasing the capacity to understand the environmental, social and economic impacts of existing and future crop protection systems in which IPM is applied, by creation of an inventory of IPM tools and techniques and the development of an impact monitoring system.

Farmers operate in an economic, social and institutional environment. SUPPORT will identify barriers and opportunities in the entire agrifood-chain for the adoption of IPM and analyse qualitatively and quantitatively their role in farmer decision-making. Data will be collected by interviews, surveys, choice experiments and derived from the (Farm accountancy data network) FADN. The results of this analysis will be used as a basis for the development of strategies and policies enabling and supporting farmers and other stakeholders to apply IPM. The development takes place in a co-creation process with stakeholders. Therefore, a multi-actor approach will be the backbone of the research process, figure 1.1. 25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs) will be used for data collection. For nine of these NCCs, Community of Practices (CoPs) will be developed with public and private stakeholders to co-create strategies and policies, figure 1.2. The CoPs will be embedded in a Network of Practice (NoP), an overarching platform connecting all stakeholders. This NoP will be used to communicate, discuss, and disseminate results of SUPPORT with the entire community of stakeholders in the EU.

Figure 1.1: Multistakeholder collaboration in the SUPPORT project

25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs)

consist in a selection of cases covering a wide range of farm typologies, sectors and systems representative of the diversity of farming in the EU and associated countries.

Communities of practices (CoPs)

gathered around nine of the NCCs are the place for co-creation with the objectives of accelerating professional development, enabling sharing, and building better practices.

CoPs will form a Network of Practice (NoP)

at a larger scale that will include actors beyond CoPs who may exert influence and seek cooperation with related initiatives as well as CoPs leaders and CoP partners.

Figure 1.2: Contributing countries in the SUPPORT project, and division of communities of practice and national crop clusters for the eight crops

Country	Bio-geographical region	Perennial		Annual cropping system					
		Processing industry	Fresh	Processing industry	Fresh	Processing industry	Fresh	Processing industry	Fresh
Denmark	Continental					X	X	X	
France	Continental								
Germany	Continental					X		X	
Italy	Mediterranean		X	X					X
Netherlands	Continental			X	X			X	
Belgium	Continental				X			X	
Poland	Continental			X				X	X
Romania	Continental					X	X		
Spain	Mediterranean	X	X		X				
Switzerland	Alpine					X	X		
Greece	Mediterranean	X	X						

■ Mediterranean ■ Atlantic ■ Continental ■ Alpine X T4.3 Community of Practices 9 X T4.2 National Crop Clusters 25

The case crops (wheat, maize, potato, olive, strawberry, apple, onion and wine grape) and countries in the consortium of the project are shown in figure 1.2. The selected crops cover from 68.6 – 92.8 % of the cropped area in the countries participating in our consortium, figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: The European coverage of SUPPORT crop areas in the member states participating in our consortium

1.2 Objective

The objective of task 1.1. ‘Inventory of IPM Tools’ in SUPPORT is to make a collection of the IPM tools and measures that are available for the eight crops that have been selected for the project. The inventory includes most of the tools that are available to growers or are expected to be

available within the next 3-5 years. The tools should relate to one or more of the IPM principles, which are shown in Table 2.1. The inventory should also include other relevant IPM tools presented in previous EU-projects. The inventory should present ratings of efficacy against the relevant pest, cost of implementation (investments/labour time), yield impact (amount/quality), potential pesticide reduction and level of current use.

The inventory of IPM tools will be used in the various activities and meetings planned in the project (focus groups, NCC's, NoP's and CoP's). It should serve as inspiration for uptake of new IPM tools and in discussions in the stakeholder groups for and against adoption of certain tools. It should also stimulate to further development and uptake of IPM tools and, hence, push innovation of new tools. Finally, the inventory and the whole SUPPORT project should pave the way for new EU policies on IPM with background in input from multistakeholder involvement.

1.3 Demarcation

The inventory is collected to provide an overview of the relevant and available IPM tools for the eight crops selected for the project. The collection of tools includes a listing of current IPM tools. It gives a brief description of every tool, but further information must be gathered if a grower wants to apply them.

The collection of tools covers tools used in the European countries with main focus on the tools available in the countries covered in the project. Tools are included in the inventory if they are in use or are expected to be in use within the next five years.

The collectors of the tools are working close to practice and the growers which should guarantee that widely used tools are contained and upcoming tools as well as non-adapted tools are provided for the inventory. There may lack some IPM tools that are seldom used e.g. some decision support systems.

An estimate of the environmental impact of the tools was required, but it was not included in the inventory of tools since the contributors were not expected to have the expertise to perform these assessments. In WP 1.2 a monitoring system will be developed for assessment of the impact on the environment, economy etc. of the IPM tools. This monitoring system and this inventory can be applied in Community of Practices, in which IPM strategies will be elaborated.

2. Approach

In Annex 6 a description of the guidelines for collection of tools to the inventory is attached. The participants were asked to fill in an on-line form in MS Forms with the information to one-pagers for each tool. Some did not work in the Microsoft environment and had problems with using the MS Forms, and they were given the opportunity to write their tools in Google-sheets or directly in Excel instead.

The contributors of tools have given ratings on a coarse scale of different parameters of the tools, and the ratings should be considered as an independent advisor's position to the subject. Ratings were made on efficacy against the relevant pest, cost of implementation (investments/labour time), yield impact (amount/quality), potential pesticide reduction, and degree of implementation. The rating system is explained in chapter 2.4 below.

The ratings in the report do not include an estimate of the environmental impact of the tools. This expertise was not present among the contributors of the tools. However, an estimate of the contribution to pesticide reduction has been required.

2.1 Collection of IPM tools/measures

The collection of tools for the inventory has been carried out by people who work close to practice like advisors and researchers. They know which tools are used and which are not. Most of them have been added to the inventory after the first focus group meetings in each NCC's in the second half-year of 2023.

The partners primarily contributed with tools for the crops in which they had NCC's.

2.2 IPM tools as one-pagers

Every single IPM tool is presented as one-pager in English and is included in the specific crop chapters where it belongs. Each crop chapter includes tools for pests, diseases, weeds and others (measures that go across different tool categories e. g. crop rotation and tools that do not fit into the traditional categories like e.g. growth regulation etc.). In addition, 13 tools are not crop specific and may cover most of the crops or cropping systems and are listed separately. Tools covering more than one crop are presented for each crop. The non-crop-specific tools are only presented in the specific appendix with non-crop-specific tools, but some tools in the crop specific chapters may to some extent look like them.

Within each crop chapter tools for diseases are presented first, followed by pests and weeds and other. If a tool is meant for more pest categories, it is presented under the first category in which it is mentioned.

The IPM tools are described as one-pagers in a way that give growers and advisors a very brief introduction and explanation to the mechanisms of the tool, and how to use it. The text should be supplemented with links to more descriptions of the tools in English and illustrative photos.

2.3 IPM principles

For each tool the relevant IPM principles are mentioned, which may be one or more of the eight IPM principles listed in Table 2.1. In the one-pagers the eight different principles are mentioned as: prevention, monitoring, thresholds, alternatives, targeted use, dosage, anti-resistance and follow-up.

Table 2.1: The 8 principles of IPM

The 8 principles of IPM	
1.	The <u>prevention</u> and/or suppression of harmful organisms should be achieved or supported among other options especially by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • crop rotation, • use of adequate cultivation techniques (e.g. stale seedbed technique, sowing dates and densities, under-sowing, conservation tillage, pruning and direct sowing), • use, where appropriate, of resistant/tolerant cultivars and standard/certified seed and planting material, • use of balanced fertilisation, liming and irrigation/drainage practices, • preventing the spreading of harmful organisms by hygiene measures (e.g. by regular cleansing of machinery and equipment), • protection and enhancement of important beneficial organisms, e.g. by adequate plant protection measures or the utilisation of ecological infrastructures inside and outside production sites.
2.	Harmful organisms must be <u>monitored</u> by adequate methods and tools, where available. Such adequate tools should include observations in the field as well as scientifically sound warning, forecasting and early diagnosis systems, where feasible, as well as the use of advice from professionally qualified advisors.
3.	Based on the results of the monitoring the professional user has to decide whether and when to apply plant protection measures. Robust and scientifically sound <u>threshold values</u> are essential components for decision making. For harmful organisms threshold levels defined for the region, specific areas, crops and particular climatic conditions must be taken into account before treatments, where feasible.
4.	Sustainable <u>biological, physical and other non-chemical methods</u> must be preferred to chemical methods if they provide satisfactory pest control.
5.	The pesticides applied shall be as <u>specific</u> as possible for the target and shall have the <u>least side effects</u> on human health, non-target organisms and the environment.

6. The professional user should keep the use of pesticides and other forms of intervention to levels that are necessary, e.g. by reduced doses, reduced application frequency or partial applications, considering that the level of risk in vegetation is acceptable and they do not increase the risk for development of resistance in populations of harmful organisms.
7. Where the risk of resistance against a plant protection measure is known and where the level of harmful organisms requires repeated application of pesticides to the crops, available anti-resistance strategies should be applied to maintain the effectiveness of the products. This may include the use of multiple pesticides with different modes of action.
8. Based on the records on the use of pesticides and on the monitoring of harmful organisms the professional user should check the success of the applied plant protection measures.

2.4 Ratings of IPM tools

Different parameters for each IPM tool are rated on a scale from 1 to 5. Each individual tool is compared to the current and most common situation without the use of the tool. In Table 2.2 the different parameters and the range of respective ratings are shown. The rating on efficacy shows how efficient the tool is assessed to be (in percent) against a given pest problem. The rating of cost of implementation is divided into labour time and investments. Rating of labour time can be both the practical work time required to use the IPM tool, e.g., monitoring in the field or the time required to learn to use an IPM tool, e.g., learning to fly a drone. Investments can be the costs of, e.g., buying a hoe or the difference in costs of mechanical weeding three times compared to spraying once. The potential impact of a tool on yield and the quality of the harvested crop are estimated and can be rated as both positive and negative compared to current situation. The potential for pesticide reduction is a parameter that should be compared to current level of pesticide use. Level of implementation measured as percentage of area indicates how widely used the tool is by growers currently. To give a brief explanation to the scale for a single tool when it is used in e.g. meetings a code is presented, where one star (*) explains the scale that goes from (1 very low – 5 very high) and two stars (**) explains the scale that goes from (1 negative – 5 positive).

Table 2.1: Explanation to ratings of different parameters, scores from 1-5

Score	1 Very little/low	2	3	4	5 Very much/high
Efficacy against the relevant pest group (%)	0-5	5-20	20-35	35-50	≥50
Cost of implementation in labour time (hours per hectare)	0-0,5	0,5-3,5	3,5-7	7-10	≥10
Cost of implementation in investments (% of the crop value per hectare)	≤1	1-17	17-34	34-50	≥50
Performance (% of normal yield) compared to pesticides	≤- 5	-5-(-2)	-2-2	2-5	≥5
Performance (% of standard quality) compared to pesticides	≤- 5	-5-(-2)	-2-2	2-5	≥5
Potential reduction of pesticide use (%)	≈ 0%	0-8	8-17	17-25	≥25
Current level of implementation (% of the area)	≤5	5-20	20-35	35-50	≥50

2.5 Additional materials

Links to relevant information about the tools are added in the description if they are available and updated. To be included, the material should either be written in English, or the webpage should automatically translate into English.

2.6 Pictures

Pictures are included in the tools if they have been provided and are illustrative for the tool.

2.7 Contributors

The contributors are those who have sent in the description of the tool, and not necessarily the author of a specific tool.

3. IPM tools in the inventory

A total of 493 individual tools have been collected including 13 non-crop specific tools, figure 3.1. The individual tools are presented in annex 6.1-6.9. Some tools are suggested for more than one pest category which means that the total number for the eight crops counts 801 tools, table 3.1. The total number of tools varies between crops from 7 in wine grape to 100 in potato.

Figure 3.1: Number of tools per crop

Table 2.1: Number of tools divided per crop and category. Some tools cover more than one pest category which results in a higher total number per crop than shown in figure. 3.1.

	Wine grape	Olive	Apple	Strawberry	Wheat	Maize	Potato	Onion	Total pest category
Diseases	5	33	41	41	29	26	50	17	242
Pests	5	35	38	45	34	41	42	19	259
Weeds	2	18	18	18	54	58	30	18	216
Others	2	3	5	12	12	18	21	11	84
Total per crop	14	89	102	116	129	143	143	65	801

The number of tools covering the 8 IPM principles are listed in table 3.2 and separated for each crop and principle. A tool may cover from one to all eight principles and the total sum is 1078. Almost half of the tools covers the principles concerning prevention and use of alternatives to pesticides.

Table 3.2: Number of IPM tools for each crop divided into the 8 IPM principles.

	Wine grape	Olive	Apple	Strawberry	Wheat	Maize	Potato	Onion	Total	% of total
Prevention	6	39	41	53	41	26	61	23	290	27
Monitoring	4	17	20	30	21	8	17	7	124	11
Thresholds	2	21	11	20	14	5	15	7	95	9
Alternatives	5	37	44	30	32	21	48	14	231	21
Targeted use	3	12	10	9	12	21	18	3	88	8
Dosage	6	26	20	6	15	25	26	12	136	13
Anti-resistance	3	9	6	5	6	17	11	2	59	6
Follow-up	3	13	6	5	10	8	9	1	55	5

3.1 Results

1.1.3 Wine Grape

There are two NCC's for wine grape, and they are in Greece and Spain. Spain also has a CoP on wine grape.

A total of 7 IPM tools is collected for wine grape and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 5 measures on diseases, 5 on pests, 2 on weeds and 2 in the category 'other'.

There is limited variation in the assessments between the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests and weeds), tables 3.3-3.9. When looking at the average of the scores for each category, the efficacy of all tools is high (35-50%). The cost in labour time and investments for implementation is assessed to be at a medium level (up to 7 hours or up to 34 % of the crop value per hectare). The impact on the harvested yield on average is estimated to be between -2 % and +2 %, and the quality of the crop on average is expected to be 2-5 % higher when the IPM-tools are used. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be between approximately 8-25 percent, most for weeds and pests. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-25 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5- \geq 50 % of the area for some tools.

Table 3.3: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	3-5
Pests	4	4	3-4
Weeds	4	4	3-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	5	4	4-5

Table 3.4: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	2	2-4
Pests	3	2	2-4
Weeds	3	2	2-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	2	2

Table 3.5: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value per hectare)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-4
Pests	3	3	2-4
Weeds	3	3	2-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3

Table 3.6: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	3-4
Pests	3	3	3-4
Weeds	3	3	3-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3

Table 3.7: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	3-4
Pests	4	4	3-4
Weeds	4	4	3-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	4

Table 3.8: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	3-4
Pests	4	3	3-4
Weeds	4	3	3-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3

Table 3.9: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wine grape cultivation. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Wine grape	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-4
Pests	3	3	1-4
Weeds	3	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	4

1.1.4 Olive

There are three NCC's for olive, and they are in Italy, Spain, and Greece. Greece also has a CoP for olive.

A total of 42 IPM tools is collected for olive and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 33 measures on diseases, 35 on pests, 18 on weeds and 3 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pest and weeds), tables 3.10-3.16. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools is high, with an average of approximately 35-50 %, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments are assessed to be at a medium level (3,5-7 hours per hectare/17-34 % of the crop value per hectare) but with big differences between the tools that cover the full scale. On average the tools do not seem to have any impact on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop, but some tools may also have either negative or positive impact on the yield. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-17 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or higher. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20- 25 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5 up to 50% or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.10: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	2-5
Pests	4	4	2-5
Weeds	4	4	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	4-4

Table 3.11: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	2	1-5
Pests	3	2/3	1-5
Weeds	3	2	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	2	2-4

Table 3.12: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	2/4	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-3

Table 3.13: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-4

Table 3.14: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-5
Pests	3	3	2-5
Weeds	3	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-4

Table 3.15: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-4

Table 3.16: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in olive cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Olive	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	4	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-4

1.1.5 Apple

There are three NCC's for apple, and they are in Italy, the Netherlands and Poland. In addition, Poland also has a CoP for apple.

A total of 56 IPM tools is collected for apple and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 41 measures on diseases, 38 on pests, 18 on weeds and 5 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pest and weeds) in tables 3.17-3.23. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools is high, with an average around 35-50, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments on average are assessed to be at medium level (3,5-7 hours per hectare/17-34 % of the crop value per hectare), but with big differences covering the full scale.

The average effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop are positive (2-5 %), but with a range from negative impact on yield to very positive yield effect for the tools. A pesticide reduction on average is suggested to be approximately 17-25 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area (pest and diseases) and approximately 5-20 % for weeds, but with a wide range from less than 5- 40 % or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.17: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	2-5
Pests	4	5	2-5
Weeds	4	4	3-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	4	1-4

Table 3.18: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	2	2-5

Table 3.19: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-4
Pests	3	3	1-4
Weeds	3	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-4

Table 3.20: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	3	2-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-4

Table 3.21: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	3	3-5
Pests	4	3	3-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	3-5

Table 3.22: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	2-5
Pests	4	4	2-5
Weeds	4	4	3-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-5

Table 3.23: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in apple cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Apple	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	2	2	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-4

1.1.6 Strawberry

There are three NCC's for strawberry, and they are in Spain, Belgium, and The Netherlands. In addition, The Netherlands also has a CoP for strawberry.

A total of 69 IPM tools is collected for strawberry and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 41 measures on diseases, 45 on pests, 18 on weeds and 12 in the category `other`.

The scores per category is shown in tables 3.24-3.30. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools for pests and weeds is high, with an average of approximately 35-50 %, and approximately 20-35 % for diseases, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation (3,5-7 hours per hectare) on average was at medium level. The cost for investments on average (1-17 % of the crop value per hectare) is assessed to be at low level, but with big differences among the tools.

The average effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop are neutral +/- 2 % (diseases) to positive 2-5 % (pests and weeds), but with a range from slightly negative impact on yield to very positive yield effect for the tools. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-25 %, highest for weeds. The range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 35-50 % of the area (pest and weeds) and approximately 20-35 % for diseases, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50 % or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.24: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	1	1-5

Table 3.25: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-4

Table 3.26: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	3	1-4
Pests	2	3	1-4
Weeds	2	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-4

Table 3.27: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-5

Table 3.28: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3/4	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-4

Table 3.29: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	2	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-4

Table 3.30: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in strawberry cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Strawberry	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	2-5

1.1.7 Wheat

There are four NCC's for wheat, and they are in Denmark, Romania, Switzerland, and Germany. In addition, Germany also has a CoP for wheat.

A total of 97 IPM tools is collected for wheat and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 29 measures on diseases, 34 on pests, 54 on weeds and 12 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests, and weeds), tables 3.31-3.37. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools for diseases and weeds is high, with an average of approximately 35-50 %, and approximately 20-35 % for pests, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % or less to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments on average are assessed to be at low level (0-3,5 hours per hectare/≤1-17 % of the crop value per hectare) with the highest cost for pest and diseases, but with big differences among the tools.

The effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop are neutral in most cases +/- 2 %, but with a positive yield effect for the tools on diseases (2-5%). Some tools may also have either negative or positive impact on the yield. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-17 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area (pest and weeds) and approximately 35-50 % for diseases, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50% or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.31: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	1-5
Pests	3	4	1-5
Weeds	4	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	1/3	1-5

Table 3.32: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-4
Pests	2	1	1-4
Weeds	1	1	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-4

Table 3.33: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most bundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-4
Pests	2	1	1-4
Weeds	1	1	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-4

Table 3.34: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most bundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	2-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-4

Table 3.35: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most bundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-5

Table 3.36: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most bundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3/4	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	1	1-5

Table 3.37: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in wheat cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Wheat	Score (average)	Score (most bundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	1-5
Pests	3	2/4	1-5
Weeds	3	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	2/4	1-5

1.1.8 Maize

There are three NCC's for maize, and they are in Denmark, Switzerland, and Romania. Romania also has a CoP for maize.

A total of 80 IPM tools is collected for maize, and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 26 measures on diseases, 41 on pests, 58 on weeds and 18 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests, and weeds), tables 3.38-3.44. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools for pests and weeds is high, with an average of approximately 35-50 %, and approximately 20-35 % for diseases, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % or less to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments on average are assessed to be at medium level (0,5-3,5 hours per hectare/1-17 % of the crop value per hectare), but with big differences among the tools.

The effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop is neutral on average +/- 2 %, but there are big differences among the tools. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-17 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50% or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.38: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	5	1-5
Pests	4	5	1-5
Weeds	4	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	1-5

Table 3.39: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-4
Pests	2	1	1-4
Weeds	2	1	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1/2	1-4

Table 3.40: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-4
Pests	2	1	1-4
Weeds	2	1	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-3

Table 3.41: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-5

Table 3.42: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-5

Table 3.43: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3/5	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	1	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	5	1-5

Table 3.44: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in maize cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Maize	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	4	1-5
Pests	3	2	1-5
Weeds	3	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	4	1-5

1.1.9 Potato

There are five NCC's for potato, and they are in Poland, Belgium, The Netherlands, Germany, and Denmark. In addition, Denmark also has a CoP for potato.

A total of 100 IPM tools is collected for potato and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 51 measures on diseases, 42 on pests, 30 on weeds and 22 in the category 'other'.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests, and weeds), tables 3.45-3.51. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools for pests and diseases is approximately 20-35 % and 35-50 % for weeds, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % or less to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments on average are assessed to be at medium level (0,5-3,5 hours per hectare/1-17 % of the crop value per hectare) except the investment for pests that was estimated to be less than ≤ 1 of the crop value, but for all categories with big differences among the tools.

The effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop are neutral on average +/- 2 %, but there are big differences among the tools. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 0-8% for diseases and pests, and 8-17 % for weeds, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50% or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.45: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	4	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	4	4/5	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	1	1-5

Table 3.46: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-5
Pests	2	1	1-5
Weeds	2	2	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-5

Table 3.47: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-5
Pests	1	1	1-4
Weeds	2	2	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-5

Table 3.48: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-5

Table 3.49: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	2-5

Table 3.50: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-5
Pests	2	2	1-5
Weeds	3	2	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	1	1-5

Table 3.51: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in potato cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Potato	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	2	1-5
Pests	3	1	1-5
Weeds	3	1	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	1/5	1-5

1.1.10 Onion

There are two NCC's for onion, and they are in Poland and Italy. Italy also has a CoP for onion.

A total of 29 IPM tools is collected for onion, and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 17 measures on diseases, 19 on pests, 18 on weeds and 11 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments between the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests, and weeds), tables 3.52-3.58. When looking at the average of the scores for each category the efficacy of all tools is 35-50 %, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % or less to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation and the cost for investments on average are assessed to be at medium level (0,5-3,5 hours per hectare/1-17 % of the crop value per hectare), but with big differences among the tools.

The effect on the harvested yield, and the quality of the crop is expected to increase 2-5 % when the tools are used, most for the tools for weeds, although the effect of the different tools differs a lot. The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-17 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 35-50 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50% or more of the area for some tools.

Table 3.52: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4	2-5
Pests	4	4	2-5
Weeds	4	4	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-5

Table 3.53: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	3	1-4
Pests	2	3	1-4
Weeds	2	3/4/5	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	2	1-4

Table 3.54: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1	1-3
Pests	2	1	1-3
Weeds	2	1	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	2	1-3

Table 3.55: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	5	1-5
Pests	4	4/5	2-5
Weeds	5	5	2-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	1-5

Table 3.56: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	5	2-5
Pests	4	5	3-5
Weeds	5	5	3-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	2-5

Table 3.57: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	4	2-5
Pests	3	4	2-5
Weeds	3	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3/4	2-5

Table 3.58: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied in onion cultivation against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Onion	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	4	4/5	1-5
Pests	4	3	2-5
Weeds	4	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	3/5	3-5

1.1.11 Non-crop specific tools

A total of 13 IPM non-crop specific tools are collected, and some cover more than one of the four categories. There are 12 measures on diseases, 11 on pests, 10 on weeds and 4 in the category `other`.

There is not much variation in the assessments among the tools within each parameter (diseases, pests, and weeds), tables 3.59-3.65. When looking at the average of the scores for each category

the efficacy of all tools is 20-35 %, but the single tools differ in efficacy from 5 % or less to more than 50 %.

The cost in labour time for implementation on average is assessed to be at medium level (3,5-7 hours per hectare) for diseases and weeds, but lower (0,5-3,5 hours per hectare) for pests and 'other' but with big differences among the tools. The cost in investments on average is assessed to be at medium level (1-17 % of the crop value per hectare), but with big differences among the tools.

The effect on the harvested yield and crop quality, is expected to be neutral -2-2 % when the tools are used, although the effect of the different tools differ from - 5 - 5 %.

The pesticide reduction is suggested to be approximately 8-17 %, but the range for the specific tools goes from 0-25 % or more. The current level of implementation is expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area, but with a wide range from less than 5- 50% of the area for some tools.

Table 3.59: Efficacy, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1= very low (0-5%); 5= very high (50% or more)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3/4	1-5
Pests	3	4	1-5
Weeds	3	4	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	5	3-5

Table 3.60: Cost of implementation in labour time, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare); 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	1-4
Pests	2	1/3/4	1-4
Weeds	3	3	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-3

Table 3.61: Cost of implementation in investments, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare); 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	2	1/2	1-5
Pests	2	1	1-5
Weeds	2	2	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	2	3	1-3

Table 3.62: Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	2-4
Pests	3	4	2-4
Weeds	3	3	2-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	4	4	3-4

Table 3.63: Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticides, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non- crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more); 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3	3-4
Pests	3	3	2-4
Weeds	3	3	2-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3/4	3-4

Table 3.64: Potential reduction of pesticide use, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low (almost 0%); 5: Very high reduction (25 % or more)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	3/4	1-5
Pests	3	3	1-5
Weeds	3	3	1-5
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	3	3-4

Table 3.65: Current level of implementation, scores from 1-5 of the IPM tools that can be applied as non-crop specific tools against the relevant pest group. 1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area) 5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

Non-crop specific	Score (average)	Score (most abundant)	Range
Diseases	3	2	1-4
Pests	3	4	1-4
Weeds	3	3/4	1-4
Others (plant growth regulations etc.)	3	4	1-4

1.1.12 Scores in average of all crops

The average scores across the 8 crops on 7 different parameters are shown in table 3.66. It is calculated as a simple average and is not balanced according to the variable numbers of tools per crop. The estimated efficacy on average of all tools (diseases, pests, weeds, and 'other') indicates an efficacy on 35-50 %.

The cost in labour time is estimated to be 0,5-3,5 hours per hectare for pests and 'other', and for diseases and weeds the cost is estimated to be 3,5-7 hours per hectare. The cost in investments is estimated to be 1-17 % of the crop value per hectare. The estimated yield difference when using the tools compared to pesticide use is estimated to be neutral (-2-2 %) for diseases, pests, and 'other'. For weeds the effect is estimated to be positive (2-5 %). The impact on crop quality is found to be neutral (-2-2 %) for diseases and weeds and positive (2-5 %) for pests and 'other'.

The potential for pesticide reduction by use of the tools is expected to be 8-17 % for all categories of pests. The current level of implementation of the tools is estimated to be 20-35 % of the area with the 8 crops.

Table 3.66: Average scores across crops for seven different parameters divided on diseases, pests, weeds and 'other'. In Table 2.2 the ratings of different parameters with scores from 1-5 is explained.

Crop	Pest	Efficacy	Cost (labour)	Cost (investments)	Performance (yield)	Performance (quality)	Pesticide reduction	Implementation
Wine grape	Diseases	4	3	3	3	4	3	3
Olive	Diseases	4	3	3	3	3	3	3
Apple	Diseases	4	3	3	4	4	4	3
Strawberry	Diseases	3	3	2	3	3	3	3
Wheat	Diseases	4	2	2	4	3	3	4
Maize	Diseases	3	2	2	3	3	3	3
Potato	Diseases	3	2	2	3	3	2	3
Onion	Diseases	4	2	2	4	4	3	4
	Average	4	3	2	3	3	3	3
Wine grape	Pest	4	3	3	3	4	4	3
Olive	Pest	4	3	3	3	3	3	3
Apple	Pest	4	3	3	4	4	4	3
Strawberry	Pest	4	3	2	4	4	3	4
Wheat	Pest	3	1	2	3	3	3	3
Maize	Pest	4	2	2	3	3	3	3
Potato	Pest	3	2	1	3	3	2	3
Onion	Pest	4	2	2	4	4	3	4
	Average	4	2	2	3	4	3	3
Wine grape	Weeds	4	3	3	3	4	4	3
Olive	Weeds	4	3	3	3	3	3	3
Apple	Weeds	4	3	3	4	4	4	2
Strawberry	Weeds	4	3	2	4	4	4	4
Wheat	Weeds	4	2	1	3	3	3	3
Maize	Weeds	4	2	2	3	3	3	3
Potato	Weeds	4	2	2	3	3	2	3
Onion	Weeds	4	2	2	5	5	3	4
	Average	4	3	2	4	4	3	3
Wine grape	Other	5	2	3	3	4	3	4
Olive	Other	4	3	2	4	4	3	3
Apple	Other	4	3	3	4	4	4	3
Strawberry	Other	3	2	2	3	3	2	4
Wheat	Other	3	2	2	3	3	3	3
Maize	Other	4	2	2	3	3	3	3
Potato	Other	3	2	2	3	3	2	3
Onion	Other	4	2	2	4	4	3	4
	Average	4	2	2	3	4	3	3

4. Reflection

4.1 Discussion

The average scores for efficacy for all crops and pests indicate that the IPM tools in the inventory have a high efficacy going from 35-50%, table 3.66. The current implementation and use of the tools from the inventory were, on average, expected to cover approximately 20-35 % of the area which leaves room for further implementation.

The reduction of pesticide use is estimated to be between 8-17 % which is significant. The scores are the average of single tools. When more tools are used in combination or sequence, a higher reduction of the pesticide use may be expected as well as increased workload and expenses for investments.

It was expected that the use of the IPM tools and measures would be more labour consuming compared to pesticide use. On average, the estimation was 0,5-7 hours per hectare. The cost of investments was on average estimated to be 1-17% of the crop value per hectare which is a wide range. It may be difficult to estimate the cost of an investment since many tools, e.g., for mechanical weed control may be investments in machinery.

The impact of IPM tools on yield loss per hectare and loss of crop quality compared to the conventional use of pesticides were expected to be in the range from -2-5%, which is considered to be a small difference.

The scores for specific parameters in the tools were given by the contributors which are experts on the crops in their specific region and country, and the ratings of the tools reflect a national or local approach to the specific tool. The tools and ratings were typically provided by 1-3 partners countries per crop. There may be differences among countries and districts within a country which are not considered in this inventory. The inventory does not give the opportunity to compare the adoption of IPM in the same crop in different countries.

From the material in the inventory, it is not possible to state the reason why some tools are widely used, and others are not.

4.2 Recommendations

It is suggested that the tools listed in the current toolbox are used for bilateral talks with farmers or in discussions in larger farmer groups. The toolbox will be available on the project website. Focus on available IPM tools is expected to increase the interest for and adaption of IPM measures.

It is important that farmers and advisors have a website/APP on national/local or EU-level which is continuously updated and on which they can find a collection of the available IPM tools and measures on their specific crops. A platform could be constructed in a way that gives suggestions not only for a single crop, but for a rotation of crops both as a mean to cure problems, but also as a proactive tool that promotes more resilient crop rotations and cropping systems.

Increasing problems with resistance to herbicides, insecticides, or fungicides emphasise the importance of IPM measures to solve or reduce the negative impact of resistance. More extreme weather conditions also speak for the necessity for an integrated approach to crop cultivation. This includes IPM tools to improve the resilience of the cropping systems.

During the project period other parts of the SUPPORT project will provide data from surveys and interviews that should bring an overview of the barriers for the adoption of IPM and address how the adoption can be improved. Another task in the project is the development of a monitoring system for a holistic assessment of IPM tools and strategies. This tool is expected to support the best choice of IPM tools on a local and regional scale.

1. Appendix

1. Wine grape

Wine grape

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Warning System For Diseases

The prediction of fungal infections is a fundamental tool in the integrated pest management, as it makes it possible to anticipate the appearance of diseases and use effective prevention or control measures. There are different control methods:

- Models based on algorithms to predict the incidence and severity of fungal diseases. These models are based on climate variables, using historical climate records to generate predictions and warnings.
- Regular crop monitoring allows early signs on fungal diseases to be detected. Plants should be inspected for spots, lesions or other characteristics symptoms. Early prevention allows quick and effective control measures before the problem gets worse.
- Disease indexes and calendars based on historical records related to environmental conditions provide guidelines for scheduling preventives treatments.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Wine grape

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Other

Use Of Healthy Planting Material

The use of healthy plant materials is an important practice in integrated pest management, providing numerous benefits. Firstly, healthy plants are less susceptible to pests and diseases. A strong and vigorous plant has a greater ability to resist infestations of insects and diseases, which reduces the need for control interventions.

In addition, using healthy plant material prevents the introduction of pest and diseases into new crops. Pests are often spread by infected or infested plants, so starting with healthy plant material is an important preventive measure. Another key factor is maintaining an environment conducive to plant health. This involves ensuring a good plant nutrition, providing optimal conditions and promoting diversity in agricultural system. Healthy and equilibrate soil favours the growth of strong and resistant plants, which reduce the probability of pest and diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/GUIAUADETRANSFORMACION_tcm30-57934.pdf
https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/GUIAUADETRANSFORMACION_tcm30-57934.pdf

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Wine grape

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Precision Applications Using Drones

Precision applications using drones.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://upcommons.upc.edu/bitstream/handle/2117/343720/Preprints_articulo2.pdf?sequence=1

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Anti-drift Nozzles In The Spraying Machinery

The use of anti-drift nozzles is a recommended practice in integrated pest management, especially when plant protection products are used. These nozzles are designed to reduce the drift of sprayed products during the application, minimizing the risk of environmental contamination and exposure to undesirable targets and crops. The drift occurs when the spray droplets drift away from the intended application target and into undesirable areas, such as water bodies, residential area, or neighbouring crops. This type of nozzles produces larger and heavier droplets, which are less likely to be moved by air and may fall closer to the intended target.

It is important to follow the manufacturer’s recommendations to nozzle size, and correctly adjust working pressure and forward speed to achieve adequate coverage. Avoid weather conditions with high winds which increase the risk of drift.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Phytosanitary Warning System Networks

The network for warning and information about phytosanitary products is a measure e.g. included in the National Action Plan in Spain to promote integrated pest management and achieve a demand based use of phytosanitary products, facilitating decision-making. An administration coordinates them, and are the regions who are responsible for their organisation and management (Aragón, Andalucía, etc).

These networks pursue the following objectives:

- To build a system in which all product are integrated, and the means that allow coordinated actions to be carried out related to plant health.
- Underpin, under the guidelines established in phytosanitary programmes developed by competent authorities, a surveillance system to ensure integrated pest management.
- To contribute, through experiments and innovation, to the implementation of solutions to alleviate the health problems affecting crops and new controls methods.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Wine grape
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Traps e.g Monitoring And Control Of The Grapevine Moth (*Lobesia botrana*)

The mass trapping is an integrated pest management strategy to control insect populations in the adults stage in an effective and sustainable way. It consists of the installation of traps or a specific device in the affected environment. The main objective of this system is to monitor the pest population to tolerable levels without relying heavily on pesticides or other more aggressive control methods. The system is based on the knowledge of natural behaviour of insects, adapting each trap to each type of insect.

In Spanish vineyards, this measure is being used against *Lobesia botrana* (Grapevine moth). The traps vary according to the species and the specific conditions of environment: sticky traps, light traps, sex pheromone traps or other types of traps are used. A strategy is based on trapping male insects. If a significant number is trapped a population calculation can be done, and if a threshold is achieved a phytosanitary treatment is done. Therefore, these traps should be placed strategically in areas where the pest is most problematic.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Biological Pest Control In Wine Grape

In addition to the extensive use of traps for monitoring population of grapevine moths (*Lobesia botrana*), some other techniques within “biological pest control” can be applied. In the case of *Lobesia*, sexual confusion can diminish reproductive performance of the pest. The use of selected cover crops or flower margins between wine rows can act as home of useful parasitoids that predate wine pests. In the *Phytoseiidae* family members such as *Typhlodromus pyri*, *T. phialatus* or *T. kampinodromus* are effective against other harmful mites (*Acarus*).

Against Piral (*Phylloxera*), the release of commercial boxes containing green lacewings (*Chrysopa*), ladybirds (*Coccinella*) and others are effective.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/GUIAUADETRANSFORMACION_tcm30-57934.pdf

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

2. Olive

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Method Of Harvesting

During the olive harvest, all practices which may cause wounds in woody tissues (the point of entry of pathogens), should be avoided, in particular when the temperature and humidity conditions are favorable to Knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*) infection.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Removal Of Infected Material

To avoid the spread of infections and lower the quantity of inoculum, especially in the presence of attacks of Knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*) or Verticillium, the infected branches must be quickly removed and eliminated by burning. Take care to sterilize the tools used with sodium hypochlorite or copper sulphate in the passage from one plant to another.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Treatment After Pruning

Since penetration of the bacterium *Pseudomonas savastanoi*, agent of the Knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*) in all the epigeal organs, particularly twigs, branches and trunks, occurs through the openings, it is important to disinfect the cut surfaces after each pruning operation. Similar treatments must also be carried out after particular meteoric events, for example hailstorms, which can injure the woody organs constituting an entry point for the pathogen.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Windbreaks

The use of windbreaks is essential to avoid damage and micro-lesions on the woody organs which can constitute access points for various types of pathogens and in particular, in the case of the olive tree, the bacteria causing Knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*). Live windbreaks, represented by trees and hedges of various kinds, also play an agroecological role, but dead windbreaks, represented by barriers, can also be useful for crop protection.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Healthy Plant Material

The use of healthy plant materials is an important practice in integrated pest management, providing numerous benefits. Firstly, healthy plants are less susceptible to pests and diseases. A strong and vigorous plant has a greater ability to resist infestations by insects and diseases, which reduces the need for control interventions. In addition, using healthy plant material prevents the introduction of pests and diseases into a new crops. Pests are often spread by infected or infested plants, so starting with healthy plant material is an important preventive measure. Another key factor is maintaining an environment conducive to plant health. This involves ensuring a good plant nutrition, providing optimal conditions and promoting diversity in the agricultural system. Healthy and equilibrated soil favours the growth of strong and resistant plants, which reduce the probability of pests and diseases.

The use of certified planting material will optimize the efficiency of selecting planting sites for establishing new orchards, and is crucial, not only to ensure the identity of the olive variety or the quality of the plant, but also its health. The use of certified material from officially licensed producers is particularly important to avoid later problems associated with scales (*Saissetia oleae*), mealybugs and other biting sucking insects, or pathogens that cause systemic infections, which can remain asymptomatic in the plant for several months or years after planting until the appearance of symptoms such as is the case of *V. dahliae* and *Xylella fastidiosa*. However, the experts pointed out that an appropriate certification scheme and legislation for olive crops is lacking. They also noted that sometimes farmers prefer to save money by buying cheaper plants, despite the fact that the plants may not be guaranteed to be healthy and free of pests. To limit potential problems due to lack of good phytosanitary status, and until a certification system is developed for olives, farmers should acquire the planting material only from nurseries that are properly accredited and registered, since they are the only ones that are subjected to inspection.

IPM principles:

Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage

Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou, Juan Sagarna, Giuseppina Las Casas

<https://www.kostelenosfytoria.gr/olive-trees-production-kostelenos-nurseries.html>

Photo: Left: Rooted Olive Cutting. Right: Young olive tree in pot.

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Biological Control

Biological management is the process of reducing a pest population by using predators, parasites and beneficial insects that ordinarily occur in nature. For example, certain predatory mites, ladybugs, lacewings and parasitic wasps can effectively control pests like olive fruit flies (*Bactrocera oleae*) and scale insects. The greatest single factor in keeping plant-feeding insects from overwhelming the rest of the world is that they are food for other insects. There are also more than one hundred olive pathogens, although only a few of them cause serious economic losses on olive groves.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev-ento-010814-021005> , chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.aua.gr/tsili/e-serv_public/COMPAG_2012.pdf

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Canopy Management

The correct management of the canopy involves an appropriate pruning, the choice of appropriate planting distances and maintaining the training form. These practices allow the canopy to ventilate and avoid the formation of a microclimate favourable to the development of pathogens, in particular *Spilocaea oleaginea* (Peacock eye spot), *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *C. acutatum*, *Glomerella cingulata* (Anthracnose olives) and *Mycocentrospora cladosporioides* (Cercospora leaf spot) and insects such as Black scale (*Saissetia oleae*), olive psyllid (*Euphyllura olivina*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Choice Of Cultivar

The varietal tradition of the olive tree is extremely wide and among the various aspects to consider for the choice of the cultivar, it's important to address the susceptibility to pathogens and insects in the cultivation area. There are morphological aspects to consider, which make some cultivars more subject to parasitic attacks (i.e. the olive fly prefers large, spherical and hard drupes) and genetic factors (i.e. different degrees of varietal susceptibility to peacock eye (*Spilocaea oleaginea*) or olive Knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*). Other aspects for the correct variety selection, that can limit the use of chemical control methods, concern the phenology and particularly the maturation period for the possibility of carrying out an early harvest to minimize the damage of the fly and the moth.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Disease-resistant Olive Cultivars

The use and selection of resistant cultivars or rootstocks is the best long-term and economically efficient control measure for controlling many diseases and some pests of olives, and should be at the core of IPM strategies. The experts indicate that although there are many olive tree varieties around the world, the main criteria taken into account when choosing a variety for planting is the previous knowledge of the variety in the region, farmers prefer to continue planting what they know. Normally, the main factor to select a variety is the productivity and environmental adaptation. In areas where the olive oil produced locally has a “certified” or “protected” designation of origin, farmers may be required to use a specific local variety or a combination of varieties. The choice of a tolerant cultivar makes IPM easier and can reduce production costs by reducing chemical inputs and the costs of other control measures. When chemical control is not possible, the use of resistance/tolerance is one of the few options.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	5
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_fg_pests_diseases_olive_tree_final_report_2020_en.pdf

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photo: George Kokkinos.

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Resistant Varieties

The resistant varieties from the commercial plant seeding, including a certificate of the healthy and proper qualities of the plant.

Some plants can have a symbiosis with mycorrhizal fungi. This symbiosis between fungus and plant roots gives biofertilizer, biofortifying, bio-stimulant and bioprotective capabilities. It requires a great technical capacity so the mycorrhization must be of the highest quality.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://revistaalmaceite.com/2018/03/06/jose-miguel-barea-csic-es-de-esperar-que-las-micorrizas-permitan-limitar-el-efecto-vecero-propio-del-cultivo-del-olivo/>

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Monitoring And Early Diagnosis

Phytophages and pathogens must be kept under control with constant monitoring. When the damage threshold is exceeded (for phytophagous), it is necessary to intervene with products permitted by the production regulations (integrated or organic). For diseases caused by fungi on leaves, in particular for Peacock leaf spot (*Spilocaea oleaginea*), it is necessary to intervene in a preventive way, on the basis of an early diagnosis of the presence of pathogenic agents to avoid damage to plants or fruits. The following are used: pheromone traps, sticky traps or light traps.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Olive Grove Fertilization

Correct fertilization in olive groves must be organized with three-year plans by distributing the necessary fertilizing units on the basis of the soil's endowment in macro and microelements and absorption by the plants for the production of fruits and vegetative organs. Soil analysis and foliar diagnostics of plants should be performed. The analysis must be carried out both before planting the olive grove and in the following period every 3-4 years. The preferred fertilization is the organic one with the use of manure, compost, green manure of legumes, etc.

IPM principles:	Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Precision Applications Using Drones

Precision applications using drones.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://upcommons.upc.edu/bitstream/handle/2117/343720/Preprints_articulo2.pdf?sequence=1

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Pruning

Olive tree pruning is a very demanding and expensive agronomic practice due to the need for specialized labour. It serves to favour a good vegetative-productive relationship and avoid uncontrolled growth of the foliage with consequent non-optimization of space and difficulties in harvesting, both mechanized and manual.

These practices allow the canopy to ventilate and avoid the formation of a microclimate favourable to the development of pathogens, in particular *Spilocaea oleaginea* (Peacock eye spot), *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Colletotrichum acutatum*, *Glomerella cingulata* (Anthracnose olives) and *Mycocentrospora cladosporioides* (Cercospora leaf spot) and insects such as Black scale (*Saissetia oleae*) and olive psyllid (*Euphyllura olivina*).

It is important to avoid severe wounds and protect the injuries to decrease the incidence of pests and diseases. In addition, pruning the branches which have been infested may help to reduce inoculum of pests and diseases, but it is very important to manage the pruning remains adequately so as not to favour the increase of olive bark beetles or the spread of pathogens (e.g., *V. dahliae*). For example, in Sicily (Italy), the branches from pruning (performed within 20 days after the harvest) are left in the field as a trap for the pest *Phloeotribus scarabaeoides* (Olive bark beetle), and once the beetle is found, they are burnt.

Pruning in intensive systems must be performed from the ground with telescopic tools, in uniform olive groves, given the large dimensions reached by the plants, it is necessary to resort to the aid of platforms with self-propelled baskets to guarantee the safety of the operators. In high-density plants, total mechanization of pruning is used with cutter bars mounted on tractors.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa, Vicky Inglezou

Photo: George Kokkinos

Spraying And Targeted Treatments

Spraying and targeted treatments are important components of pest and disease management in olive orchards. They are primarily aimed at controlling pests and diseases that commonly affect olive trees, such as the olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*), olive moth (*Prays oleae*), diseases like olive anthracnose (*Colletotrichum*), olive knot (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*) and other bacterial diseases. When pest populations exceed the established threshold, targeted pesticide applications may be necessary. However, the emphasis is on judicious and selective use of pesticides, adhering to strict guidelines and regulations, and choosing products with the least impact on non-target organisms and the environment. The timing of spraying and targeted treatments depends on the specific pest or disease being targeted. Monitoring and regular field observations help determine the optimal timing for treatments.

Targeted treatments involve localized applications to specific areas of the tree or specific pest hot spots.

Spraying and targeted treatments are often employed as part of an IPM approach in olive orchards that combines various strategies, including cultural practices, biological control, and the judicious use of pesticides.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

The Use Of Kaolin In Olive Groves

The use of kaolin in olive groves represents an integration of the technical means used to contain the attack of *Bactrocera oleae* (olive fruit fly). The spraying, with the aid of common nebulizers, forms a protective barrier on the vegetation. A good protective film must have some fundamental requisites, i.e. be chemically inert, with particles with a diameter of less than 2 µm, formulated in such a way as to create a uniform layer which alters and hinders the behavior of the insect on the plant without however interfering with the exchanges of vegetable gases. The compound mostly used for this purpose is kaolin, an aluminum silicate in the form of a fine white non-porous and non-expandable powder easily dispersible in water, chemically inert in a wide pH range.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Photo: Nileas

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Irrigation

The olive tree is a xerophilous plant adapted to the Mediterranean climate, even if traditional plants generally do not have irrigation systems, in modern olive growing irrigation is organized in the same way as for other orchard plants. Proper irrigation management increases productivity and drupe quality. Among the possible irrigation systems, the fixed ones and in particular those with microflow (drip or spray) are preferable. In fact, these offer numerous advantages for the high efficiency of water use, for the maintenance of water availability close to the capacity of the field, for the non-wetting of the leaves of the trees, which could favor the infestations of some pathogens and for the containment of the development of weeds, as only small portions of soil are wetted.

Irrigation volumes and shifts vary according to the water balance calculated with the help of the pluviograph and the crop indices.

Adequate management of irrigation (frequency and doses) may help to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases. In the case of soils infected by *Verticillium dahliae* (Verticillium Wilt of Olive) in which a susceptible variety is planted, daily irrigation resulted in greater Verticillium wilt development than plants irrigated weekly, bi-weekly (with the same amount of water), or with deficit irrigation.

In several olive orchards, rational use of irrigation water management and irrigation networks in combination with adequate ground management is very important for the management of the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*). However, sometimes management of irrigation is difficult due to water scarcity, or the allocation of a specific time (days and hours) to the farmer for irrigation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/13/14/1954>

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou, Cinzia Benincasa

Photo: George Kokkinos

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Forecasting Systems

Forecasting systems are used to identify the risk level linked to the attack of a pest or a disease and to decide the tool and moment to apply some management practice mainly a plant protection product, which is usually an insecticide for pest control (i.e., pyrethroids for *B. oleae*), or copper for some pathogens (*V. oleagina*, *P. syringae pv. syringae*). These forecasting systems have been or are being developed for some pests (*B. oleae*) and (*C. oleaginum*) olive diseases (eg. Petazzi et al., 2002; Romero et al., 2018). Nowadays, the availability of Information Technology (IT) tools such as wireless sensors to constantly monitor climatic and vegetation data will enable the implementation of precision plant protection techniques in some regions/farms. The experts pointed out that although IT tools are available in several EU regions, they are rarely used directly by the olive farmers since the availability of weather stations, climatic sensors, and some expertise in the interpretation of data is needed. However, the experts believe that in the near future these tools will increasingly be used by advisory services.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/14/23/5951>

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photo: George Kokkinos

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Others

Avoid Wounds On The Trunks

If wounds on the trunks are not treated it could become an entryway for pest and disease vectors. This wound provides an easy entry to pathogens and insects, which can result in significant damage to the plant. Some key practices are shown below:

Prevention of wounds in trunks; this includes practices such as avoiding damages in trunks during tillage and keeping a security distance around the trunks to avoid mechanical damage.

Sealing wounds, if they occur, to prevent them from becoming an entry point for pests and diseases. This sealing can be done using resin-based products or healing putty.

Physical protection, especially in young trees or those located in areas with high pest pressure, by physical protectors placed around the trunks to prevent damage. This protection is usually netting or barriers.

Proper plant maintenance, including irrigation, balanced nutrition and weed control can improve plants' health and reduce their susceptibility to pests and diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Agroecological Support Structures

The application of agroecological principles in the olive grove provides a conservative management of the soil, combined with vegetal corridors in the interrow (support crops of various kinds) and agroecological infrastructures, the latter consisting of a spontaneous non-productive vegetable component. This type of management involves an increase in functional biodiversity, therefore of arthropod fauna and useful insects as well as natural enemies, representing a proactive measure to reduce the entity of future outbreaks of parasites. Other advantages of eco-sustainability of the culture concern the soil conditions being more favorable to the growth and development of plants through the management of organic matter and the increase in biological activity, the better use of energy, water, nutrients and last but not least the maintenance of genetic resources.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Anti-drift Nozzles on Sprayers

The use of anti-drift nozzles is a recommended practice in integrated pest management, especially when chemical products are used in applications. These nozzles are designed to reduce the drift of sprayed products during the application, minimizing the risk of environmental contamination and exposure to unwanted crops and targets.

The drift occurs when the spray droplets drift away from the intended application and into undesirable areas, such as the mass of water, residential areas, or neighbouring crops. This type of nozzles produces larger and heavier droplets, which are less likely to be windblown and may fall closer to the intended target.

It is important to follow the manufacturer's recommendations and correctly adjust nozzle size, working pressure and forward speed to achieve adequate coverage. Also, it is recommended to avoid adverse weather conditions, such as high winds that may increase the risk of drift.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Choice Of The Olive Grove

The choices in the plant are fundamental because in any case they are largely definitive. Management has no lesser impact on the productive and economic results of the olive grove agronomic in all its aspects. Among the factors to consider in choosing the area in which to build a new olive grove are: Altitude, exposure, slope, temperature and rainfall. Soils with high clay content and low permeability should be avoided. Such conditions can increase the risk of waterlogging in the flat areas of the olive grove if an adequate system of groundwater drainage is not guaranteed.

When choosing the varieties to be used for the creation of a new olive grove it is preferable to favor the autochthonous ones which are the result of a selection process that lasted even hundreds of years and is more suitable for specific pedo-climatic conditions.

Land preparation is essential to create the best conditions for the seedlings to take root and for the successful cultivation of the olive tree.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage;
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Distribution Of Pesticides

The first tool that is simple, cheap and can also be adopted aftermarket on atomizers is the anti-drift nozzle. Different from traditional ones and with a greater length due to the presence of an integrated turbulence chamber - produces homogeneous drops by decreasing the percentage of small drops, which are subject to drift.

The improvement of the distribution of pesticides through the regulation of the equipment must be done in a workmanlike manner: The energy of the drops must be exhausted inside the leaf mass to minimize the dispersion of the product in the environment (drift). Nozzle calibration must be performed periodically to ensure: spray under pressure, spray speed, and spray volume. Modern equipment is designed to guarantee greater precision in the distribution of the product. Common to all sprayers, the low-volume spraying technology reduces crop and water consumption, ensuring greater plant coverage.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up;
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Monitoring And Scouting

Monitoring is very important in IPM. This is because the mere presence of a particular pest does not provide enough information for decision-making. The pest or disease may not be sufficiently widespread, or the population levels may not cause enough damage, to warrant undertaking management strategies. Regular monitoring of olive orchards, with an effective recording of the results, helps identify pest populations and disease outbreaks early on. This involves visually inspecting trees, leaves, fruits, and the surrounding environment for signs of pests or damage. Thus, olive tree cultivators have at their disposal important information that helps in making decisions on whether and when action should be taken, and how effective actions have been. The first step is to concentrate on the most serious pests and diseases and keep records about the times and locations where problems are most likely to occur. Since natural enemies play an integral role in the system, they also need to be recorded.

IPM principles:

**Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives;
Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up**

Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photo: Vicky Inglezou

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Monitoring Climatic Parameters

Use the agro-meteorological network and install company tools capable of monitoring climatic parameters like rain, temperature, humidity, wind, etc., that are essential in choosing the correct agronomic practices. The fight against the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*), the main parasite of the olive grove, must not be practiced for example when the temperature is higher than 30 degrees (thermal threshold) even if the catches on the traps exceed the limit threshold.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Agroecological Practices

Agroecology is related to a set of practices and management operations based on ecological principles and nature-based processes which involve the whole agri-food system and food supply chains, including socioeconomic, cultural, and political strategies. Some of these principles and strategies include, among others: a) taking advantage of the positive interactions, complementarity, and synergies among elements (plants, animals, soil, air, water, and humans) of the agroecosystems; b) reducing the dependency on external inputs (pesticides and synthetic products) and non-renewable sources; c) recycling and closing cycles of nutrients and biomass; d) maintaining and promoting biodiversity; e) supporting adaptation and resilience to climate changes; e) promoting fair remuneration for agricultural production and agroecosystem services; f) fostering stewardship and participation in agrifood supply chain decision-making.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://inuouja.com/en/sustainability/agroecology-applied-to-the-olive-grove/>
https://oa.upm.es/11123/1/PALOMA_BENGOCHEA_BUDIA.pdf

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photos: Internet (<https://communities.springernature.com/posts/make-olive-groves-green-again>)

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Crushing Materials From Pruning

Crushing and incorporation into the soil as mulch of olive tree pruning waste promotes nutrient retention and provides habitats for the edaphic community, resulting in an increase in biodiversity. In addition, it increases soil organic matter and other indicators of soil fertility and contributes to carbon sequestration in soil.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1164556316300346>

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photos: George Kokkinos

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Compost And Organic Matter

Compost and organic matter improve soil health. Healthy soils support strong, disease-resistant plants that are less susceptible to pest attacks.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-5904-0_8

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photos: George Kokkinos

Olive

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Direct Control And Intervention When Needed

Direct control and intervention when needed based on the selection of one or more management options on the basis of monitoring results and action thresholds (Intervention), giving priority to a wide range of non-pesticide options.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.internationaloliveoil.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Olivicultura_eng.pdf

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photos: Top, right: Olive Leaf Spot (*Spilocaea Oleaginea*)Internet. Bottom, left: Fly trap “KarateTrap” by Syngenta; right: Other type of fly trap.

(Top <https://www.kosnews24.gr/koinwnika/item/262797-ksekinoy-n-oi-dolomatikoi-psekasmoi-ton-elaiodendron-gia-tin-katapolemisi-tou-dakou-se-rodo-ko-kaso-lero-astypalaia-kai-tilo>;
<https://www.tiroqaverd.com/en/blog/olive-leaf-spot-spilocaea-oleagina-n62>; Bottom:
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/epp.12922>; <https://www.e-agroland.gr/en/store-en/pesticides>)

Cultural Management

Keeping olive trees healthy and preventing plant stress helps trees to better withstand and repair the damage caused by pests, diseases, weeds, etc. Evidence indicates that healthy olive orchards resist infestation by pests better than olive orchards with low vigor. The most effective and most important of all practices is to observe what is going on on the farm. Many serious disease or pest problems can be halted or slowed by regularly visiting the olive orchard, knowing what to look for, recognizing potential problems, and intervening early. Cultural/traditional methods play a crucial role in managing pests and diseases. Techniques such as proper orchard sanitation, pruning, and maintaining optimal tree nutrition and irrigation help promote tree health and vigor, making them less susceptible to pests and diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_fg_pests_diseases_olive_tree_final_report_2020_en.pdf

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photos: Vicky Inglezou

Phytosanitary Alerts Networks

The network of alerts and information on phytosanitary products is a measure included in the National Action Plan to promote integrated pest management and achieve a rational use of phytosanitary products, facilitating decision-making. The administration only has the duty to coordinate them, and it is the regions who are responsible for their organisation and management (Aragón, Andalucía, etc).

These networks pursue the following objectives: to build a system in which all agents are integrated, and the means that allow coordinated actions related to plant health to be carried out. To underpin, under the guidelines established in phytosanitary programmes developed by competent authorities, a surveillance system to ensure integrated pest management has to be included.

To contribute, through experiments and innovation, to the implementation of solutions to alleviate the health problems affecting crops and new control methods.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Biological Pest Control

In olive trees, the release of *Chrysopa* larvae in the case of olive moth is well documented. Reservoir plants that attract natural enemies such as phytoseiidae (acarisation), *Anthocoris* (aranuelo) are good options. Mass olive fly trapping can help reduce populations to an acceptable level. The management of vegetation covers can help control weeds such as pinillos (*Conyza*). There are also natural extracts (Vidi Fol) against repilo bacteria.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/productos-fitosanitarios/guias-gestion-plagas/olivar/default.aspx>

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Natural Insecticide In The Control Of *Bactrocera oleae*

Spinosad is a natural insecticide with a broad spectrum of action, used to contain olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) infestations in organic olive groves. It is extracted from the products of the metabolism of artificial crops of the telluric actinomycete *saccharopolyspora spinosa*. From a chemical point of view, the active principle is constituted by the mixture of two toxins produced by the metabolism of the actinomycete, called, respectively, spinosin A and spinosin D. Both toxins belong to a category of substances with biocidal activity, still little known, called generically spinosoids or spinosines. Spinosad should not be applied as a normal treatment but in a particular way and with very small volumes of water. The jet must be directed towards the areas of the canopy with less presence of fruit. The recommended technology is the one that uses a nozzle capable of producing a single jet or splash.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Pest Monitoring And Intervention Thresholds

Every defense strategy must be based on the monitoring of pathogens to identify the thresholds that justify an intervention. For the olive fly, it is the active infestation in the drupes that allows us to quantify the damage. To identify the moment of intervention, 100 olives are examined under a stereomicroscope, adopting intervention thresholds of 15-20% of active infestation (presence of eggs, the presence of live eggs and larvae of different ages of the diptera) in July, increasing the thresholds as we get closer to harvesting. The monitoring carried out directly on the olives, identifying the live stages and the exit holes of the diptera, allows you to always have a precise picture of the progress of the infestation; in this way the olive grower, in addition to intervening only when necessary, can also evaluate the real risk of loss due to fruit drop and plan the harvest. For the monitoring of the moth, pheromone traps are used to detect the trend of the male flights, but since the correlation between catches and risk of infestation in the fruits is very low, the only valid monitoring technique remains the sampling of the olivines for evaluate the extent of the infestation in order to predict the autumn drop. Prudential thresholds are 10-15% of infestation for oil cultivars.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	0
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas

Pheromone Traps

Pheromone traps are used to monitor and manage specific pests in olive orchards in Greece, primarily the olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*). The traps utilize synthetic versions of the female olive fruit fly's sex pheromones to attract and capture male insects, disrupting their mating patterns and reducing pest populations. Traps are strategically placed throughout the olive orchard. Their number and placement density depend on various factors (size of the orchard, pest pressure and regional recommendations). Traps are regularly monitored to assess pest populations and activity levels. The captured insects are counted and identified to determine the population dynamics and timing of pest emergence. The timing of trap deployment is crucial to coincide with the peak activity of the targeted pest. By capturing male olive fruit flies, the traps provide an indication of the presence and intensity of the pest population, allowing growers to implement control measures when necessary.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/read/19121718/attract-and-kill-of-the-olive-fruit-fly-bactrocera-oleae-in-greece-as-a->

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Technical Means To Fight *Bactrocera oleae*

Technical means for the mass capture of the olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*), both in integrated and organic olive growing is with the aid of special traps, i.e. a polyethylene bag (15 x 20 cm) containing a food attractant (ammonium bicarbonate) for males and females of *B. oleae*, coated on the outside with a special paper treated with a pyrethroid insecticide (0.0019 g deltamethrin/trap). A dispenser containing the sex pheromone is supplied with the bag. Another type is a laminated panel to be fixed on a branch of the plant. The surface is pretreated with Lambda-Cyhalothrin. The particular methods of transfer of the active principle allow the trap to maintain the insecticide action unchanged throughout the season (from June to November). The attractants are fixed on the panel: sexual based on pheromones and food based on ammonium salts.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Monitoring Olive Flies And Prays Olive Moths

Mc Phail Traps or chromotropic Traps are used to monitor the population of targeted insects, the most important in the olive orchard being olive fruit flies (*Bactrocera oleae*) and Prays olive moths (*Prays oleae*). The treatment would only be advisable if a certain threshold of the pest population is achieved. For instance, the appearance of adults in traps for a specific focus spot application using Mc Phails Traps.

It allows also to correlate populations of pests with other external conditions as meteorological or phenological conditions.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/productos-fitosanitarios/guias-gestion-plagas/olivar/default.aspx>

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Use Of Mycorrhizae

Mycorrhizas in olive growing, as well as all the other components of the microbiota, have been shown to have benefits on plant growth and also on the induction of resistance and tolerance to abiotic stresses. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) colonize the roots of plants and they diffuse into the surrounding loose soil improving nutrient uptake from the soil to the plant and stimulating the transfer of photosynthesis from the plant to the soil. The importance of this symbiotic association in agroecosystems is related to a growing attention to management sustainability and to the role of these systems as carbon dioxide (CO₂) sinks.

The plants must come inoculated with mycorrhiza from commercial plant seeding companies, including a certificate of the healthy and proper qualities of the plant. The symbiosis between the fungus and root gives biofertilizer, biofortifying, biostimulant and bioprotective capabilities. It requires a great technical capacity to inoculate so the mycorrhization must be of the highest quality.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa, Juan Sagarna

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests; Weeds
Trap Crops

Specific crops that pests prefer in order to draw them away from the main crop. This can help protect the primary crop from infestation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.enicbcmed.eu/artolio-presents-how-grow-olive-trees-without-using-chemicals-beginners-guide>

Contributed by: Vicky Inglezou

Photo: Olives planted with daisies.

(<https://www.oliviadaolive.com/best-companion-plants-for-olive-trees/>)

Cover Crops

The use of cover crops in the autumn-winter period reduces or eliminates the inconveniences related to soil processing and chemical weeding and improves the agro-ecological characteristics of the olive grove, which thus acquires a greater equilibrium and stability, with a consequent reduction of external inputs and environmental and health risks. Advantages related mainly at ground level with an increase in organic matter, an improvement in the structure and protection of the soil from erosion with greater water infiltration, the cover crops always have a cleansing effect by lowering weed pressure and can have further beneficial effects: repellent action for soil pathogens, if essences of the Brassicaceae family are used, nutritional benefits using the Fabaceae which enrich the soil with nitrogen. At the end of the cycle, the grass can be shredded or flattened to form an organic mulch or buried with the practice of green manure.

Cover cropping or vegetation cover in olive orchards is an environmentally friendly and sustainable practice. It is a mantle of herbs that covers the ground surrounding the olive trees. It is the most important measure for the protection of the soil against erosion, one of the main problems of the olive grove throughout the Mediterranean basin. On the one hand, it protects the soil from the direct impact of raindrops (soil disintegration), and on the other it acts as a filter against the sun rays, preventing the evaporation of water. It constitutes a physical barrier for the flow of surface water when there is a slope, which causes gullies where there is no grass cover on the surface of the crops. Cover crops can also enhance soil biodiversity and create habitats for natural enemies of some pests.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas, Vicky Inglezou

Photo: Vicky Inglezou

Olive
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Grassing Of Olive Groves

Grassing is an agronomic practice with low environmental impact for the control of weeds in the inter-row of olive groves. The chemical-physical and microbiological characteristics of the soil have improved thanks to the lower consumption of organic matter. An increase in practicability at any time year after year, even with moist soil, facilitates the execution of crop practices.

Sloping terrains are better protected from the risk of erosion thanks to the combination of two factors: on the one hand, the better permeability of the terrain favors the infiltration of water, on the other, the turf reduces the runoff of surface water. Turf together with pruning residues increases soil fertility.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Mulch Along The Olive Grove Row

Organic mulching consists of covering the ground in the spring-summer period with dead materials of an organic nature and has a weed control effect because it prevents the emergence of plants, as well as limiting soil evaporation. This type of mulching can be achieved at the end of a controlled grassing, thanks to the shredding or flattening of the crops. In non-grassed olive orchards, a mulch can be made using pruning residues which, at the end of winter, are shredded and left to cover the soil. Organic mulching increases soil organic matter and returns nutrients, it improves soil treatability, and helps maintain water content in the top-soil layers.

The sub-row of the olive grove can be managed conservatively with the mulching technique.

Organic materials are distributed along the rows: straw, processing by-products, wood shavings, etc. Mulching can also be done with plastic or biodegradable material with the aim of controlling the growth of weeds. Organic materials, thanks to their biodegradability, can represent a valid alternative to plastic materials, performing the same mulching function and with the advantage of not having recovery and disposal costs, once their turf containment action is finished during the first few years from the plant.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Giuseppina Las Casas, Cinzia Benincasa

3. Apple

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease

Removal Of Apple Mummies To Prevent Blackrot

Blackrot (*Botryosphaeria obtusa*) is a fungal disease of apples. The fungus hibernates on fruit mummies, and thus mainly occurs on apple cultivars that keep their mummies for a long time, like Elstar. In a three year research project the effects of the removal of fruit mummies as an infection source were studied. The results are promising: the infection rate of harvested apples is reduced by 60 – 90%.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
***Aureobasidium pullulans* To Improve Storability**

Treatment with the antagonistic yeast *Aereobasidium pullulans* prevents the infection by pathogens such as *Penicillium* sp., causing e.g. Penicillium rot, and *Botrytis* sp., e.g. causing gray mold, and hence improves storage of fruit.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Biological Control: Application Of Microorganisms To Avoid Storage Problems And Fire Blight

Biological agents based on microorganisms are used, e.g. inducers of resistance to reduce the occurrence of diseases such as fire blight (*Erwinia amylovora*) and storage diseases. Management of fire blight is complicated by limitations on use of antibiotics in agriculture, i.e. antibiotic resistance development, and limited efficacy of alternative control agents. Even though successful in control, preventive antibiotic sprays also affect non-target bacteria, aiding the selection for resistance which could ultimately be transferred to the pathogen *Erwinia amylovora*. Trunk injection is a target-precise pesticide delivery method that utilizes tree xylem to distribute injected compounds. Trunk injection could decrease antibiotic usage in the open environment and increase the effectiveness of compounds in fire blight control. In case of storage diseases one of the major issues is *Penicillium expansum* Link., the causal agent of apple blue mold. It can cause severe loss of stored fruit. The BCAs and chemical inducers of resistance have direct effects against *P. expansum*, significantly reducing the percentages of infection and/or lesion sizes when applied directly against this pathogen. The antifungal activities of acibenzolar-S-methyl, β -aminobutyric acid and methyl jasmonate were also confirmed *in vitro* against *P. expansum* and *Trichoderma atroviride* P1.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Joanna Puławska

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
Copper Products Application After Pruning

The use of copper for disease control on apples has always been viewed from two directions as the very positive disease-control benefits of coppers are counterbalanced with the risk of phytotoxicity to trees, most notably through russetting of apple fruit. Two major apple pathogens, the fire blight pathogen (*Erwinia amylovora*) and the apple scab pathogen (*Venturia inaequalis*), are highly sensitive to copper, and we have no reason to believe that copper is a material that is at risk for resistance development in either of these pathogens. Copper-containing fungicides have been widely used in agriculture for more than a century to control bacterial and fungal diseases of fruit, vegetable, nut-bearing and other crops, remaining the main group of products in the program to overcome resistance to systemic fungicides. Copper salts have an extremely small particle size, and the original formula creates an effective barrier against disease, working against direct contact with the pathogen. It is known that copper perhaps has various negative impacts on the environment, including the protected plant. Copper application is especially important in varieties susceptible to diseases of bark and wood like i.e. Gala. Copper products should be applied directly after winter pruning of trees with no risk to beneficial organisms.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
Crown Pruning

Proper pruning of trees is important to allow better crown clearance and airiness, which in turn reduces the wet period of leaves and fruit, thus preventing possible infections. With well-formed tree crowns, it is also possible to have an accurate spraying of the trees, which is particularly important for difficult diseases, which undoubtedly include scab (*Venturia inaequalis*). Good effectiveness of the treatments can be obtained only with good coverage of the entire tree with the preparation, including the apical part and proper penetration of the product into the crown.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease

Disease And Pest Forecasting

Apple scab (*Venturia inaequalis*) forecasting - the determination of term and size of *V. inaequalis* ascospore discharges, analysis of sporulation of scab fungus, and the occurrence of apple scab risk infection, using Burkard apparatus and forecasting models (eg. A-scab and MetApple *Venturia inaequalis*). Adaptation of spraying terms to the terms of infection risk.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

<https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/44725>

Contributed by: Joanna Puławska

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
Nitrogen Input

Use appropriate amounts of fertilisers, especially nitrogen. Too much fertilisation with this nutrient leads to increased susceptibility to diseases, prolonged period of vegetative growth, i.e. the presence of young growths, higher susceptibility to infections with pathogens like *Venturia inaequalis*, *Erwinia amylovora*, or *Podosphaera leucotricha*. Inadequate fertilisation can stimulate apple trees to grow stronger, also leading to crown thickening, which creates more favorable conditions for infection.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease

Post Harvest Fruit Chilling

Pre-refrigeration of fruit immediately after harvesting are useful strategies to control the growth of pathogens.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Maria Concetta Strano

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
Removal Of Infected Plants

Eradication of plant pathogen infections is very important for plant protection. The current strategy for eradication of a pathogen also relies on techniques for removal and disposal of affected host plants. This technique is recommended for the control of apple scab disease caused by the fungus *Venturia inaequalis*, which spreads by airborne spores and survives the winter on fallen leaves; Powdery mildew of apple (*Podosphaera leucotricha* (Ellis & Everh.) E. S. Salmon); and other fungal diseases (caused by e.g. *Nectria galligena*; *Sphaeropsis malorum*; *Phomopsis mali*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Maria Concetta Strano

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
Removing Of Apple Leaves (Debris) In Autumn

Apple scab, caused by *Venturia inaequalis*, is one of the world's most commercially significant apple diseases. The fungus has a catastrophic impact on apples, causing considerable losses in fruit quality and productivity in many apple-growing locations despite numerous control agents. During winter, the fungus survives in fallen leaves, infected fruit, and cankers on the orchard floor. These overwintering sources serve as a reservoir for inoculum for the upcoming growing season. Various alternative and complementary control measures that are part of integrated orchard management have been developed and used for apple scab control. Ascospore production in fallen leaves has been targeted by sanitation treatments, including plowing or leaf removal, or by enhanced decomposition of leaves, including treatment with urea, dolomitic lime, sugar beet pulp (vinasse), molasses, fungal antagonists, and shredding of leaf litter.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Puławska

The Application Of 1-MCP As A Post-harvest Treatment

Fruit ripening is defined as a set of physiological processes involving physical, chemical and biochemical changes that increase the attractiveness and palatability of fruit. These changes include: skin color (change of basic color from green to yellow due to chlorophyll breakdown and simultaneous condensation of carotenoids), firmness (softening of tissues due to weakening of connections between flesh cells), flavor (hydrolysis of starch to simple sugars and simultaneous decrease in organic acids), and aroma (secretion of aromatic volatile compounds). The rate of these transformations is largely influenced by ethylene. Since fruits are living organisms, they also transpire and respire after harvest, resulting in a gradual loss of quality, which depends, among other things, on the variety, harvest date, post-harvest treatment of apples and storage conditions. Initially it was thought that ethylene only initiates the ripening of apples, but later studies show that it also plays an important role in maintaining this process. Apples ripening is associated with a large increase in ethylene production, which is typical for climacteric fruit. 1-MCP belongs to the group of growth regulators, and is a substance in the group of cyclopropene derivatives. It is available as a powder contained in water-soluble sachets. When mixed with water, the active substance is released and enters the tissues of the apple.

The use of products containing 1-MCP makes it possible to maintain the high firmness of apples, delay their over-ripening processes, and reduce the occurrence of surface scald in regular cold storage or in KA. The agent also inhibits the production of ethylene in the fruit, as well as any processes that occur under the influence of ethylene in the environment. The use of 1-MCP as SmartFresh and Harvista for better storage and shelf-life of apples is a common practice among farmers. It enables better protection for storage problems like bitter pit, storage breakdown; better storage regarding the skin quality and tenderness of the flesh.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease

Prevention Of Storage Diseases

The basic parameters of fruit storage are: temperature, relative humidity, and composition of the storage atmosphere.

For apples, the optimal storage temperature is -1.0°C to $+2.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and relative humidity is 90%.

The composition of the atmosphere and temperature should be adapted to the specific apple variety.

In fruit orchards in Poland, apples are stored in cold storage:

Ordinary with normal atmosphere: 21% O_2 + 78% N_2 + less than 0.1% CO_2

MO - with modified atmosphere: 16% O_2 + 79% N_2 + 5% CO_2

KA - with a controverted atmosphere:

- with standard composition: 5% CO_2 + 3% O_2 + 92% N_2

- low-oxygen ULO: 1.5% CO_2 + 1.0-1.5% O_2 + 97-97.5% N_2

- extremely low-oxygen - including DKA - dynamically controlled atmosphere: 0.4% O_2 + 1.0% CO_2 + 98% N_2 . Fruits in storage facilities consume oxygen, give off ethylene and carbon dioxide, as well as water vapor. They lose weight in the process. Maintaining the right temperature during storage and controlled atmosphere (DCA, CA) are important for the quality of apples after storage and during shelf-life. Of course another important factor is preventing the outbreak of the storage diseases, such as wet rot of apples - *Penicillium expansum*; brown rot of pome trees - *Monilinia* spp.; grey mould caused by *Botrytis cinerea*; rot caused by the fungus *Neonectria ditissima* (syn. *Neonectria galligena*); alternariosis of apples - *Alternaria* spp. (mainly *Alternaria alternata*); rot caused by the fungus *Diaporthe eres*. By associating the modification of the chemical composition of the atmosphere surrounding the food with the refrigeration treatment, the life of the products can be considerably extended.

IPM principles:	Prevention, Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease

Thermotherapy Shelf life

Thermotherapy on apples to increase shelf-life is a green strategy that reduces fungal diseases. The water temperature and contact time are respectively: 50-52°C for about one and a half minutes; the palletised crates or stacked bins are uniformly heated by the rapid passage of hot water pumped by the special machines. A control system determines the work cycle, and varies it as desired.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease
UV Treatment To Powdery Mildew

Powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha* Ellis & Everh.) is an important threat to apple growers. Using chemical fungicides brings good control results, however it can pose a problem regarding the maximum residue level (MRL's) in fruit. The aim is to develop new methods of disease control which do not pose a threat to fruit safety for the consumers. In this matter different biological control agents were tested as well as physical techniques, especially ultraviolet light. UV was earlier proven to be an effective tool in the control of powdery mildew in greenhouse production in strawberries. Scientists from the Netherlands also proved it to be effective in apple production. Check the usefulness against powdery mildew in apple orchards.

IPM principles:	Prevention, Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease; Pests
Application Of Biological Plant Protection Products Such As Plant Oils And Silicone Products

Products based on plant oils (e.g. *Camelina sativa*) or silicone-based products (Siltac) are used in Poland to lower the population of apple and pear soft-body mites and insects i.e. red spider mite and two-spotted spider mite (both refer to *Tetranychus urticae*), aphids (*Aphididae*), or psylla (genus of sap-sucking insects).

The woolly apple aphid (*Eriosoma lanigerum*) is an apple tree pest, which has become much more important in recent years. In many orchards it appears in outbreaks causing extensive losses.

Control of the aphid is not easy. Silicone-based products are an efficient tool to control the woolly aphid in apple orchard. The colony of this insect is covered with a heavy, wax, wooly coating.

Therefore the applied chemical preparations have a limited possibility of getting to the pests' body surface. Silicone-based products can also be used to control two-spotted spider mites and other small insect pests as they also act as a physical barrier in a similar way as other horticultural oil-based products which are an effective tool against mite pests, e.g. San Jose scale (*Quadraspidiotus perniciosus*), and pear psylla (*Psylla pyri*), and can contribute to suppression of codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*) and spotted tentiform leafminer (*Phyllonorycter blancardella*).

Oils also act as physical pesticides by creating a film on eggs, spores, or soft-bodied insects, thus suffocating them. A dormant (or pre-bloom) oil application can help manage mite populations; additional summer oil applications can also lower populations. However, some apple varieties have different sensitivities to summer oil sprays and use may result in fruit and foliar damage.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Biological Control Agents

Several biological control methods are available such as entomopathogenic nematodes, fungi, viruses and predatory insects. This limits the use of chemical pesticides and aims to keep harmful populations to an acceptable level.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Packaging In A Protective Atmosphere

The packaging in modified atmosphere in the containers for sale to the public are based on oxygen, carbon dioxide, nitrogen. These last two compounds inhibit the formation of moulds, yeasts and bacteria, and the alteration of lipids. Argon, helium and nitrous oxide are also permitted. The indication "product packed in a protective atmosphere" must appear on the packaging.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Pest And Disease-Free Planting Material

Use virus-free (VF) or virus-controlled (VT) nursery material purchased from nurseries accredited by the Regional Phytosanitary Service (SFR) and accompanied by the passport and marketing document certifying "quality CAC".

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Maria Concetta Strano

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Pest Monitoring

Monitoring of pathogens, for example with the aid of captaspores to detect the flight of ascospores of *Venturia inaequalis*. Use different types of traps for monitoring pests and, where possible, for mass trapping (e.g. *Cossus cossus* and *Zeuzera pyrina*).

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Precision Spraying

Precision spraying systems/robots that only spray at a certain leaf density. An estimated reduction of 25% in chemicals/fertilizers can be achieved.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease; Pests
Preservation Of Natural Agro-ecosystem

Preservation of the natural agro-ecosystem by hedges, tree lines, wooded areas, ponds, etc.. This area should not be less than 5% of the SAU. The ecosystem in and around the apple orchard can provides a natural habitat for predatory insects and increases biodiversity. Also elements like coniferous hedges provide protection against weather

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Maria Concetta Strano, Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests

Pruning For Reduction Of Infected Wood And Barks Parts

The pruning cuts are made to favor good lighting and ventilation in all parts of the canopy to improve disease resistance. The cut used to eliminate all the portions damaged by parasitic or environmental factors are essential. Fruit thinning is often necessary to avoid negative repercussions on the "state of health" of the plants which, in case of excessive production, weaken and become more susceptible to parasitic attacks.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Simona Fabroni

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease; Pests
The Use Of Kaolin In Apple Orchards

A ministerial decree of 2003 made it mandatory in Italy to use the phytosanitary treatments for the (*Cacopsylla melanoneura*) (Förster) vector insect of the apple proliferation. The use of kaolin in apple orchards represents a new opportunity in the containment of parasites. Spraying with the aid of common sprayers, forms a protective barrier on the vegetation. A good protective film must have some fundamental requirements, i.e. be chemically inert, with particles with a diameter of less than 2 µm, formulated in such a way as to create a uniform layer which alters and hinders the behavior of the insect on the plant without however interfering with gaseous exchanges of the vegetable. The compound mostly used for this purpose is kaolin, an alumino-silicate in the form of a fine white non-porous and non-expandable powder which is easily dispersed in water and chemically inert in a wide pH range. Kaolin clay, when used properly, has proven an effective organic option to deter pear psylla (*Cacopsylla pyri*) on pears, and plum curculio (*Conotrachelus nenuphar*) and first generation codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*) damage on apples. Later in the season use can suppress apple maggot (*Rhagoletis pomonella*) damage and second generation codling moth, but when used past early July when apple maggot becomes a threat, the increased chance of a bothersome amount of kaolin clay residue remaining on apples at harvest becomes a limitation. Also, full season use of kaolin clay has been associated with an increase in phytophagous mite populations.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Use Of Anti-hail Nets

The use of anti-hail nets for the defense of pome fruit from the key insect the codling moth, *Cydia pomonella*, is a recent innovation. The anti-hail nets prevent or minimize the entry of insects causing a progressive over time

decrease in the number of populations in the orchard.

The couplings of the insects present under the net are greatly reduced or eliminated. Among the possible

causes, still being studied, we can mention the "disturbance" effect exerted by the networks during the phase of courtship. In this phase, the insect prefers the top of the vegetation. Other causes may

be sought in the modification of microclimatic parameters under the network

The protection system consists of white anti-hail nets with 5.4 x mm2.2 mesh. Additional benefits achieved:

- drastic reduction of chemical residues in fruit and in the environment
- Facilitations in the realization of biological productions
- no increase in the main fungal diseases (scab, pear spot)
- reduction of damage caused by Miridae (deformed fruit)
- hail protection
- protection of fruits from birds (increased damage in recent years)
- protection of dripping wings from insects and birds
- control (in the single-row) of setting and therefore of the productive load in the apple tree as an alternative to thinning

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.biobestgroup.com/nl/biobest/producten/monitoring-scouting-4466/feromoonvallen-4492/mc-phail-trap-4566/>

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Agro-metereological Monitoring

Use the regional agro-meteorological network spread throughout the country to carry out climate monitoring and thus ascertain the conditions predisposing to infections.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Choice Of Cultivar And Pathogen Resistant Varieties

An effective tool for containing phytosanitary problems is represented by the use of resistant varieties. Introduction of new scab-resistant apple varieties for the enhancement of Valtellina fruit growing with a significant reduction in pesticide treatments and protection of the environment and consumers. There are selections created by the University of Bologna in a complex breeding program, which have the characteristic of being resistant to the key apple pathogen, the scab. The companies involved, distributed along the entire production area, from Talamona to Lovero. The apple cultivars are self-sterile, therefore it is necessary to intercrop with different interfertile cultivars. For adequate pollination and high quality fruit (shape and size in particular) the pollinators should be at least 10% of the plants.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni, Cinzia Benincasa, Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Tom van der Meer

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds
Choice Of Rootstock And Nursery Material

The right rootstock, reducing the vigor of the tree, induces an earlier entry into production and allows the facilitation of the antiparasitic defense. It is important to guarantee the absence of *Erwinia amylovora* (causing fire blight) in the nursery material, which is a very dangerous pathogen.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni, Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Choice Of Suitable Pedoclimatic Areas

The southern exposure is optimal, the one to the south-east and south-west is good, while the one to the north is inadequate. It adapts to most soils with the exception of excessively superficial, loose, clayey, calcareous soils. The slightly ventilated and open areas are the best as, since there is no stagnation of humidity, they reduce the development of scab (*Venturia inaequalis*) and the onset of rustiness of the epidermis in the fruits.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Wojciech Warabieda, Simona Fabroni

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds
Innovative Canopy Training Systems

Training systems with 2 vertical epsilon axes to be arranged along the line of the row to obtain balanced trees without a base stage. In the Guyot system we gradually move to 3, 4, 6, 8 permanent axes, a totally different system of growing apple trees. The traditional system of raising one or more permanent vertical axes is overcome. The floor plan geometry is rotated 90 degrees. The primary structure of the tree, the trunk, instead of being raised vertically, is stretched horizontally to form one or two cords parallel to the ground at a height of half a meter. Productivity is increased, mechanization is facilitated and above all the reduction of biotic and abiotic impact.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Targeted use; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Irrigation

The correct management of irrigation should not reduce fruit shelf-life. Among the possible irrigation systems, the fixed ones are preferable and in particular those with micro-flow (drip or spray). They offer many advantages for the high efficiency of water use, for the maintenance of water availability close to the field capacity, for non-wetting of the leaves of the trees, which could favor the infestation of some pathogens and for reduced development of weeds, as only small parts of land are wetted. To define the irrigation volumes and shifts, it would be advisable to have a rain gauge or better an evaporimeter. Optimal drainage has to be ensured to prevent staggling of water. Water quality is an important aspect. Water quality has improved in e.g. the Netherlands. Attention needs to be paid to this since water in streams can be brackish and is therefore not suitable for irrigation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni, Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Pest Monitoring

Monitoring of diseases and pests is important to make well and informed decisions about the need to use plant protection measures and/or pesticides. Monitoring for pests and for plant or fruit injury it is of fundamental importance to determine the presence and severity of individual pests in the orchard. Pheromone traps, sticky traps or light traps can be used during orchard monitoring. For some pests like beetles, the beat-tray method may be suitable. Accurate determination of tree infestation by particular species of pests and comparison of the obtained values with the action thresholds provides the basis for making decisions about economically justified control treatments. Regularly monitoring in the orchard is of key importance to limit chemical use.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer, Wojciech Warabieda

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Pre-planting Strategy In The Field

the clearing and leveling of the land, eliminating bumps and depressions, facilitate the disposal of water, avoiding surface stagnations. it is advisable to build hedges or plants with a windbreak function in order to form a reserve of auxiliaries. The sowing of particular herbaceous species, such as buckwheat for example, helps to create an excellent refuge and a source of nourishment for hoverflies, predators of aphids.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Simona Fabroni

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Rationalization Of The Use Of Plant Protection Products

The quality and efficiency of the distribution of plant protection products is increasingly important; the volumes of water must be optimized in relation to the type of sprayer present on the farm, the phenological phase (greater or lesser expansion of the vegetative surface) and the parasite to be combated.

IPM principles:	Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Simona Fabroni

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Rotation Of Active Ingredients

Rotation of different pesticides with different modes of action reduces the risk of developing resistance against active ingredients in pest species. Reports of for example codling moth already reported resistance against certain common pesticides. Additionally, evidence suggest that multiple applications with a lower dosis compare to a single application with a high dosis is equally as effective or more effective in the eradication/suppression of pests.

IPM principles:	Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds

Sprayer Calibration

Calibration is done by adjusting the sprayer in a way that ensures precise dosing of the target volume of liquid with the smallest possible losses e.g. drift. When calibrating a sprayer, several parameters should be taken into account to ensure accurate and effective application of pesticides like application rate, nozzle selection, spray pressure, sprayer speed, and volume of spray.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Wojciech Warabieda

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Disease; Pests; Weeds; Other

Sanitation

Proper sanitation is of huge importance to prevent spreading of diseases and pests and remove sources of contamination. Activities include removal of contaminated branches, bark, fruits and leaves, and sterilization of the used tools.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Other

Shredding Of Fallen Leaves

Fallen leaves are shredded to facilitate decaying by soils micro- and macrobiome. This provides nutrients for the soil and trees. Faster decaying of the leaves also prevents the build-up of harmful fungi in the wet microclimate between the leaves.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pest
Keeping Up With Hygiene Measures

Leaving parts of plants infected by pests or pathogens in the orchard leads to their spread. There are two main objectives regarding keeping up with hygiene measures to avoid spread of disease. The first one is performing the sanitary pruning of fruit trees every year as well as removing and destroying infected plant parts each year (best is to burn the infected wood outside the orchard). For the majority of pathogens, it is important to disinfect all tools such as pruning shears, etc. Additionally, in order to prevent the spread of the pathogens, clean and sharp tools should be used to produce smooth and clean cuts. This facilitates healing and reduces the risks of attack by insects and fungi. Additionally, copper-based products are often used as a fungicide to prevent the spread of fungi and bacteria on trees after pruning. Copper fungicide refers to any plant product with copper sulfate as an active ingredient. When dissolved in water or combined with other compounds, copper can penetrate diseased plant tissue and prevent fungi and bacteria from spreading further since these organisms are sensitive to copper ions

IPM principles:	Prevention, Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Wojciech Warabieda

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Mycorrhizal Colonization In Apple Orchards

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) colonize plant roots and spread in the surrounding bulk soil enhancing the nutrient uptake from the soil to the plant and stimulating the transfer of photosynthates from the plant to the soil. The importance of this symbiotic association in agro-ecosystems is related to an increasing attention to management sustainability and to the role of these systems as sinks of carbon dioxide (CO₂).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Follow-up;
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa

Application Of Bacteria-based Products In Pest Control

Bacillus thuringiensis (e.g., Dipel, Deliver, Biobit, Javelin, Agree) is a microbial insecticide specific for the control of caterpillars. It contains spores and crystalline endotoxin that must be ingested by larvae with high gut pH to provide control. It is effective against many fruit pests, including leafrollers and fruitworms. Although this material will contribute to the management of codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*) and other internal lepidopterous apple pests, it is not as effective as most conventional insecticides. One exception is the obliquebanded leafroller, which has become so difficult to control with conventional toxicants that the Bt products work at least as well as any material available. Compared to conventional insecticides used against these pests, Bt insecticide coverage should begin earlier and requires shorter intervals between spray applications. This material is exempt from requirements for tolerance on all raw agricultural commodities, thus it can be sprayed up until harvest. It is harmless to humans, animals, and beneficial insects, including the honey bee.

IPM principles: Alternatives

Efficacy*:

Cost (labour time)*: **2**

Cost (investments)*: **3**

Performance (normal yield)**: **3**

Performance (standard quality)**: **3**

Pesticide reduction*: **4**

Current implementation*: **3**

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Attract And Kill Method For Pest Control

The 'attract and kill'-method is a combination of attractants and killing agents which are paired with trapping devices. Other names include mass trapping, lure-and-kill and attracticide. This method was meant to make massive control systems of pests in orchards. The idea was to attract the pest to one place outside the orchard using pheromone or other to lure them with and to treat them with the PPP. Attract-and-kill can be combined with the resistant plants in IPM. Attraction from synthetic plant volatiles

or extracts, or from living plants can be combined with repellence from similar sources in push-pull systems. In many push-pull systems, the attractant (pull) is not combined with a toxicant. The

aim is not the destruction of pest populations but rather their redistribution to hosts or locations where they are less damaging.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury

Apple
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Beneficial Organisms

Apple orchards attract many kinds of insects that damage vegetation and fruit. But these orchard pests have insect enemies of their own. Growers can provide habitat for these natural enemies, also known as beneficial insects, as part of an integrated pest management (IPM) strategy that reduces the need for pesticides. Building shelters for beneficials like earwigs (*Dermaptera*) or Common green lacewing (*Chrysoperla carnea*) is crucial in order to build up the large population of natural enemies of pests for the spring. It is a great way to encourage the build-up of beneficials for the whole season to help with biological control of aphids (*Aphididae*), psyllidae and other small insect pests.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Wojciech Warabieda

Biological Control

Pests and their natural enemies are part of complex food-webs and interact with other species, notably at upper trophic levels such as hyperparasitoids and predators. Biological control using natural enemies and entomopathogens, play an important role in limiting the densities of potential pests. These natural enemies include predators, parasitoids, and pathogens. An effective control is achievable in orchards that support and promote a healthy and diverse natural enemy network.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Maria Concetta Strano, Dorota Labanwoska-Bury

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Pheromone Traps

Monitoring is essential in order to determine if countermeasures that have to be taken. Traps with specific pheromones can be used as a monitoring tool for harmful insects.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	0
Performance (standard quality)**:	0
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Introduction Of Shelters For Beneficials

Building shelters for beneficial animals like earwigs (*Forficula auricularia*) or lacewings (*Chrysoperla carnea*) in order to build up the large population for the spring. Nice way to encourage the build-up of beneficials for the whole season to help with biological control of aphids, psyllidae and other small insect pests

IPM principles:	Prevention, Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska, Tom van der Meer

Mating Disruption

Mating disruptions using pheromone dispensers prevent male codling moths (*Cydia pomonella*) and leafroller moths (*Tortricidae*) from finding females and thus prevents egg deposition and thus damage to the trees and fruit. Mating disruption aims to disrupt chemical communication by organisms and interrupt normal mating behaviour by dispensing synthetic sex pheromone, thereby affecting the organism's chance of reproduction. This can be done by using both attractive and non-attractive pheromone blends. Mating disruption with sex pheromones can be effective if the edge effect of mated females flying in from outside the treated area can be avoided. This can be done if very large areas are treated or if the area treated is isolated such as in a mountain valley. This method uses both hand-applied dispensers and aerosol dispensers. The method is effective under certain conditions. One of them is the size of the orchard, which should not be less than 4 ha. In addition, the effectiveness of the method may be limited under very high pest pressure. The shape of the field should be such that border edges are minimized. The method works better in a square-shaped orchard than in a narrow rectangular orchard. Applying this method to neighbouring orchards will usually improve its effectiveness. Furthermore, the mating disruption method is not effective in young orchards because the pheromone quickly dissipates due to lack of foliage. By using this method, we reduce the use of pesticides, which has a positive effect on biodiversity, including beneficial fauna, and also reduces the likelihood of the increased emergence of pests resistant to insecticides. Mating disruption is a term coined for the reduction in egg load or larval population through disruption of mating by inundating large quantities of pheromone in the field. The disruption is achieved through confusion (males are overtly confused), trail masking, and laying false trails (Campion *et al.*, 1980). Successful mating disruption is indicated by a drop in the trap catches over time, reduced mating in fields as witnessed through visual observations, lesser incidence of pests or damage in comparison to untreated areas, and the absence of spermatophores in the females. Sometimes avoidance or delayed mating with calling females was also attributed to effectively reducing the fecundity of the females. Ecological factors such as emergence patterns of diapausing pupae, diurnal rhythms, and weather factors play a significant role in the effectiveness of mating disruption.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer, Wojciech Warabieda

Microbiological Control Methods

Microbial antagonism occurs by the application of fungi, bacteria and virus in specific formulations (biofungicides), which effectiveness is the result of several mechanisms of action such as antibiosis, mycoparasitism, and induced resistance. A negative aspect is mainly due to a low effectiveness and stability of microorganisms used, with regard to the conditions of the natural environment (temperature, rain, air humidity etc.).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.gfactueel.nl/vlekjes-aan-vrije-schurftresistente-appelrassen/>

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Wojciech Warabieda, Maria Concetta Strano

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for pests

Removing Late Pink Stage Flowers

Removing dried out late pink-stage flowers reduces the risk of the apple blossom weevil (*Anthonomus pomorum* L.) in the following growing season by removing also the pupae of the weevil.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Sexual Confusion And Disorientation Methods

To control the population of pest flies, using pheromones and sticky traps.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Dorota Labanwoska-Bury, Maria Concetta Strano

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Using Pheromone For Mating Disruption

Using pheromone disruption tools e.g. Isomate is very efficient in the control of codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*) and other insects belonging to *Tortricidae*. In France and in Italy by using this method codling moth is controlled 100%, although carpovirusine or 1 PPP is generally applied in Italy.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska-Bury, Maria Grazia Tommasini

Beneficial Organisms: Introduction Of Predatory Mites

Spider mites (*Tetranychidae*) are a very invasive pest species in the apple orchard. The main damage is that feeding mites sucks leaf fluids and chlorophyll, resulting in "bronzed" foliage. Slightly damaged leaves cause little or no adverse effect to the crop. Extensive leaf bronzing results in decreased photosynthesis, often causing reduction in the fruit size, premature fruit drop and reduction in fruit set the following year. The chemical control of spider mites can be difficult, if the population level gets high. In order to prevent an outbreak of spider mites in apple orchards, the introduction of predatory mites from the *Phytoseiidae* family is used. A particularly efficient species in reducing herbivorous mites is predatory mite - *Typhlodromus pyri*.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Wojciech Warabieda

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mulch Along The Apple Orchard Row

The under-row of the apple orchard can be managed conservatively with the mulching technique. It consists in distributing organic material along the rows: straw, processing by-products, wood shavings etc. or plastic film to reduce the emergence of weeds.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cinzia Benincasa, Tom van der Meer

Apple

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Weed Control On The Row

Minimum tillage under the tree along the row favours weed control and roots aeration avoiding the application of herbicides. An alternative is a new techniques with a machine with round branches that runs on the weeds on the row able to flatten the grass and consequently to reduce its development.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Maria Grazia Tommasini

Hot Water Treatment In Weed Control

Thermal weed control plays an important role in managing weeds in synthetic herbicide-free systems, particularly in organic agriculture and in urban areas where synthetic herbicides are prohibited. Hot water and hot foam treatment applied with the special equipment (like a weed sprayer) can be used to control weeds in apple rows. Thermal weed control involves heat being transferred to plant material (leaves, stems, flowers, propagules, etc.) to destroy cell structures and denature proteins. To control above ground vegetation with thermal weed control methods, the heat requirement depends on the weed species, their growth stages, water status, and the presence of moisture on the leaf surface. The dose applied is critical and determines the efficacy of the weed control. Pyro-weeding exploits the heat generated by water vapour, or more recently, by foaming products of natural origin which, causing a thermal shock to the annual species, which precipitates their rapid withering. Other innovative solutions focus on machines capable of spraying high pressure water (piston pump operating at 1000 bar) on weeds to contain their spread along the row.

IPM principles: Alternatives

Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Dorota Labanowska

Application Of Organic Matter

Application of organic amendments as alternative to mineral fertilisers can improve soil functionality and soil biodiversity with an effect on tree resilience to soilborne diseases. Natural soil amendments, organic and mineral can be an effective solution to these problems. Soil amendments are substrates used to improve the properties of cultivated soils and positively affect crop yields. Their main purpose is to improve soil fertility by increasing the availability of nutrients and water for plants, limiting soil drying, maintaining high microbiological activity in the soil, and increasing the uptake of nutrients by plants. The application of organic amendments as alternative to mineral fertilisers can improve soil functionality and soil biodiversity with an effect on tree resilience to soilborne diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Maria Grazia Tommasini

Beehives Placement

Insecticides, by definition and design, kill insects including pollinators if sufficient dosage and exposure levels are met. Plant systemic neonicotinoid insecticides in particular may affect bee health and may contribute to the decline of some species. An important advantage of IPM is that the pest management practices can be adjusted to accommodate new factors such as pollinator protection. A good tool in IPM of apple orchard is the placement of beehives (6-7 beehives/ha) near crops to encourage pollination by pollinators.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Maria Concetta Strano

4. Strawberry

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Biofungicide (Salt Ions)

Salt ions (potassium hydrogen carbonate) disrupt the fungal cell membranes and inhibit spore germination, making them effective against powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*), a common disease in strawberries. Can also be used to suppress Botrytis Fruit Rot (*Botrytis cinerea*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Biofungicide (Copper)

Copper based fungicides are used to manage angular leaf spot (*Xanthomonas fragariae*). It is not very common in cultivation system of high tunnels. Mainly for open field cultivation on ground. Pay attention to avoid negative impacts on water quality.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Use Of Resistant Cultivars

Pre-planting disease prevention through the use of disease resistant strawberry such as red core disease (*Phytophthora fragariae*) and powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*). Strawberry is an Octoploid which makes breeding for resistant/tolerant genes to pests and diseases difficult. Phytophthora resistance is paid attention to, mildew is more about tolerance. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly june-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for Phytophthora. Some newer cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant to powdery mildew and Phytophthora than older (mostly june-bearing) cultivars (like Elsanta).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Clara Sciffer, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro, Johanna Molenaar

Use Of UV-C for Powdery Mildew

Regular treatments with an UV-C robot (Ultraviolet-C includes the high energy wavelengths between 100 and 280 nm) can be used against mold spores (*Botrytis cinerea* and *Podosphaera aphanis*). Due to the high energy content, exposure leads to DNA damage in the organisms, and kills the spores. Treatments are carried out during the night to avoid recovery of the fungus during the day and is automatised to reduce labour time. It is used in practice in greenhouses in the Netherlands.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.futurefarming.com/tech-in-focus/field-robots/robot-combats-powdery-mildew-in-strawberries-using-uv-c-treatment/> <https://www.futurefarming.com/tech-in-focus/field-robots/robot-combats-powdery-mildew-in-strawberries-using-uv-c-treatment/>

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Clara Schiffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Hygiene In The Greenhouse: Washing The Truss Support Ribbons

In the case of *Mucor* spp.: the tape that gives support to the strawberries has to be washed and disinfected.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Agrovision: Adviesberichten Aardbei

Decision support tool for powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*) and Botrytis Fruit Rot (*Botrytis cinerea*) in open field. Does not work very well for strawberry on table tops, and is not relevant for strawberries in the greenhouse.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Link to more information:

<https://www.agrovision.com/nl/producten/teelt/adviessystemen/adviesberichten>

Contributed by: Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Calcium Application

Ensure an adequate supply of calcium (Ca) to prevent physiological disorders like blossom end rot. Lime or gypsum applications can help improve calcium availability. It's important to note that while adding calcium amendments can be effective, other factors such as consistent watering practices, soil moisture management, and proper fertilization are also critical in preventing blossom end rot.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Beneficial Bacteria

Endophytic bacteria and Plant-growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) such as *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Azospirillum*, *Rhizobium*, and *Streptomyces* can be used to prevent *Botrytis cinerea* (causing Botrytis Fruit Rot) and other fungal diseases as well as soil pathogens. More evidence on the topic is still needed.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Biosprays (*Bacillus subtilis*)

Bacillus subtilis-based biopesticides can help suppress various fungal diseases, including gray mold (*Botrytis cinerea*) and powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Beneficial Fungi

Fungi can be used to control other fungi as well as insects. Some beneficial fungi used for fungal control includes *Trichoderma* spp., AMF (arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi), *Penicillium* spp., *Gliocladium* spp., and *Clonostachys* spp. For insect control *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium* spp., and *Lecanicillium* spp. can be used. However, prove of effect lack for many of them. Entomopathogenic fungi do not work so well in greenhouses, because relative humidity can be controlled well.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Remove Affected Strawberries

Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest, for powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*), for mucor (*Mucor* spp.) and spotted wing drosophila (*Drosophila suzukii*) an extra round through the crop can occur).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Use of Extra Physical Barriers

Use of extra physical barriers surrounding the crop to avoid wind damage and to lower the entering of whiteflies (*Trialeurodes packardii*), spotted wing drosophila (*Drosophila suzukii*) and thrips (e.g. WFT, *Frankliniella occidentalis*) in the crop. Protection from wind damage can also lower the powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*) pressure. The set up of these physical barriers is however only done in cropping systems that are locally anchored and are therefore used for multiple years. Because of this, this technique is mostly used in cropping systems using substrate and not in cropping systems in soil. Table tops with rain cover and table tops in polytunnel are used to keep out rain. This lowers the incidence of Botrytis Fruit Rot (*Botrytis cinerea*), but increases the incidence of powdery mildew. Powdery mildew spores can be washed away by water.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Extensions Services, Experts

Advisors from extension services and other experts often visit the farm and monitor the crop. Biological crop protection suppliers also often monitor the pests present. The person harvesting the strawberries and the farmer could also monitor the crop, but the personnel often lack the knowledge to recognize the early symptoms of disease/pests. Do not monitor pests/diseases only, the presence of natural enemies should also be monitored. If the balance between pest and natural enemies is monitored over time, you can prevent spraying in many cases by timely adjusting the introduction of natural enemies.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Steam Treatment of Soil and Transplants

Plant sauna. Steam treatments of transplants can be an effective way of reducing mites (e.g. *Tetranychus* spp.) populations in the early phase of transplanting. Temperatures of 48 °C have been shown to completely kill adult females after 2.7 h of exposure and eggs after 1.9 h of exposure. The soil can also be steamed to temperatures of 65 °C for 30 min. The time and amount of steam needed to raise the soil temperature to 65 °C depends on various soil factors, including texture, type, and moisture content. It can be done with fresh tips and with tray plants. Kills Phytophthora (*Phytophthora cactorum*, *P. citricola*, *P. megasperma*, *P. parasitica*), powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*) and mites. In the Netherlands used in breeding and for elite tray plants.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.hortidaily.com/article/9281562/strawberry-plants-in-line-for-the-plantsauna/>

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Remove Dead Plant Material

Removing fallen leaves and flowers is important to prevent diseases and certain pests such as the strawberry blossom weevil (*Anthonomus rubi*) which takes shelter under the ground in dead plant material. The removal of buds and adults prevents the growth of pests and diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Lime Sulfur

Lime sulfur can be used before winter to disinfect the plants. Additionally, it is effective after infection has occurred to eliminate pests/diseases. Has been tested effective against powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*), mites (e.g. *Tetranychus* spp.), leaf curl (*Caulimovirus venafragariae*) and other pests. It is not used during periods of hot weather due to potential phytotoxicity. Harmful to some natural enemies.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Pests: Physical Barriers

Nets for birds, and mesh against insects, or other physical barriers to protect crops against pests.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	0
Cost (labour time)*:	0
Cost (investments)*:	0
Performance (normal yield)**:	0
Performance (standard quality)**:	0
Pesticide reduction*:	0
Current implementation*:	0

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Activation of Systemic Defenses (By Means of Jasmonic Acid) (Elicitor Application)

Exogenous application of the active form of jasmonic acid, methyl jasmonate (MeJA), is known to induce plant defenses, resulting in increased plant resilience against herbivorous insect pests. It applied as foliar sprays, MeJA enhances the production of defensive metabolites, such as phytoalexins and proteinase inhibitors, promoting the plant's resilience. The application timing and concentration depend on factors like pest pressure and growth stages, with early application during critical phases like flowering. Environmental considerations, including temperature and compatibility with beneficial organisms, are essential. MeJA is often integrated with other IPM practices, emphasizing regular monitoring, thresholds, and a comprehensive approach to pest management in strawberry cultivation, ensuring effective protection while minimizing environmental impact.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

https://www.actahort.org/books/926/926_86.htm

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Desinfecting Water With UV/Sand Filter

Slow sand filtration is employed to control the proliferation of *Phytophthora* and *Pythium* species, effectively reducing their presence by over 99.9% and thereby preventing their spread. However, this method is not as effective in retaining other pathogens like *Fusarium*, bacteria, viruses, and nematodes. To control these additional microorganisms, high-dose and extended-duration UV disinfection is employed, which proves sufficient in eliminating all types of fungi, bacteria, viruses, and nematodes.

In strawberry cultivation, the use of peat and coconut substrates initially results in high water turbidity, hampering the effectiveness of UV disinfection. This issue can be resolved by introducing "clean" water into the system, which improves water clarity and subsequently enhances the capacity of UV disinfection. This, however, leads to increased energy consumption.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Trichoderma

Trichoderma species are successful plant beneficial microbial inoculants due to their ability to act as biocontrol agents with direct antagonistic activities to phytopathogens, and are capable of promoting plant growth. Strawberry growers use them to obtain higher fruit yield and healthier plants.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

CATT (Controlled Atmosphere Temperature Treatment)

Used on mother plants in nurseries. Plants are exposed to a temperature of 35 °C and 50% CO₂ for 48 hrs. The treatment has a mortality rate of more than 99.8% of the *Tarsonemidae* mites. There are no harmful irreversible effects of CATT on field mother plant vitality. In 2009 CATT was scaled up to commercial level and widely used by Dutch plant material producers.

IPM principles: Prevention, Alternatives

Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Soil Solarization

Covering the soil with plastic to heat it up and sterilize it by killing pathogens and weed seeds. Effective against black root disease which is caused by multiple soilborne fungi.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Soil Testing

A comprehensive soil test to assess nutrient levels and pH is needed to develop a proper fertilization and irrigation plan which prevents diseases and pests. Adjust soil pH if necessary to maintain it within the optimal range for strawberries, typically around 6.0 to 6.5.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Slow Release Fertilizers

Coated granules or controlled-release formulations, can provide a steady supply of nutrients to strawberry plants over an extended period which promotes a healthier growth making plants less prone to diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Foliar Sprays

Nutrients and biostimulants (e.g., seaweed extracts or amino acids) can be used to enhance plant health, stress tolerance, and resistance to diseases and pests. Not much evidence on effects have been shown yet.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Clara Sciffer, Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Others
Cultivation Technique: Analysis And Fertilizer Use

Adapted fertilizer use based on a 4-5 yearly soil- and crop analysis. In open field on soil systems this is even more; at least one time per cropping cycle a soil analysis should be done. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*), Botrytis fruit rot (*Botrytis cinerea*) and aphids (*Aphididae*). Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. If abnormal colouring or development of the strawberry crop is observed, a foliar analysis should be carried out to determine a possible nutrient deficiency, which, depending on its severity, can be corrected with foliar fertilisers. Excess of potassium reduces fruit growth. Application in greenhouse systems: Fertilizer in circulation water. Application in full soil systems: Before and during the production cycle with a drip line.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Others

Impact From Pesticides: Neveneffectenlijst

List --> Will become app. This list shows the impact of many crop protection products on natural enemies and pollinators.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.biobestgroup.com/nl/neveneffectenlijst>

Contributed by: Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Others; Weeds

Spraying Advice: S spuitadvieslijst Met Neveneffecten

Spraying advice list with indication of effect of crop protection product on natural enemies and pollinators. It helps growers use crop protection products wisely in their IPM strategy. Two ways: 1. Choose product with lower impact on natural enemies and/or pollinators. 2. If you use a product bad for natural enemies, then introduce (high numbers of) natural enemies a few days after application.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

https://www.biobestgroup.nl/_files/ugd/dc5380_2ea89cb2423047f79bf410d921712bff.pdf

Contributed by: Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Drip Irrigation

Use drip irrigation systems to deliver water directly to the root zone, this minimizes moisture on the foliage and reduces the risk of foliar diseases. (Ex.: T-Tape irrigation, Subsurface drip irrigation, raised bed drip irrigation)

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Buffer Zones

Pesticide free areas usually to protect water sources and other environmentally sensitive areas from contamination and delineate specific spraying areas. Minimum 1-3 m 'crop protection free' buffer zones from water courses in open field systems (this buffer zone can be larger depending on the PPP).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Healthy Plant Material

Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Flower Strips Between Rows

Planting flower strips inbetween rows is used to offer resources for pollinators and natural enemies of crop pests such as shelter, oviposition sites, overwintering opportunities and food resources. Also effective against weeds. Greenhouse experiments are made with bankerplant that is hung under the gutters (so they do not take space or light). Allysum is very effective for establishment of *Orius leavigatus*.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno; Johanna Molenaar

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Integrated Irrigation

Combination of tools, techniques, and data sources to support decision-making throughout the growing season. These tools may include soil moisture sensors, weather forecasts, irrigation scheduling software, and on-farm observations.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Prediction Models

1. Weather prediction models: Used for efficient usage of pesticide applications and reducing the unintended consequences of chemical residues.
2. Degree Day Models: Locally used to predict key life stages for insect pests, weeds, and diseases and increase the efficacy of management activities.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Crop Rotation

Crop rotation 1:3 (means that the crop is grown one year in three years) for strawberries in open fields e.g. to reduce wireworms (*Agriotes* spp.) and other soil-borne problems. Open field strawberry can be rotated with brassicas, legumes, root crops, cereals and green manure crops to avoid the build up of diseases and pests in the soil as well as keep the soil covered to avoid weeds. Overall crop rotations should be followed by crops which are non-hosts to common strawberry pests such as nematodes. Growers should avoid solanaceous crops and other small fruit crops like raspberries following strawberry. Not necessary for tray field cultivation or greenhouses. In this case proper sanitation and sterilization is required.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro, Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Hygiene In Greenhouses: Cleaning Of The Gutters

After every production cycle in the greenhouse, the gutters are cleaned (mostly with high-pressure water, but at least once a year also with cleaning agents).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Choice of Intervention Techniques

Biological, and if feasible also mechanical and physical crop protection measures are preferred. Apply these first in case they can reach sufficient levels of efficacy and are economically feasible to use. Farmers are very aware of eventual negative side effects of certain chemical pesticides. Therefore, biological alternatives are preferred. Broad spectrum insecticides are not used, farmers first choice is to use beneficials. Fungicides: Farmers try to use as much preventive biological measures as possible in order to avoid the use of fungicides. Herbicides: A lot of attention to preventive measures (e.g. steaming of the trays), but usually a broad spectrum of herbicide is used 1-3 times per cropping cycle as weed control in tray plants.

IPM principles:	Dosage; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Monitoring

Find out which pests are important to monitor. Make use of monitoring techniques including recording number of pests in sticky traps and identifying species. Scouting fields for diseases, monitoring the condition of the plants (leaf color/ angle), assess the amount of weeds, etc.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Ammonium Sulfate Fertilisation and Crop Rotation

The use of ammonium sulfate as a fertiliser has been shown to decrease black root rot a disease complex (including the fungi *Pythium* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Rhizoctonia* spp., and several species of nematodes). The effects were even more pronounced by also introducing a crop rotation of oats (*Avena strigosa*) and Triple S sorgho-sudangrass (*Sorghum bicolor* x *S. sudanense*) followed by strawberry. The use of these crops also suppressed weeds, which are a big threat to strawberries, as well as diseases. Crop rotation is not common for all cropping systems, e.g in the Netherlands most strawberries are grown in growing medium.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds

Hygiene: Steaming

Plant propagation: The trays used for plant propagation get steamed every year or if there were problems with *Phytophthora* species the year before. Production of strawberries: The pots get steamed when using cultivars sensitive to *Phytophthora*.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds

Use Officially Approved And Healthy Plant Material

Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use). The use of healthy plant material is a more environmentally efficient measure than eliminating pests with plant protection products. The choice of nursery plants is the first action towards sustainable and high-quality production. Healthy plant material is more likely to resist pest attacks. It is also less likely to spread diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro, Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Biofungicide (*Clonostachys rosea*)

Spores/mycelium of the *Clonostachys rosea* fungus are mainly used preventatively. Effective biofungicides disseminated by bumblebees to protect flowers against *Botrytis cinerea* (causing Botrytis fruit rot) decreases fruit loss.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Biopesticides

Protac SF: Highly effective corrective measure for IPM programmes. Physically-acting, silicon polymers create a thin, sticky net over pests and immediately immobilise and rapidly eliminate spider mite (*Tetranychus* spp.), aphid (*Aphididae*), whitefly (*Trialeurodes packardii*) and thrips (e.g. WFT, *Frankliniella occidentalis*)

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Choice of Pesticide

Choose a pesticide which is specifically tailored to the relevant pest. Choose pesticides which have little effect on natural enemies and pollinators. Introduce beneficials after application.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Targeted use; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Bioinsecticides

Spraying neem (*Azadirachta indica*) extract with the active ingredient, azadirachtin, acts as a mild insecticide which is not harmful to humans, beneficial insects and pollinators. It is used against diseases as well as pests in strawberry most effective against thrips (e.g. WFT, *Frankliniella occidentalis*). Other bioinsecticides are formulated with fatty acids such as Bayer's Flipper; a broad-spectrum contact bio-insecticide/acaricide for control of mite (*Tetranychus* spp.), aphid (*Aphididae*), whitefly (*Trialeurodes packardii*) and thrips (e.g. WFT, *Frankliniella occidentalis*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Pheromone Traps

Pheromone traps use sex pheromones and aggregated pheromones to lure insects in and trap them. They can help monitor and trap specific pests, such as strawberry blossom weevils (*Anthonomus rubi*) or strawberry tortrix moth (*Acleris comariana*).

They allow the detection of pests before critical periods where the use of insecticides will be optimal. This allows pesticides to be used more efficiently. Without this detection method, it would be necessary to apply insecticides on a calendar basis.

The traps are combined with thresholds of risk levels and are used in coherence with other tools, such as insecticides or sexual confusion methods. The use is based on placing traps in the field. It is recommended to use the traps before the first generation of the target pest. The use of sex pheromones requires the use of a traps suitable for the specific insect size, behaviour, population level and environment in which it will be placed. In protected crops, enclosures should be reinforced to avoid the entry of adults and to maintain the hygiene of the plot to reduce possible refugees.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Monitoring: Warning Systems

Warning system for the spotted wing drosophila (*Drosophila suzukii*) based on close monitoring of the pest by extension services.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Biological Control: Use of Predatory Mites

Application and release of beneficial organisms: Predatory mites (preventive: *Neioseius californicus* and curative: *Phytoseiulus persimilis*) against spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.), and predatory mites (*Neioseius cucumeris*, *Amblyseius swirskii* and *Amblydromalus limonicus*) against whiteflies (*Trialeurodes packardi*).

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer, Carolina Gattorno, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Biological Control: Use of Predatory Bugs and othe pests

Application and release of beneficials: predatory bugs (e.g. *Orius laevigatus*) against whitefly (e.g. *Trialeurodes packardii*). Predatory bugs are used when the use of predatory mites is not sufficient for control. There are several predatory insects and organisms which can be used to control pest populations. In strawberry, ladybugs (*Coccinella septempunctata*), wasps, nematodes, as well as lacewings and hoverflies are used. They are mainly used to control trips, aphids, mites, rootworm, weevils and whitefly.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer, Carolina Gattorno, Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Trapping *Drosophila suzukii*

Pheromone or food traps against spotted wing drosophila (*Drosophila suzukii*). The warning system for the spotted wing drosophila also indicates when to intervene.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Push-Pull Technique

The use of hexyl butyrate (HB) is an example of an effective push element and *L. rugulipennis* female sex pheromone combined with phenylacetaldehyde as the pull element.

This method involves luring pests away from the crops and towards an attractive source where they can be removed.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Trap Crop

Alfalfa is a highly preferred host plant of *Lygus* spp. (Hemiptera: Miridae). As such, intercropping alfalfa trap-crops in strawberry production can serve as a sink for both *Lygus* (primarily *Lygus hesperus* Knight) and its natural enemies. This technique makes use of a trap crop (alfalfa in this case). However, it is still not very used by growers.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Raised beds, propped or supported fruit

Raising strawberry fruit from the soil is effective in preventing soil-borne pests such as sap beetles (*Stelidota geminata*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Yellow-Sticky Traps for Monitoring

The use of sticky traps (long ‘ribbons’) usually in combination with a pheromone trap is often used against thrips (e.g. WFT, *Frankliniella occidentalis*), white fly (*Trialeurodes packardi*), spider mites (*Tetranychus* sp.) as well as aphids (*Aphididae*). The yellow traps and pheromones attract the pests and stick them onto the traps. Effective for monitoring the pests that are present and controlling populations. Sticky traps are placed throughout the crop at the start of the production cycle.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno, Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Irradiation

Irradiation of boxed fresh fruits with gamma rays (100 Gy) is used for the management of *Bemisia tabaci* and *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (both whiteflies).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Pest Control In Nursery And Plant Production

In the case of diseased plants, the affected plants must be uprooted and destroyed. Another preventive measure to ensure that the plant material remains healthy is to clean the borders of the crop and optimise the use of nitrogen. If the presence of white spider mites is detected at nursery level, a hot water immersion treatment of the seedlings (thermotherapy) is carried out, which is a very effective treatment against the spider mite, the disadvantage being that it has negative effects on the plants. With a whitefly (*Trialeurodes packardii*) presence of 70% or more, biological control organisms such as *Orius laevigatus* (2 to 4 individuals/m²) should be installed as soon as possible, provided that the environmental conditions are suitable.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Locate Pest Hotspots To Minimise Spread To Other Plots.

Locating and controlling hot spots of pests reduces waste, spread of pests to other plots and lowers the resistance. Soil movement must be limited to avoid the spread of pests, and strawberries must be cultivated in well-drained, slightly calcareous and saline soils, otherwise the fruits become susceptible to attack by grey mould (*Botrytis cinerea*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Funnel Traps for Codling Moth (*Cydia pomonella*)

In case sticky traps are ineffective there are funnel traps which lure pests with pheromones and then once when they are in the dispenser they fly around until exhausted which is when they fall into a bucket with soapy water. This is used for codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*).

IPM principles:	Alternatives, Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mechanical Weeding

Mechanical weeding with plough or mechanical weeding without plough (harrow, weeder, cultivator, rotary hoe, other) can be used.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Carolina Gattorno

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Physical Barriers For Weed Control

Physical barriers (plastic/fabric) is used to avoid weeds in open field soil cropping systems. The use prevents the growth of weeds in between rows. Straw is also used, however foil is preferred by most growers.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Monitor And Maintain Weed Perimeters

There should be a first stage of protection of the strawberries, if possible the ground is completely cleared of the rhizomes of perennial weeds. In case other weeds, waste and other overgrown perennial weeds have to be controlled, the digging method with careful selection of all rhizomes works on very small areas.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds; Others

Appropriate Planting Density

Manipulation of planting density is a tool used to optimise production in strawberry cultivation. Also, the effect of density will depend on the cultivar, horticultural management and environmental conditions. The greater the distance between plants, the greater the growth. High planting densities reduce the growth of vegetative varieties leaf area, and higher densities are also more likely to make it easier for diseases to spread and pests to affect a larger number of plants. Planting density does not affect reproductive development, as represented by the number of inflorescences. However, it has been found that the highest yields and number of commercial fruits per plant were achieved at lower densities.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Cultivation Technique: Irrigation

The plants are irrigated directly at the roots to meet the crop's water needs and avoid run-off of nutrients.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Drift-reduction Techniques

Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ DR) in open field systems. Drift reduction caps can also improve the effectiveness of the pesticide application.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Anti-resistance: Correct Dosage

Stick to recommended doses of pesticides.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Evaluation: Efficacy Of IPM Measures

Monitor infestation levels before and after the measure; evaluate the efficacy of implemented IPM measures.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Evaluation: Register All Chemical Crop Protection Measures

Register all chemical crop protection measures.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Control Relative Humidity and Temperature

Growing strawberries in a controlled environment makes it possible to provide beneficial temperatures for the plants. Strawberries have particular temperature requirements, the temperature should be increased gradually at the beginning of the season, this mimics the transition from winter to summer, thanks to this the plants grow and produce more. Another important factor is relative humidity, which affects the plants' ability to absorb nutrients, which in turn slows down growth and fruit development. High humidity is a very common problem in greenhouse production. Plants constantly transpire, releasing moisture into the air, and in an enclosed environment such as a greenhouse, humidity will increase dramatically. High humidity indicates that the air is saturated, and therefore the plants cannot transpire. Transpiration is essential, otherwise the roots will not absorb water from the soil and the plant will not receive the nutrients it needs. Moisture not only affects nutrient uptake, it also plays an important role in the development of diseases and mould. In wet conditions, common diseases such as Botrytis fruit rot (*Botrytis cinerea*) and powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*) can develop. These diseases have a major negative impact on crops. They slow down or even stop the development and reduce the fruit yield. In extreme cases, they can even kill entire cycles of strawberry crops. Many of the most common diseases require high humidity. Thus, by maintaining an ideal humidity range and avoiding high humidity, outbreaks can be prevented. Disease prevention through humidity control reduces the need for toxic pesticides and fungicides.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro, Clara Sciffer

Strawberry
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Others
Avoid Waterlogging

Avoid waterlogging and maintain good drainage to reduce neck and root fungi. Nutrients and suitable levels of organic matter must be provided continuously. Sandy soils are preferred. Clay soils should be avoided, as they retain excess moisture, especially with rainfall rot develops in the strawberry roots, since they need sufficient oxygen levels. Saline soils should be avoided, as the crop is quite sensitive to excess conductivity. A continuous supply of water must be guaranteed, but care must be taken with waterlogging problems, the biggest problems with water supply are related to excess, not to frequency. The most common is to use fertigation systems, especially drip irrigation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro

Plan and Adjust Fertilisation

An excess of nitrogen in the soil causes an increase in vegetative growth, reduces the yield and favours the loss of fruit turgidity, while an excess of potassium reduces fruit growth. The fertiliser dose is proportional to the expected yield and takes into account the physico-chemical properties of the soil (fertility analysis). Nitrogen is one of the most important nutrients in strawberry cultivation. The dose of 100 kg/ha of nitrogen in strawberry, applied with ammonium nitrate, produces a higher yield and fruit quality, positively favours leaf area, fresh matter weight, dry matter weight and ammonium nitrate accumulation. The application of granular fertiliser or nutrient solution on strawberry crops has a direct influence on the quantity and quality of production. When abnormal colouring or development of the strawberry crop is observed, a foliar analysis should be carried out to determine a possible nutrient deficiency, which, depending on its severity, can be corrected with foliar fertilisers.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Celeste Victoria Oliveira Navarro, [Carolina Gattorno](#)

Strawberry

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Others

Pushing Flowers Forward

The flower clusters are pushed forwards, so they can dry faster as they are not influenced anymore by the microclimate of the leaves. This also ensures a better contact during the application of pesticides. By pushing the flower clusters forwards, harvesting becomes also easier.

IPM principles:	Prevention;
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

5. Wheat

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Prevention Of Take-all (*Gaeumannomyces tritici*)

Do not grow wheat after wheat on sandy soil. Consider rye and triticale as an alternative on sandy soils. The risk for take-all (*Gaeumannomyces tritici*) disease is high when growing winter wheat 2nd and 3rd year on sandy soil types. Take-all can result in large yield losses. Seed coating with latitude (in Denmark only allowed on imported seeds) has some effect.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Symptoms of Take-all. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

No Maize As Forecrop

Avoid wheat where the previous crop is maize. The risk of infestations with Fusarium (*Fusarium avenaceum*), and thus the formation of Fusarium toxins in winter wheat, is high with maize as previous crop.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Symptoms of Fusarium in wheat. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Diseases In Cropping Systems Without Ploughing

Winter wheat in cropping systems without ploughing. With wheat/triticale as previous crops and reduced tillage, there is an increased risk of infestations with Fusarium (*Fusarium culmorum*) and thus formation of Fusarium toxins in wheat. It is important to grow the wheat varieties that are least susceptible to Fusarium. A risk assessment scheme has been developed. At high risk, fungal control during flowering may exceptionally be recommended. With wheat as previous crop and at the same time using reduced tillage, wheat tan spot (DTR) (*Drechslera tritici-repentis*), in addition to the usual diseases, can be a problem. It is therefore important to choose fungicides that have an effect against both DTR and the other fungal diseases, including Septoria (*Septoria tritici* and *Septoria nodorum*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Symptom of Fusarium, middle: DTR, right: *Septoria tritici*. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Resistant And Tolerant Varieties

See the susceptibility of varieties from national field trials on, e.g SortInfo.dk. The selection of varieties should not only take disease susceptibility into account. The choice of varieties is often a compromise, and it is also necessary to include traits such as yield, winter hardiness, feed value, outlets, etc. Variety mixtures reduce the risk of fungal infestation. Use variety mixtures with less susceptible varieties. As far as possible, choose varieties and variety mixtures with good resistance to yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*), powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis*) and Septoria (*Septoria tritici/Stagonospora nodorum*). New and modern breeds can show considerable resistance or tolerance to diseases and pest. The use of these varieties can thus significantly reduce the use of pesticides.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

www.sortinfo.dk

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars-Ole Hingst

Photos: Left: Yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*). Right: Powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis*).
Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Cultivar Choice In Systems Without Ploughing

See the susceptibility of varieties on e.g. SortInfo.dk. The selection of varieties should not only take susceptibility into account. The choice of varieties is often a compromise, and it is also necessary to take into account yield, winter hardiness, feed value, outlets, etc. With reduced tillage, varieties with the low susceptibility to wheat tan spot (DTR) (*Drechslera tritici-repentis*) and Fusarium (*Fusarium* spp.) have high priority. Choose varieties and varietal mixtures with low susceptibility to wheat tan spot (DTR) (*Drechslera tritici-repentis*), Fusarium ear blight (*Fusarium culmorum*), yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*), powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis*) and Septoria (*Septoria tritici/Stagonospora nodorum*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*). Right: Powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis*).
Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Diseases: Registration Network

Follow the development of fungal diseases in your national registration network if present, and by inspection in your own fields. Start monitoring the fields when the first diseases appear in the national registration network. Use the national thresholds for control.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

<https://registreringsnet.dlbr.dk/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Monitoring Diseases

Control of fungal diseases should be based on observations in the field. If necessary, consult the national decision support system (DSS) for thresholds e.g. Plant Protection Online (PVO) in Denmark.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

<https://plantevaerndonline.dlbr.dk/cp/menu/Menu.asp?SubjectID=1&ID=djf&MenuID=10009999&Language=da>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Check The Thresholds

Check the thresholds for control of DTR (*Drechslera tritici-repentis*), fusarium ear blight (*Fusarium culmorum*), yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*), brown rust (*Puccinia recondita*), and powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis*) during the season and decide whether one, two or three fungal sprays should be carried out. Use national thresholds e.g from LandbrugsInfo.dk, among others.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/basis/9/3/d/plantebeskyttelse_bekampelsestarskler_svampesygdome

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Brown rust pustles. Right: Powdery mildew. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Adapt Strategy And Dose

Adapt strategy and dose according to the varieties characteristics and precipitation conditions. Varieties and variety mixtures with different susceptibility require different treatments.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Unsprayed Spot

Set aside an untreated window to help assess the effect of spraying.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/6/b/f/pl_ipm_sproejte_og_doseringsvinduer_i_marken.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Clean Machinery

Thorough cleaning and washing of machinery the risk of transmitting loss-causing viral diseases between fields is reduced. Infestation of soil-borne viral diseases are rare, but there has been an increase in the number of cases. A complex of 3 different viral diseases, namely soil borne cereal mosaic virus (SBCMV), soilborne wheat mosaic virus (SBWMV) and wheat spindle streak mosaic virus (WSSMV).

Viral diseases transmitted by soil fungi can be very loss-causing and the virus can be retained in the fungus and be infectious for up to 20 years. The infection is typically spread by machines around the field and to other fields. There are only a few resistant varieties.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/0/a/b/faktaark_ipm_jordbarne_virusygdomme_i_vintersad.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Wheat Tan Spot And Fusarium

If previous crop is wheat, ploughing will reduce the infestation of wheat tan spot (DTR) (*Drechslera tritici-repentis*) and Fusarium (*Fusarium avenaceum*). When growing wheat after wheat in combination with reduced tillage, the risk of infestation with wheat tan spot (DTR) and Fusarium and thus Fusarium toxins due to infection from plant residues of wheat increases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: DTR symptoms. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Seeding Wheat Second Year

The second year's wheat should be seeded latest due to the risk of take-all (*Gaeumannomyces tritici*) disease. The risk of take-all disease is greater in second year with wheat than in 1st-year wheat. Early seeding and sandy soil is also factors that increase the risk of take-all disease (*Gaeumannomyces tritici*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Symptoms of take-all disease. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Early Sowing Promotes Barley Yellow Dwarf Virus (BYDV)

Early sowing increases the risk of infections with Barley yellow dwarf virus (BYDV). This is because the aphids (*Aphididae*) that are vectors for the diseases will migrate to the first established winter seed fields, where they have long time to transmit the virus.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Symptoms of BYDV. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Decision-Making Tools

The consistent use of decision-making tools can lead to a reduced use of pesticides. The basis for this is close observation of the crop and compliance with the damage threshold. Regional information from advisors and warning services is important for this. Use local forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases, e.g., offered by phytosanitary services.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Targeted use; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Balanced Fertilisation Based On Soil Samples And Mapping

Not only the types of fertilisers used, but also their dosage and timing of application have to be considered. It is known that a balanced use of fertilisers will improve the growing conditions for the plants. A stronger crop has a better resistance to pest and disease infestations and will be able to compensate for losses by producing new leaves. Soil analyses and mapping should be made once every 4-5 years in order to decide the fertilisation plans.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Use Forecasting Models

Use forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases, e.g., offered by phytosanitary services.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

<https://ipmguidelinesforgrains.com.au/ipm-information/making-informed-control-decisions/monitoring/monitoring-tools-and-techniques/#beat>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other

Conventional Seed Treatment

Conventional seed dressing is beneficial against various plant diseases. Due to the fact that the plant is protected from the beginning, it develops faster and may lead to reduced need for spraying later. However, the need must be considered.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other

Biological Treatment

Treating seed with a biological treatment can give the plant an advantage compared to untreated seeds during juvenile development. The protection against feeding and a faster youth development are possible advantages. The need should be considered.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Combined Harvesting Headers With Integrated Mulch Shredders

Shredding and scattering of crop residues can be used to destroy the pests within them. The resulting mulch layer reduces water evaporation, suppresses the growth of unwanted weeds and provides organic matter. This can improve soil fertility.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Maria Toader, Lars-Ole Hingst

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Crop Rotation & Choosing The Crops In Rotation

The practice of growing different crops sequentially on the same plot of land to improve soil health, optimise nutrients in the soil, and prevent pest, diseases and weed pressure. For example, soybean-maize-sunflower-wheat. An improper crop rotation results in a risk of multiplication of harmful diseases and pests in the soil.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Valentin Petrus

Photos: Valentin Petrus

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Healthy Seeds

The use of healthy and certified seeds has several advantages. During germination, the plant does not come into contact with possible pathogens, which allows the plant to develop better and establish quickly, which improves competition with weeds and insects.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Biodiversity: Use Drift Reduction Technique Along Field Borders

A stable field border without fertiliser application and impact on spray drift from herbicides can over time give opportunity for more flowering plants to emerge which can provide food for insects. Drift reduction technique prevents the negative direct effect on insects by drift from pesticides. A field edge or ditch edge with minimal impact from the activities inside the field surface will grow with perennial grasses and dicotyledonous species, which are usually not weeds inside the fields. In this way, there will be no room for cleavers (*Galium aparine*), barren brome (*Bromus sterilis* L.) and rat's tail fescue (*Vulpia myuros*), which easily spread into the field.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/2/1/c/faktaark_ipm_min_gode_markkant.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Cleavers (*Galium aparine*) (Aarhus University), middle: Barren brome (*Bromus sterilis* L.) (Aarhus University), left: Rat's tail fescue (*Vulpia myuros*) (Poul Henning Petersen, SEGES Innovation)

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Monitor Efficacy

Monitoring of the pest infestation level before and after the measure is important to decide whether a measure makes ecological and economic sense. Also to document the success of a measure to identify any potential.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Krefl

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Documentation Of Results

Documentation of results to measure the success of the crop protection strategy.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Plant Strengtheners And Biostimulants

Usage of plant strengtheners and biostimulants such as *Trichoderma atrobrunneum* (fungus), *Bacillus methylotrophicus*, and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (both bacteria) can stimulate plant growth. Also arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), endophytic bacteria, and the plant-growth promoting (PGPR) groups of bacteria, and chemicals such as humic acids, fulvic acids, amino acids, and plant growth promoting substances (auxins and cytokinins) can stimulate the plant growth. The products should be tested in field experiments for documentation of the effects.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft, Lars-Ole Hingst; Maria Toader

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Crop Protection Decision Based On Extension Services, Experts

Use the expertise from the extension services for recommendations of necessary treatments.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Site Specific Application

Application of pesticides should only be applied in areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture). Spot spraying can be used to control root weeds or other local problems. Variable rate applications can be used on under variable soil conditions.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft; Marian D. Thorsted

Use Certified Seeds

Use certified seeds or cleaned seeds of high quality from own fields. With certified seed you will get healthy seeds and new genotypes with a very low content of weed seeds. When using own seed, they have to be cleaned for weed seeds and only the large grains should be sown. The seeds should be coated only if seed analysis has shown a need for coating. Remember to pay an eventual breeder tax when using your own seed, which is a prerequisite for producing new high-yielding varieties that have good resistance and other desired characteristics. Look at the website sortsejere.dk for payment of breeders tax in Denmark.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Cereal ground beetle (*Zabrus tenebrioides* Goeze)

Cereal ground beetle (*Zabrus tenebrioides* Goeze) represents one of the most important pests of wheat in southeast of the Romania.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

<https://agronomyjournal.usamv.ro/pdf/2017/Art42.pdf>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Close Monitoring And Regular Observations Of Pests, By e.g. Visual Control, Traps, Nets

Pest monitoring supports the decision of counteracting a given level of infestation and to select the adequate control method. The classic monitoring approach of pests is based on placing a series of traps in the infested areas that are checked by human operators on a regular basis.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Aphids In The Autumn

Follow the development of aphids (*Aphididae*) in the national registration network if present, and by inspection in own fields. Spray when many aphids are found (2-3 per cent infested plants) or in high risk fields when warned. Aphids can transmit the barley yellow dwarf virus (BYDV). It can be difficult to detect the presence of aphids. The highest risk in fields sown early (before September 15 if Denmark) in the more mild areas of the country (southern and coastal areas).

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

<https://registreringsnet.dlbr.dk/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Aphids on wheat. Right: Symptom caused by BYDV. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Aphids - Unsprayed Window

Set aside an untreated area to help assess efficacy of spraying in autumn. The risk assessment for spraying against aphids (*Aphididae*) in autumn is based, among other things, on experience with infestation.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/6/b/f/pl_ipm_sproejte_og_doseringsvinduer_i_marken.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Symptom caused by BYDV. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Biodiversity - Unsprayed Buffer Zones

If you want to promote the conditions for insects and other organisms at the edge of the field, you can close the sprayer in a 4-6 meters wide zone along the field borders, not necessarily in the same place every year.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Aphids In Spring/Summer

Follow the development of aphids (*Aphididae*) in the national registration network if present, and by inspection in own fields. Use the national thresholds for control in Denmark e.g. on LandbrugsInfo.dk.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Registreringsnettet: <https://registreringsnet.dlbr.dk/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Aphids. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Monitoring For The First Aphids (*Aphididae*)

Start monitoring the fields when the first aphids (*Aphididae*) appear in the National registration network e.g. and during your own field inspection. Control of aphids should be done based on observations in the field. If necessary, consult the national decision support system for thresholds e.g. Plant Protection Online (PVO) in Denmark.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

<https://plantevaerndonline.dlbr.dk/cp/menu/Menu.asp?SubjectID=1&ID=djf&MenuID=10009999&Language=da>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Aphids. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Check The Thresholds For Control Of Aphids (*Aphididae*)

Asses the need for spraying. Find national thresholds e.g. on LandbrugsInfo.dk, among others.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/basis/9/4/2/plantebeskyttelse_bekampelsestarskler_for_skadedyr

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Aphids. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Pests - Use Reduced Dose

Use a quarter to half a dose if needed. A quarter to half a dose gives the highest net profit.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Pests - Follow The Flight Of Orange Wheat Blossom Midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*)

With a high percentage of wheat in the crop rotation, follow the flight of orange wheat blossom midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*) in a national registration network if present, or use pheromone traps in your own field.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/6/b/f/pl_ipm_sproejte_og_doseringsvinduer_i_marken.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Larvae of the Orange wheat blossom midge. Right: Adult Orange wheat blossom midge. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Resistance To Orange Wheat Blossom Midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*)

No need to control orange wheat blossom midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*) in resistant varieties. Some varieties are resistant, see the national trials for information.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Ikke i sortinfo

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests, Weeds

Seed Bed: Establish An Even And Uniform Seedbed

A uniform seedbed with soil tubers in appropriate sizes provides the best effect of soil-herbicides. Slugs (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*) are also inhibited. Even fields also minimize boom variation when spraying, thus achieving a more uniform dosage.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Slug. Right: Damage by slugs. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Uniform Seeding Depth

Uniform seeding depth provides uniform germination and thus good competitiveness against weeds. By increasing the seeding depth from 2 cm to the normal 4 cm, the slug (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*) infestation was reduced by approx. 70 percent. Placing the kernels on a moist bottom in the seedbed provides a better and more even germination.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Slug. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Detect Any Slugs (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*) Infestation On Time

Slugs (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*) can be a problem on clay soils. The effect of slug control has the best efficacy if the infestation is detected in time. Therefore, place slug traps after sowing if there is a risk of slug infestation.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Slug. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Slugs And Shallow Stubble Tillage

Late sowing increases the risk of injury by slugs (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*). If there is a risk of slugs on clay soil, a shallow stubble tillage should be carried out before sowing. Stubble cultivation disturbs the slugs, reduces the amount of food and dries them out. The best effect is achieved in dry conditions. The risk of high numbers of slugs on clay soils is 5 times higher after rapeseed than after cereals.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Slug. Right: Damage by slugs. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Late Seeding And Slugs

With late sowing, wheat has difficulties "growing from" a slug infestation.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Damage by slugs. Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Close Monitoring And Regular Observation

Close monitoring and regular observation of pests, e.g. visual controls, traps, or nets.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

<https://ipmguidelinesforgrains.com.au/ipm-information/making-informed-control-decisions/monitoring/monitoring-tools-and-techniques/#beat>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Application And Release Of Beneficials And Microbes

Application and release of other beneficials and microbes working against pests, e.g., *Coccinellidae* (ladybugs), *Chrysopidae* (lacewings), *Hymenoptera* (sawflies, wasps, bees) etc.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.agroline.ch/de/bioprotect/ratgeber/mikroorganismen>

Contributed by: Cordelia Krefl

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Promotion Of Ecological Habitats In Wheat Production Systems

Promotion of ecological habitats to support beneficial organisms through e.g. flowering strips, hedges or wildflower fallow.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Mating Disruption Of Pests

Usage of mating disruption techniques using e.g., food or pheromone traps.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Barren Brome (*Bromus sterilis*)

If Barren brome (*Bromus sterilis*) occurs a shallow harrowing max. 2 cm in depth should be carried out after harvest. Barren brome germinate in the dark (they dont have seed dormancy). Therefore, a superficial harrowing provokes a greater proportion of seeds to germinate immediately after harvest. Superficial harrowing prevents seeds of other weed species from going into germination dormancy. Work in the stubble should only be done prior to establishment of winter crops.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Barren brome. Poul Henning Petersen, SEGES Innovation; Aarhus University

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Control Couch Grass (*Elymus repens*)

Control couch grass (*Elymus repens*) with glyphosate 2-3 weeks before harvest, where permitted. Before grain harvest, couch grass is very sensitive to glyphosate, because of the large amount of aboveground biomass compared to the amount of underground stolons. However, pre-harvest glyphosate spraying is not allowed in EU in cereals for human consumption.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Couch grass. Poul Henning Petersen, SEGES Innovation.
Photo of leaf sheath by Aarhus University

Crop Rotation With Spring Sown Crops

Spring sown crops should be included in crop selection and rotation. Increase the proportion of spring crops if the population of grass (*Poaceae*) weeds is increasing. Spring crops sanitize grass weeds. Most grass species have significantly less germination in spring and have no or much less seed shedding in spring crops.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Machine Hygiene - Weeds

Clean the cutting tables of combines, carts and tractors when switching between fields with a lot of grass weeds, for example black grass (*Alopecurus myosuroides*) to fields without black grass. A lot of grass weeds are spread by machines. This makes it difficult to avoid spread, but it is worth doing as much as possible to avoid bringing in seeds from infected fields on to 'clean' fields.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/public/2/5/8/plantebeskyttelse_undga_spredning_ukrudt_sygdomme_jord

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Black grass. Left photos: Aarhus University, right: Poul Henning Petersen, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Purchase Herbicides Based On Previous Years' Knowledge

Weed control should be based on the experience from previous years, and adjusted in relation to the year's observations. Grass weeds in particular are difficult to recognize in the earlier stages of development, when chemical control is optimal and can be done with the lowest doses.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Ploughing Reduces Grass Weed

Ploughing reduces grass weed problems and delays the development of the grass wheat if with continuously cropping of winter cereals. Seeds of grasses relatively quickly lose the ability to germinate when lying on the soil surface. When ploughing, a smaller share of the seeds gets the opportunity to germinate.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Setup And Adjust The Plow Correctly

Setup and adjust the plow correctly in a way where the top layer of soil is laid down precisely on the furrow bottom. A high quality of ploughing work is a prerequisite for getting the best result of ploughing against grass weeds. With inadequate ploughing, this year's seed shedding can germinate already in the next crop.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Spring Application Of Herbicides

Based on knowledge of the susceptibility of varieties and the weed population, products are purchased for the spring and summer period. A stock of crop protection products ensure the flexibility to treat the crops at the optimal time.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Control Root Weeds While The Population Is Small

Thistles (*Cirsium*), field horsetail (*Equisetum arvense* L.), sow-thistle (*Sonchus* spp.) and other root weeds should be controlled while the population is still small. Against root weeds, no more than 80-85 percent effect is achieved by spraying. Therefore, early action on small populations is necessary. A multi-annual effort is required for large stocks.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: A thistle. Right: Field horsetail. SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Root Weeds - Spaying Technique

Use a high volume of water and a low speed when the majority of shoots are developed and 10-20 cm in height. With conventional spraying techniques, a minimum of 200 litres of water per hectare must be used to control root weeds. Air sprayers provide good coverage with smaller volumes of water.

IPM principles:	Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: A thistle. Right: Field horsetail. SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Glyphosate In Seed Beds Without Ploughing

Perform a treatment with glyphosate at least two days prior to tillage. Glyphosate treatment and harrowing immediately prior to sowing withers volunteer cereals and weeds. However, 7-10 days before when root weeds are present.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Adjust The Seed Rate According To Seeding Time

A high seed rate increases the risk of lodging, but strengthens competitiveness against weeds. Increased plant number may be relevant at a very high weed pressure. The seed rate should be adapted to the choice of seeding time.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Increased Seed Rate If Resistant Weeds

Where resistant grass weeds are present the seed rate should be increased by 25-50 percent to favour the suppression of resistant black grass (*Alopecurus myosuroides*), ryegrass (*Lolium* spp.) and rat's tail fescue (*Vulpia myuros*). If possible, use variable seeding rates on the basis of the density of grass weeds. However, spring crops will be most effective. Increased seed rate may increase the need for growth regulation.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Black grass; middle: Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*); right: Rat's tail fescue. SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Variable Rate Sowing In Fields With Variable Soil Types

To ensure a uniform establishment, it may be necessary to harrow extra prior to sowing on areas with a high clay content, and there may be a need to increase the amount of seeds. Prescription maps can be made in e.g. CropManager (field management APP) for variable seedrates. A VRA map for seeding can be made on the basis of the clay content or from experiences with establishment in different areas of the field, which will be an advantage.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: CropManager VRA map. SEGES Innovation

Strategic Ploughing

A switch between ploughing and plough-free establishment can speed up the reduction of weeds in the soils seedbank. When ploughing, the seedbank is mixed up entirely. When ploughing is omitted for 2-4 years, a large part of the seedbank will decay in the lower parts of the ploughing layer. Is ploughing

resumed again, the the seedbank is significantly reduced in the soil that is turned up.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Avoid Processing The Stubble

Avoid processing the stubble for as long a period as possible after harvest. Untouched stubble causes the greatest "mortality" for grass weed seeds and most other weed seeds. An exception is Barren brome (*Bromus sterilis* L.), where a thorough stubble processing (max. 2 cm) right after harvest causes the seeds to germinate. Most grasses have limited germination dormancy. When they are left on the ground, they will germinate the first occasion in a humid period. Seeds lying on the ground, in addition to germination, will also be largely destroyed by fungal infestations or eaten by birds and insects.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Barren brome. SEGES Innovation; Aarhus University

Without Ploughing - Shallow Stubble Tillage

Carry out a very shallow stubble tillage immediately after harvest, maximum 2 cm in depth. The stubble management creates a false seedbed, which promotes the germination of volunteer cereals, barren brome (*Bromus sterilis* L.) and other grasses in dry conditions. Avoid deep tillage, which places the weed seeds at a depth where they don't have opportunities for germination. Several shallow stubble treatments can increase the germination of weed seeds. In Denmark stubble till prior is allowed only ahead of establishment of winter crops. Stubble management is also an essential element in creating a proper seedbed for the next crop and reduces the risk of infestation by slugs (*Deroceras agreste*/*Deroceras reticulatum*) on clay soils.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photos: Left: Barren brome. Right: Slug. SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Stubble Management - As Shallow As Possible

Perform stubble management as shallow as possible. If there is a need to distribute straw and husks, this should be done with tools that work superficially in the upper 2 cm, e.g. straw tillers or harrow types with precise depth control.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Sow First-year Wheat And Fields Without Special Weed Problems First

Early sowing increases the emergence of weeds and grass weeds in the autumn.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Late Seeding If Grass Weed Pressure Is High

Fields with a high pressure of grass weeds should be seeded as late as possible. Post-poning the sowing time results in less emergence of weeds. Do not sow winter cereals in fields with a lot of black grass (*Alopecurus myosuroides*), ryegrass (*Lolium* spp.) and/or rat's tail fescue (*Vulpia myuros*) and windgrass (*Apera spica-venti*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars-Ole Hingst

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/WP3-9_IS_8_IWMPRAISE_2019.pdf

Photos: Left: Black grass; middle (left): Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*); middle (right): Rat's tail fescue; right: Windgrass. Aarhus University & SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Update Weed Maps Pre-harvest

Walk through the fields and make notes on field maps or in an App, e.g. Farmtracking, if there are weed species that have not been controlled sufficiently or are new to the area. In particular, map the grasses. Map also wild oats (*Avena fatua*) and root weeds.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

<https://en.seges.dk/Our-Competencies/Data-driven-management-and-software/FarmTracking>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Leaf sheath of wild oats. Aarhus University

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Register In 'Non-sprayed Patches'

Register and take notes of the species that occur in 'Non-sprayed Patches' and assess the effect of weed control. Before harvest there is a unique opportunity to assess whether or not the crop rotation is in balance in terms of preventing problems with weeds. Notes are valuable when communicating with the advisor about crop rotation and cultivation strategy.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Make Necessary Adjustments To Products And Doses

Follow the plant emergence in autumn and make necessary adjustments to product choices and doses based on the expectation to the weed population. At the optimal time of spraying, it is not possible to estimate the amount of weeds that will germinate. The choice of products must be based on previous years knowledge to the weed flora. The dose can be adjusted according to sowing time, as late sowing results in significantly less germination of weeds.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Soil Applied Herbicides In The Autumn

Autumn weed control should, as far as possible, be based on soil-applied herbicides. The soil-applied herbicides are generally less prone to the development of resistance in the weeds. Control weeds as soon as the tracks are visible in the field. The optimal time for controlling weeds in winter cereals is during the emergence, i.e. at the BBCH crop stage 10-11.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Foliar Herbicides in Autumn To Small Weeds

Apply foliar herbicides in autumn to small weeds in good growing conditions. The effect of foliar herbicides is best on small weeds with 0-2 true leaves.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Adjust The Dose Of Foliar Herbicides

Adjust the dose of foliar herbicides according to the size of the weeds and the spray conditions. If the optimal spraying time is missed, it is necessary to increase the dosage. Humid conditions are optimal for high effect of soil-herbicides, but experience shows, that they also have efficacy in autumn if spraying is carried out under dry conditions.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Avoid To Use ALS-inhibitors (SU-herbicides) In Autumn

The development of resistance is best countered by limiting the use of ALS-inhibitors (SU agents) in the autumn and reducing the population of grass weeds to a level that minimize the need for control in spring.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Good Practice For Use Of Prosulfocarb

Follow good practice for application of prosulfocarb to get maximum effect and avoid drift. Use minimum 200 L/ha water, coarse drops, a maximum speed of 6-8 km/h, and a boom height of maximum 50 cm. Maximum average temperature should be 15 degrees celcius. Assure the best possible coverage of the soil and the best effect of the herbicide. At the same time, the risk of wind drift is reduced.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/d/1/2/pl_ipm_faa_bedre_virkning_og_reduceret_afdrift_af_jordmidler.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Spraying Foliar Herbicides In The Morning

Spraying with foliar herbicides in the morning gives the best effect on weeds.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Unsprayed Window In The Autumn

An unsprayed window makes it possible both to assess the effect of the spraying carried out in the field and to get a 'snapshot' of the field's weed flora.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/6/b/f/pl_ipm_sproejte_og_doseringsvinduer_i_marken.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Limit The Number Of Chemical Weed Treatments

Limit the number of chemical weed treatments as much as possible and, if possible, avoid spring follow-up against weeds. The number of herbicide treatments is the most important factor for the development of resistance.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Reduce Seed Shedding

Reduce seed shedding from grass weeds that cannot be effectively controlled due to population size or resistance. Seed bank management is a way to use every opportunity to reduce seed shedding. Sow headlands over again when grass weeds cannot be effectively controlled. Provide mowing or desiccation through herbicides in patches with a lot of grass weeds during the flowering of the grass. Do manual weeding of single plants.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Spring Assessment If Weed Control Is Needed

Walk through the fields in early spring and assess the need for follow-up spraying against weeds. Assess whether headlands, borders or spot treatment is sufficient, for example against grass weeds, chamomile (*Matricaria/Tripleurospermum*) and cleavers (*Galium aparine*). Weed control in spring should be based on observations in the field. In this way, the needs can be assessed and control can be carried out with the most optimal choice of product and with the lowest possible dose. The necessary effect is assessed in relation to crop rotation and the need to avoid propagation of weeds prior to subsequent crops.

IPM principles:	Thresholds; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Cleavers. Aarhus University

Decide The Dose With A Decision Support System (DSS)

Determine the required dose with a decision support system (DSS), e.g. Plant Protection Online, effect tables or other types of information about the strengths and weaknesses of the products. In Denmark 'Plant Protection Online' provides efficacy tables and recommendations on weed control in relation to the products and necessary dosage.

IPM principles:	Alternatives, Dosage,
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://plantevaernonline.dlbr.dk/cp/menu/Menu.asp?SubjectID=1&ID=djf&MenuID=10009999&Language=da>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

No ALS inhibitors (SU-agents) In Spring If Used in Autumn

Do not use ALS inhibitors (SU-agents) to control grass weeds in spring if ALS inhibitors have been used in the autumn. Avoid development of resistance to ALS inhibitors by switching between active ingredients with different modes of action. In addition, the approvals prohibit certain combinations of ALS products in autumn and spring.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Winter wheat
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Control Wild Oats (*Avena fatua* L.) According To Legislation

Wild oats (*Avena fatua* L.) are covered by legislation, which means that you have an obligation to control or remove the plants in the fields.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Leaf sheath of wild oats. Aarhus University

Stale Seedbed

Preparation of a false/stale seedbed to stimulate germination of weed seeds and eliminate weeds before sowing wheat. Two to three weeks before the actual sowing date, the soil is prepared for sowing. This allows many weeds to germinate and be controlled before the actual sowing.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft, Lars-Ole Hingst, Marian D. Thorsted

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-false-seedbed-stale-seedbed/>

Without false seedbed

With false seedbed

Figure: Stale seed bed, SEGES Innovation

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Inorganic Materials

Application of inorganic materials such as salt ions or phosphites.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mulching

Apply mulch to suppress weeds.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Physical Measures

Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields to control weed.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Harrowing - Mechanical Weed Control

Winter wheat is a very robust crop. As long as the weeds are in the cotyledon stage, harrowing is most effective. Sunny and windy weather makes the weeds dry up faster. After emergence (BBCH 9-10) winter wheat is still very sensitive, but from BBCH 13 winter wheat is much more robust than weeds. A diagonal or crosswise harrowing to the direction of drilling can lead to a higher effectiveness. Mechanical weed control is an effective weed management method and it can provide effective weed management even when other methods are not possible.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst, Maria Toader, Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mechanical Weeding Without Plough

Instead of ploughing, elimination of weeds can be done mechanically using a harrow, weeder, cultivator, rotary hoe or other.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Weeds From Manure and Compost

Field and machine hygiene should ensure e.g. manure/compost, that is free from weed seeds, and crop residues are removed.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft, Maria Toader

Winter wheat

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

Prevent Lodging

Early sowing increases the risk of lodging in the following spring, especially at high seed rates. The crop biomass increases to a high level in the fall, and competition between the individual plants in the crop increases. A dense plant population will increase the tendency of the plants to stretch, thus increasing the risk of lodging in spring.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Catch Crops - Intercropping

Cultivation of catch crops can have different effects depending on the time of sowing and the selected crop or mixture of crops. The most important aspects are the protection of soil erosion, the prevention of nutrient leaching and the improvement of soil structure.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Plant Growth Regulation (PGR) In Spring

Plant growth regulation should only be used if the crop biomass is very dense or a variety with a very soft straw is grown. Use a digital lodging forecast and biomass maps e.g. in CropManager.dk to help assessing the needs. The following conditions increase the risk of lodging: early sowing, high seed rate, mild winter and early application of large amounts of nitrogen or organic soils. A targeted cultivation strategy in terms of variety selection, seed rate and nitrogen application is a more effective method to prevent lodging than chemical growth regulation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

CropMananger: <https://cropmanager.dk/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Leave An Unsprayed Plot When Using Plant Growth Regulation

Set aside an unsprayed 'window' for assessment of the efficacy. An unsprayed plot in the field will help evaluate the effect and need for growth regulation.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/-/media/landbrugsinfo/public/6/b/f/pl_ipm_sproejte_og_doseringsvinduer_i_marken.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

6. Maize

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Choice Of Cultivar

Selection of the maize variety according to the susceptibility to leaf spot fungi is not possible today. The information is not given from the breeder. The susceptibility of varieties to leaf spot fungi varies, but information is currently insufficient. In e.g. Denmark please consult SortInfo.dk to watch variety traits.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

sortinfo.dk

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Photo: Left: Southern corn leaf blight (*Drechslera*
Right: Maize eye spot (*Kabatiella zae*). Ghita C. Nielsen

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Pathogen Database

The pathogen database provides information on the impact of a pathogen on crops and how the crop affects pathogens. This allows for optimization of the cropping plan. The crop rotation plan should be set up in a way that pathogen host plants are prevented or not in the rotation before a crop that is highly impacted by that pathogen.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Use Of Plant Biostimulants

Biostimulants are vital to meet agricultural demands in a more sustainable manner. Biostimulants contribute to improve plant tolerance to biotic and abiotic stress (pest and disease infestations). The efficacy of the biostimulants should be shown in field trials.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.bpia.org/solutions-provided-by-biological-products-biostimulants/>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Balanced Fertilisation

Balanced fertilisation should be based on soil samples and mapping every 4-5 years. Not only the types of fertilisers used, but also their dosage and the timing of application should be considered. A balanced use of fertilisers will improve the plant's growing conditions. A stronger crop has a better resistance against pest and disease attacks and will be able to compensate for losses by producing new leaves.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

<https://www.fao.org/3/aq378e/aq378e.pdf>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests****Forecasting Models**

Usage of forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases, e.g., offered by phytosanitary services.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

<https://ipmguidelinesforgrains.com.au/ipm-information/making-informed-control-decisions/monitoring/monitoring-tools-and-techniques/#beat>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds****Field Margin Management**

For preventing weeds in the field margin, it is important to control them in the early growth stages through chemical or mechanical measures. If they are not controlled the weeds represent an important source of weed seeds to spread within the crop.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

<https://worldwidescience.org/topicpages/e/efficient+weed+control.html>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Combined Harvesting Headers With Integrated Mulcher/Shredder

Shredding and scattering crop residues in order to destroy the pests which are within them, such as larva of *Ostrinia nubilalis*. This action will also destroy weeds found in the maize crop at harvest. By the shredding operation the maize crop residues will decompose quicker.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

<https://edepot.wur.nl/425679>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photo: European corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*). Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Crop Rotation And Choosing The Crops In Rotation

Crop rotation is the practice of growing different crops sequentially on the same plot of land to improve soil health, optimise nutrients in the soil, and prevent pests, diseases and weed pressure. A good example of crop rotation for maize could be soybean-maize-sunflower-wheat. Johnson grass (*Sorghum halepense*) and cockspur grass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) develop well in maize crops and they are among the most important weeds in maize crops, while winter cereals do not favor their development. *Fusarium graminearum* develops well in maize monoculture or when maize follows after wheat. An insufficient crop rotation results in a risk of multiplication of harmful diseases and pests in the soil, as well as weeds specific for maize crop.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

<https://rodaleinstitute.org/why-organic/organic-farming-practices/crop-rotations/>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photos: *Echinochloa crus-galli* to the left (Maria Toader, USAMVB), *Fusarium* in maize to the right (Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation).

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Companion Cropping

Grow maize in combination with other crops such as field bean, chickpea, soybean or turnip. This can stimulate growth and reduce pest risk with the "push and pull" technique.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iimr.icar.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/National-Maize-Seminar-2020-Souvenir.pdf>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Resistant Cultivars

To grow pest- and disease-resistant varieties/hybrids in agricultural production is a basic component of IPM. It is important to know which hybrids to choose for maize cultivation in order to prevent disease or pest attacks.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

<https://bsppjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/ppa.13365>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Plant Strengtheners And Biostimulants**

Usage of plant strengtheners and biostimulants such as *Trichoderma atrobrunneum* (fungus), *Bacillus methylotrophicus* or *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (both bacteria). The efficacy of these products should be tested in field trials.

IPM principles:	Alternativer; Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

<https://uvadoc.uva.es/bitstream/handle/10324/57112/Combined-use-Trichoderma.pdf?sequence=1>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Monitoring**

Crop protection should be based on observed pest infestation levels monitored in the field.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335320605_An_overview_of_crop_loss_assessment_in_maize

https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/pnaax152.pdf

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Crop Protection Based On Official Thresholds

Crop protection based on thresholds, respectively taking decisions to apply treatments and control operations when a threshold is reached. There are specific thresholds used for each organism.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9803-2023-INIT/en/pdf>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Decision Based Crop Protection From Systems For Warning And Forecast**

Choice of the crop protection strategy is based on warnings and forecastings issued either from the forecasting models and tools used by farmers or issued by public or private institutions.

IPM principles:	Monitoring, Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Crop Protection Decision Based On Extension Services**

A suitable crop protection strategy for maize can be based on crop experts from the extension services.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Reduced Application Frequency**

Reduction of the frequency of pesticide application whenever possible. The more times and the higher doses are used the higher risk for resistance development.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Precision In Crop Protection

Application of pesticides only on those areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture). Spot spraying or variable rate application can be used.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Photo: Variable rate application in Crop Manager, SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Use Recommended Doses

Stick to the recommended doses of the pesticides.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Drift-reduction Application**

Drift-reducing application techniques increase the efficacy of spraying and reduce the drift especially when applying pesticides under the least favorable conditions.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Different Resistance Classes

Using pesticides that work differently or have different resistance classes should be used on a regular basis to prevent resistance development.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Evaluation

Monitor the infestation levels before and after the measure of e.g. pesticide applications to assess the success of the crop protection strategy in maize production.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

<https://repository.cimmyt.org/bitstream/handle/10883/817/95071.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y->

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Exclusion Of A Small Area Of The Field**

Test efficacy of measures by excluding a small area of the field and compare it to the treated area.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Documentation Of Results

Document results to measure the success of the crop protection strategy.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Crop Rotation

A multi-segmented crop rotation with winter and summer crops, as well as leaf and stalk crops, reduces the disease pressure of plant specific weeds, pests and diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://edepot.wur.nl/172092>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Crop Protection Decision Based On Extension Services, Experts

To choose a suitable crop protection strategy for maize, based on extension services and experts.

IPM principles:

Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other****Reduced application frequency**

Reduction of the frequency of pesticide application whenever possible.

IPM principles:

Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Biological Control Of Harmful Organisms

The proper use of selected microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi and viruses have several benefits for agriculture. These include a healthy soil microbiota, biological production of important compounds that promote plant health, and to be used as biocontrol agents (BCAs) that provide protection from plant pathogenic microorganisms, e.g. *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Trichogramma ichneumon* are used against *Ostrinia nubilalis* pest.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://repository.uaiasi.ro/xmlui/bitstream/handle/20.500.12811/605/LSA_v.61_nr.1_Is%20biological....pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photo: European corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*). Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Use Of Bioinsecticides

Control of *Tanymecus dilaticollis* (maize leaf weevil) by using bioinsecticides (organic extract) from the *Fabaceae* family , e.g. use of bioinsecticides for seed treatment such as Neem-TS, Laser 240-TS and Bactospeine DF-TS in a rate of 2.5 g/250 grams of seeds, or use of bioinsecticides for vegetation treatment in early growth stages, such as Neem-TV and Laser 240-TV in rate of of 150 ml/ha.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Georgescu-Emil/publication/346271108_Test_of_some_insecticides_for_Tanymecus_dilaticollis_Gyll_control_in_organic_agriculture_conditions/links/6047715d299bf1e078667093/Test-of-some-insecticides-for-Tanymecus-dilaticoll

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Good Knowledge To Maize Pests And Diseases**

The biological and morphological characteristics of the pests and diseases and the mode of damage influence the choice of the best pest control methods.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://plantwiseplusknowledgebank.org/doi/full/10.1079/pwkb.species.54122>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Close Monitoring And Regular Observations Of Pests, e.g. Visual Control, Traps, Nets

Pest monitoring supports the decision of counteracting a given level of infestation and to select the adequate control method. The classic monitoring approach of pests is based on placing a series of traps in infested areas that are checked by human operators on a regular basis.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Prevent Oat Cyst Nematodes (*Heterodera avenae*) By Choosing Resistant Barley and Oat Varieties**

All cereals, including maize, propagate oat cyst nematodes. Yields losses due to oat cyst nematodes differs. There are only resistant spring barley and oat varieties. A reduction in the number of nematodes of 40-60 % can be expected every year when a non-host crop or a resistant cereal is grown.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

<https://repository.cimmyt.org/bitstream/handle/10883/1267/93390.pdf>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Pests Rarely Have Economical Significance In Denmark

Frit flies (*Oscinella frit*) rarely do damage to maize. Frit flies can only do harm in the 1.5-2 leaf stage, and usually maize grows quickly past this stage of development in warm weather. Aphids (*Aphididae*) most often appear so late that control is not relevant. When growing maize 2-3 years after ploughed grass, infestation of the wireworm larvae (*Agriotes* spp.) may occur. With grass as previous crop, crane fly larvae may occur. Crane flies (*Tipula paludosa*) attack all crops, but maize is least susceptible to infestation. There are no options for chemical control. The european corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*) is a new pest that is spreading in Denmark, but control is not yet relevant. Ploughing reduces the risk of infestation.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

<https://cropscience.bayer.co.uk/agronomy-id/pest-and-slugs/frit-fly>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Avoid To Waste Seeds At Sowing

Seeds lost when they are poured into the seeder and in the headlands attracts birds to the field. They may eat lots of seeds and cause damage to the crop even before emergence.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://www.groupe-techna.com/en/natural/advice/damage-birds-corn-crop>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Prevention And Control Of *Tanymecus dilaticollis***

Agrotechnical measures and appropriate crop rotation lead to the reduction of pest populations, and the destruction of weeds has the effect of shortening the life span of adults and their reproduction due to lack of food.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://plantwiseplusknowledgebank.org/doi/10.1079/pwkb.species.54122>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Trichogramma As Biocontrol Agent

Application of *Trichogramma ichneumon* flies against the corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*).

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.agroline.ch/de/bioprotect/ratgeber/mikroorganismen>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photo: European corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*). Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

***Bacillus thuringiensis* As Biocontrol Agent**

Application of *Bacillus thuringiensis* against the corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.agroline.ch/de/bioprotect/ratgeber/mikroorganismen>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photo: European corn borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis*). Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

***Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* As Biocontrol Agent**

Application of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* against the corn rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.agroline.ch/de/bioprotect/ratgeber/mikroorganismen>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Photo: *Diabrotica* on maize plant. Maria Toader, USAMVB

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Close Monitoring And Regular Observation**

Close monitoring and regular observation of pests, by e.g. visual controls, traps, nets.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

<https://ipmguidelinesforgrains.com.au/ipm-information/making-informed-control-decisions/monitoring/monitoring-tools-and-techniques/#beat>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Application And Release Of Beneficials and Microbes**

Application and release of other beneficials and microbes working against pests, e.g., *Coccinellidae* (ladybugs), *Chrysopidae* (lacewings), *Hymenoptera* (sawflies, wasps, bees) etc.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.agroline.ch/de/bioprotect/ratgeber/mikroorganismen>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Pesticide Selection

Make sure to select a product tailored exclusively to the harmful organism.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:167:0001:0123:en:PDF>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Enhancement Of Ecological Habitats

Enhancement of ecological habitats, to improve the abundance of natural predators of the pest.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/natural-enemies/conservation-and-enhancement-of-natural-enemies/4CFDDDDCF812C81F31C4237BE0D62705>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Nematodes Support Tool

Plant parasitic nematodes pose a significant threat to crop yield and quality, with important groups including cyst, root-knot, root-lesion, stem, and free-living nematodes. The most effective way to manage nematodes is through healthy crop rotations, alternating between host and non-host crops or varieties to reduce infestation rates in the soil. To support this, the model contains information about the susceptibility and tolerance of 70 crops to 32 nematodes, though the databases are not soil- or country-specific. The model provides risk information based on specific crops, including green manure crops, and crop rotation, with user-provided farm-specific input. Created by the H2020 project Best4Soil and based on the Dutch model www.aaltjesschema.nl developed by Wageningen University and Research, the model assumes that the user-selected plant parasitic nematodes are present in the field.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

<https://nematodes.soilhealthtool.eu/en-gb/Nematode-scheme>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Monitoring Of Weed Seed Input Via Manure And Compost**

Check the contamination with weed seeds in manure and compost, and make sure that they are free of germinable seeds before using them.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Spot Spraying Based On Drone Maps

Several weed species appear in spots, and should be treated with spot spraying. A drone overflight can locate the spots and an application map for spot spraying can be made for the sprayer, e.g. Thistle-tool in CropManager.dk.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/IWM_TS_28_Spot-spraying.pdf ,
<https://www.pix4d.com/blog/drone-mapping-spraying-invasive-species/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Photo: Thistle spot located with drone in cereal field, Rasmus Emil Jensen, SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Resistance Test Of Weeds

If there is a reduced effect of the herbicides used and a suspicion of resistance, then a test should be submitted to test for resistance in a laboratory.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.agricentre.basf.co.uk/Documents/marketing_pages_files/autumn_cereals_files/academy_supplements_files/wrag_herbicide_resistance_testing.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Row Injection Of Slurry And Precision Application Of Fertilizer

With precision application of nutrients, it is the crop that is fertilized and not the weeds, this improves the crop's competition against weeds.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

<https://samson-agro.com/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Drainage

A well drained arable soil gives the best conditions for good crop growth. Be sure to drain wet spots, as several weeds will often spread from damp areas to other areas of the field.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.fao.org/3/r4082e/r4082e03.htm>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Eliminate Irregular Field Parts

Eliminate irregular field parts from the rest of the field. Often, field corners with poor access for machinery and wet areas will be best suited for fallow or other purposes. Cutting off these areas will often reduce the immigration of weeds such as cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*)

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

<https://worldwidescience.org/topicpages/w/weed+control+challenges.html> ,
<https://www.feedipedia.org/node/451>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Registration Of Areas With Weeds For Follow-Up**

Use e.g. the Farmtracking app to register 'hotspots' with weeds, such as root weeds, so that the information are retained and can be used in planning an effort the following year.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

<https://en.seges.dk/Our-Competencies/Data-driven-management-and-software/FarmTracking> ,
https://manoa.hawaii.edu/hpicesu/DPW/SAILER_2006/05.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Check Control Efficacy Before Rows Closes

Detecting a weed problem in time, gives the best opportunities to intervene with preventive measures that reduce further multiplication, e.g., cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), resistance in annual meadow-grass (*Poa annua* L.) and root weeds.

IPM principles:	Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://worldwidescience.org/topicpages/w/weeds+echinochloa+crus-galli.html>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Photos: Annual meadow-grass. SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Prevention Of Cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), Green Bristle-grass (*Setaria viridis*) And Root Weeds

Maize thrives well in monoculture, so it is the consideration of preventing propagation of weeds and possible remediation of a weed problems that determines the extent to which there is a need to rotate maize with other crops. Cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) and green bristle-grass (*Setaria viridis*) are shade-sensitive and, due to the late germination, do not do well in grass, winter and spring cereals and other crops that provide competition at their time of emergence. Mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris* L.) is difficult to control in maize, but can be effectively controlled in cereals or in stubble. Maize in crop rotation also provides an opportunity to prevent the development of herbicide resistance.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rCqOmBm5fus>https://edisciplinas.usp.br/pluginfile.php/4480121/mod_resource/content/1/ref.3.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Photos: Green bristle-grass. Aarhus University

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Spraying Before Inter-row Hoeing

In the establishment phase, maize is very sensitive to competition from weeds. The first spraying must be effective, not leaving weeds inside the row. If the timing is not perfect, the dose must be adjusted. The next time the interrow hoeing can be used.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/IWM_TS_24_inter-row_hoeing_row_crops_WP2-9.pdf <https://www.hutchinsons.co.uk/early-weed-control-is-vital-for-protecting-maize-yields/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Ensure An Even Seedbed For Inter-Row Hoeing.**

When the field is as even as possible, a uniform cut is achieved throughout the entire working width, and gives the opportunity to drive with a uniform depth of 4-5 cm

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/IWM_TS_24_inter-row_hoeing_row_crops_WP2-9.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Inter-row Hoeing After Spraying**

Clean away weeds that has survived after chemical control, and do it as early as possible before the weeds compete with the maize and cause the cleaning aggregates to clog. Weeds that have survived the first and/or second spraying are usually difficult to control satisfactory even with high doses. A row cleaning performed close to the row is usually more effective than a chemical solution.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://d-nb.info/1222137550/34>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Mounting For Inter-row Hoeing**

Mount hoes/discs that provide good overlap and throw soil into the row. An overlap of about 5 cm with new hoes/discs ensures that mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris* L.) and other 'tough' weeds are cut and loosened. On machines with goosefoot hoes, wide hoes in the middle will move soil out to the outer hoes, which pile approx. 5 cm of soil on top of weeds inside the row

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.bednar.com/en/inter-row-cultivation/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Adjustments For Inter-row Hoeing

Adjust the inter-row weed hoe to run no more than 5 cm from the row and no more than 5 cm in depth. Maize with 5-6 leaves has roots with a depth of 5 centimeters, which reach about 5 cm out from the plants. Cleaning at a depth of 5 cm and 5 cm to the row, has in experiments, not caused damage to the crop. A thorough cleaning provides the best release of the weeds so that as many weeds as possible dry out.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0472/13/2/421> , <https://www.hutchinsons.co.uk/early-weed-control-is-vital-for-protecting-maize-yields/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Purchase Of Herbicides

Purchases of herbicides should be based on previous years' knowledge. Timing is important when controlling weeds in maize. Products should be purchased in advance to ensure the the first spraying can be carried out at the optimal time.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0472/13/2/421>

<https://www.hutchinsons.co.uk/early-weed-control-is-vital-for-protecting-maize-yields/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Effect Tables Or Effect Profiles Of Herbicides

Use effect tables or effect profiles of herbicides in a decision support system, e.g. Plant Protection Online, to get an overview of the strengths and weaknesses of the products. Efficacy tables and profiles in Plant Protection Online are results from experimental testing of the products, and they show the strengths and weaknesses of the agents.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Planteværn Online :
<https://plantevaernonline.dlbr.dk/cp/menu/Menu.asp?SubjectID=1&ID=djf&MenuID=10009999&Language=da>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Split Spraying Strategy

Keep in mind that the best control strategy is split spraying on small weeds. It may be followed up with a third spraying to control late emerging weeds or root weeds.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://extension.psu.edu/introduction-to-weeds-and-herbicides>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Chemical Control On Small Leaves.

Carry out the first spraying before the weeds have more than 0-2 leaves, to achieve the best effect at low doses. Especially species such as cranes-bill (*Geranium* spp.), speedwell (*Veronica* sp.) and black bindweed (*Polygonum convolvulus* L.) must be controlled early to achieve sufficient effect.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

<https://croprotect.com/weeds/cranesbill-1>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Photo: Cranesbill. SEGES Innovation

Adjust The Dose

For an effective control the dose should be adjusted if the spraying time for the first spraying is postponed. Insufficient effect in the first spraying means that higher doses must be used later. The total cost and consumption of herbicides will be lowest by adjusting the dosage in the first spraying.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://worldwidescience.org/topicpages/h/herbicide+chemical+control.html>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Control Of Cockspurs (*Echinochloa crus-galli*)

In case of occurrence of cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) or green bristle-grass (*Setaria viridis*), it is necessary to have a control strategy that is both effective and prevents the development of ALS-resistance (resistance to products with acetolactate synthase as mode of action). In addition, the strategy must be adapted in relation to whether cover crops are to be established. Get inputs from your advisor.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Phots: Left: Cockspur. Right: Green bristle-grass. SEGES Innovation; Aarhus University

Early Control Of Cranes-bill (*Geranium spp.*)

Use quick control of emerging weed species, such as cranes-bill (*Geranium spp.*), with glyphosate during the years when weeds germinate before the crop. Cranes-bill is difficult to control when it has developed leaves. In years of slow maize germination, cranes-bill will emerge before the maize, and early glyphosate use make the timing of the subsequently sprayings better.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

https://content.ces.ncsu.edu/pdf/chemical-weed-control/2023-02-09/VIIWEED_CONTROL.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Photo: Cranes bill. SEGES Innovation

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Decision Support Tool Used For Mixtures And Doses

Use a decision support tool, e.g. Plant Protection Online, when choosing the mix and dose of products. Suggestions for weed control from Plant Protection Online provide a starting point for choosing the products and dose. The proposal is in line with the experience and knowledge gained in the field of weed control in maize.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Planteværn Online :
<https://plantevaernonline.dlbr.dk/cp/menu/Menu.asp?SubjectID=1&ID=djf&MenuID=10009999&Language=da>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Avoid Weed Resistance

Use product mixtures and alternate between active ingredients with different mode of action to reduce the risk of development of resistance in the weeds. The ALS inhibitors (e.g. Iodosulfuron-methyl-Na) should be used in combination with mesotrione and/or other agents that have other modes of action.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

https://grdc.com.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0036/593883/Post-emergentWeedControl_Approved-03112023.pdf?utm_source=website&utm_medium=download_button&utm_campaign=pdf_download&utm_term=National&utm_content=Understanding%20post-emergent%20herbicide%20weed%20

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Glyphosate For Ploughing-free Establishment**

Glyphosate should be used to control weeds and cover crops during ploughing-free establishment. Established weeds cannot be effectively controlled after the emergence of maize.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/68948>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Diflufenican With Large Stocks Of Speedwell (*Veronica* spp.)**

Diflufenican product should be used in fields with a large stock of speedwell (*Veronica* spp.). Speedwell is difficult to control effectively with the products that can be used after the emergence of maize.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://hortsense.cahnr.wsu.edu/fact-sheet/weeds-speedwells-veronica-spp/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Harvest Hygiene

Clean cutting tables on forage harvester, silage wagons and tractors for material that contains weed seeds, when switching from fields WITH cockspur (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) to fields WITHOUT cockspur. Seeds of cockspurs and others are primarily spread with soil on machines and with plant residues on the maize harvester and silage wagons. This makes it difficult to avoid spread, but it is worth doing as much as possible to avoid dragging soil and crop residues from infected fields into 'clean' fields.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Follow-up; Anti-resistance; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7qciNQ31ocE>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Seed Quality

The seeds should have a good vitality and sow the maize in a well-prepared seedbed. A good establishment forms the basis for a high crop biomass later in the growing season, which makes the crop more competitive to late emerging weeds or weeds that have not been controlled satisfactorily.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362161758_Yields_and_weed_management_of_sweet_corn_as_influenced_by_seedbed_preparation_methods_and_wheat_residues_rates

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Wait For The Right Soil Temperature**

When the daily average soil temperature at a depth of 10 cm has passed 8 °C and the weather forecast shows continuously rising temperatures, a fast and safe establishment of maize is achieved.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://eos.com/blog/soil-temperature/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mechanical Weeding

Mechanical weed control is an effective weed management method and it can provide effective weed management even when other methods are not possible and can outperform them in some situations. In Romania, for the maize crop, it plays a supporting role.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

<https://edepot.wur.nl/116036>

Contributed by: Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Field And Machine Hygiene

Field and machine hygiene through e.g. manure/compost free from weed seeds or removal of crop residues, so that the spread of weeds within and between fields is prevented.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Stale Seedbed

Preparation of a false/stale seedbed aims to make the weed seeds germinate and be controlled before maize sowing, through chemical or mechanical operations.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.bhu.org.nz/wp-content/uploads/sites/155/ffc-files/weed-management/false-and-stale-seedbeds--the-most-effective-non-chemical-weed-management-tools-for-cropping-and-pasture-establishment-2015-ffc-merfield.pdf>

Contributed by: Cordelia Krefl

Without false seedbed

With false seedbed

Figure: Stale seed bed, SEGES Innovation

Sowing Time And Seed Density

Correct seeding time supports early seed germination and fast sprouting to mitigate the growth of weeds. This together with proper seed density allow a fast crop canopy development which has an important effect on mitigation of weed growth. Also, early sowing allows plant emergence in a period when *Tanymecus dilaticollis*, the most important pest in maize crop in Romania, is less active due to lower temperature. Too high plant density leads to a specific microclimate (more humid) inside the crop canopy, which is favorable for the development of certain pathogens.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/fg_32_cropping_design.pdf

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft, Maria Toader

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mechanical Weeding With Plough

Usage of the plough to eliminate weeds mechanically.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/fg_32_cropping_design.pdf

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Inorganic Materials

Application of inorganic materials such as salt ions or phosphites.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/materials-science/inorganic-chemical>

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Mulching

Apply mulch to suppress weed.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Physical Measures

Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields to control weed.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Cordelia Kreft

Maize**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Mechanical Weeding Without Plough**

Usage of other instruments than the plough to eliminate weeds mechanically.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

<https://edepot.wur.nl/116036>

Contributed by: Cordelia Krefl

7. Potato

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Reduction Of Early Infestation Of Late Blight (*Phytophthora infestans*).

At least 3-4 years between potatoes is needed to obtain a good reduction of early infestations with Late blight. The resting spores (oospores) can survive in the soil for 3-4 years, and can infect healthy potato plants during germination. The disease is soil-borne and is a crop rotation disease, but can also spread via infected tubers and infected soil on tubers. This may be the reason why a connection has been found between early infestation of late blight and strained crop rotation.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

<http://www.endure-network.eu/content/download/4003/29720/file/Potato%20CS%20Guide%20Number%201%20LR.pdf>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of Potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Avoid Maize As Pre-Crop

Maize can cause the multiplication of free-living nematodes and perhaps stem canker (*Rhizoctonia solani*), which is why it should be avoided as a pre-crop to potatoes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases****Avoid Surplusses Of Nitrogen Fertilization**

It is recommended to divide the inorganic fertiliser in two applications and supplement with foliar sap analyses to determine the optimal N-level and the need for additional N in the end of June. Both too low and too high nitrogen levels may affect the disease level.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Avoid Having Potato Dumps

Dumps with potatoes contains inoculum and is a source to primary infection of Late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) in spring. Thus, avoid to have dumps, or cover them with plastic.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

<http://www.endure-network.eu/content/download/4003/29720/file/Potato%20CS%20Guide%20Number%201%20LR.p>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of Potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Burning Of Infected Potato Foliage

Burning off potato blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) infected potato foliage is an effective strategy to prevent the spread to neighbouring plants and fields. Make sure that burning is allowed.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases****Canopy Architecture Forming**

Greater distance between rows and plants in rows creates less favorable conditions for the development of fungal diseases in the field.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases****Certified Seed Prevents Ring Rot (*Clavibacter sepedonicus*)**

Certified seed prevents ring rot (*Clavibacter sepedonicus*), but also many other seed-borne diseases. The use of certified seed and the control of wasted potatoes prevent ring rot, which can survive in infested potatoes left in the field. In recent years, ring rot has not been found in Denmark.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

<https://www.platform.ipmdecisions.net/dss-info-list> ; (DSS Potato Late Blight; Hutton Criteria Late Blight Model)

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Conditions For Harvesting Potatoes

Good harvest weather is dry weather, so rot and spread of various fungal and bacterial diseases are prevented. The soil temperature should preferably be above 10 °C and the air temperature 12-14 °C or more. It provides the fewest injuries and the best wound healing. The operating speed of the unit (tractor + machine) should be adapted to the harvesting conditions (3-5 km/h), the working depth of the digging unit should be 12-15 cm, and the height of tuber falling on the machine should be below 30 cm.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Cultivars With Late Blight Resistance

The resistance of a cultivar to late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) can be very helpful in reducing the use of fungicides as part of an integrated control strategy. Both partial resistance and fungicides can slow down the development of late blight. Reports suggest that partial resistance in foliage can complement fungicide applications, leading to reduced application rates or longer intervals between sprays.

The use of resistant cultivars varies across Europe. In Western Europe, resistant cultivars are not widely used because the commercially important characteristics such as quality, yield, and earliness are usually not found in the cultivars that has late blight resistance. However, in countries where fungicides are not available or too expensive, using resistant cultivars is one of the most important ways to reduce blight damage. Choose resistant cultivars (against potato blight (*Alternaria solani*, *Phytophthora infestans*) if possible. Lists are provided by research stations.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

http://www.endure-network.eu/about_endure/all_the_news/potato_late_blight_a_4_billion_problem

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Lars Ole Hingst, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Tom van der Meer, Clara Sciffer

Photo: Healthy potatoes. Mark Manshanden, WUR

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Cultivation Technique: Pre-germination

Pre-germination to promote early seedling emergence (against black scurf; *Rhizoctonia solani*).
Germination 6-8 weeks before seeding, can reduce the risk of diseases and pests in the early stages of germination after the tubers are seeded.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer; Tom van der Meer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases****Disinfection Of Stores, Boxes, etc.**

Careful cleaning and disinfection helps preventing the spread of ring rot (*Clavibacter michiganensis*) and brown rot (*Ralstonia solanacearum*), but also reduces the risk of problems with e.g. gangrene (*Phoma spp.*), dry rot (*Fusarium spp.*) and/or silver scurf (*Helminthosporium solani*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools IPM tool for Diseases

DSS Potato Late Blight (BlightApp)

Late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) is a fungal disease that can harm crop foliage and tubers. To control this pest, farmers use fungicides, and the most important factors are the timing of spraying and the choice of fungicide. The Farm Maps BlightApp assists potato growers in implementing a preventative late blight control strategy throughout the season. The app recommends spraying before infection events are predicted, and alerts farmers to use curative or eradicate sprays if needed. The app uses continuously updated weather data and crop growth rate to provide tailored advice to each field, with fungicide recommendations based on the Euroblight fungicide table. The app also allows users to adjust crop growth and local disease pressure. Developed by Wageningen Research and tested in several countries, BlightApp is available across Europe.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

<https://www.farmmaps.net/en/Apps/Application/Late-Blight>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Photos: Symptoms of potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases
Early Blight (*Alternaria solani*) Monitoring And Warning

Based on the emergence date, variety type and climate data, the Alternaria TOMCAST model can predict when there is a risk of Early blight (*Alternaria solani*) infestation in the crop. Potatoes should be treated for early blight for the first time in risk fields when at inflorescence.

IPM principles:	Monitoring, Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.platform.ipmdecisions.net/dss-info-list>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of early blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools IPM tool for Diseases

Prevention Of Fusarium Dry Rot (*Fusarium oxysporum*)

Fusarium dry rot (*Fusarium ssp.*) is prevented by healthy seeding material. It can survive in the soil for several years after growing potatoes. Soil contamination with Fusarium is common, but infection through infected seed potatoes can also be of great importance.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of Fusarium dry rot. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

IPM 2.0 Control Strategy

IPM 2.0 control strategy uses several potato late blight (PLB) (*Phytophthora infestans*) systems to predict when to apply a fungicide. First, it is assumed that a resistant potato variety is being grown. When an outbreak of PLB is predicted by a decision support tool, and when the PLB strain has shown to be able to circumvent the resistance of the host variety, only then the specific fungicide will be applied. This significantly reduces the number of times sprayed and will also reduce the risk resistance development in the fungal strains.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

https://www.efpp.net/ipm2/Program%20for%20web%20site/Friday%20session%20and10/10_Kessel%20IPM2.pdf

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Photos: Symptoms of potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Monitoring And Warning Of Potato Late Blight (*Phytophthora infestans*)

Monitoring should be made locally and supported by different decision support tools for late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*). Follow the development in the local monitoring system and the DSS as a guide to the start of the blight control programme. Late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) is the most important disease in potato. The control of this disease is mainly based on the use of chemical protection. However, it should be remembered that the occurrence and development of the disease is closely related to the development of thermal and humidity conditions. The date of commencement and continuation of chemical protective treatments should be determined on the basis of the occurrence of optimal values of temperature and precipitation for pathogens and insolation. In the case of late blight, a properly performed first treatment prior to infection determines the effectiveness of further protection in the field and the achievement of a satisfactory yield.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

https://www.ipmdecisions.net/media/4jkcvxnf/ipm_factsheet-hutton-criteria-late-blight-model_v0001_print.pdf ; <https://projects.au.dk/blightmanager/potato-late-blight/infection-pressure-local> ; <http://www.endure-network.eu/content/download/3999/29692/file/P>

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Pathogen Database

The pathogen database provides information on the impact of pathogens on crops and how the crop affects pathogens (decline in propagation). This allows optimization of the cropping plan. By setting up the crop rotation in a way that pathogen host plants are prevented or not in the rotation before a crop that is highly impacted by that pathogen.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Pathogen scheme 2023
[Best4Soil Pathogen scheme](#)

Date : Tuesday, August 29, 2023
 Country : Netherlands
 Description : Test tool
 Soil Type : clay soil

Ctrl+Click on a cell for background information about the crop / pathogen combination

	Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. <i>api</i>					Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. <i>asparagi</i>					Fusarium solani f. sp. <i>phaseoli</i>					Phytophthora <i>castrorum</i>					Phytophthora <i>capsici</i>					Pythium <i>aphanidermatum</i>				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Potato	-	-	-	-	-	● C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	■ B	?	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	-	-
Wheat	-	-	-	-	-	● C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	-	-
Rapeseed	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	-	-

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Legend damage	
	unknown
	none
	little (0-15%)
	medium (16-35%)
	serious (36-100%)

Legend multiplication	
--	active population decline
?	host plant susceptibility unknown
-	none
●	poor
●●	moderate
●●●	strong
■	host, no quantification
R	variety dependent
G	resistant rootstocks for grafting exist
A	survival on debris or damping-off disease
B	root and tuber infection, or resting structures in soil
C	vascular infection
i	some information

Legend soil type	
1	sandy soil
2	reclaimed peat soil
3	sandy clay loam
4	clay soil
5	silty soil (loess)

Legend longevity	
<= 1	After [] years of growing a non-host crop the pathogen is only present in such low numbers it will never lead to yield loss
2 - 4	
5 - 10	
>= 11	

Scheme from Best4Soil.eu

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Prevention Of Blackleg/Soft Rot (*Pectobacterium parmentieri*, *P. atrosepticum*, *P. brasiliense*, *Dickeya solani* And *D. dianthicola*)

It is not possible to make chemical control of the bacterial disease Black leg/Soft rot disease (*Dickeya solani*/*Pectobacterium carotovorum*). The use of healthy seed material is important. There are many options for prevention and reduction of the disease, including clean machinery and crop rotation.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

<https://potatoes.ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/storage-practices-to-minimise-the-risk-of-soft-rot-and-blackleg-in-seed-potatoes>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of black leg/ soft rot Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases
Prevention Of Common Scab (*Streptomyces scabies*)

Common scab (*Streptomyces scabies*) can be prevented through crop rotation and seed material. Common scab is spread with soil and seed potatoes. The bacterium can overwinter on organic matter in the soil and soil infection is the main source of infection. The more frequently potatoes are grown on an area, the most infectious agent multiplies on the area and the greater the risk of infestation of tubers. Common scab can survive for more than 7 years. Irrigation can prevent scab.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Prevention Of Wart (*Synchytrium endobioticum*)

Prevention of potato Wart (*Synchytrium endobioticum*) must be prevented through crop rotation and healthy seed material. Due to its hardy resting bodies it can survive in the soil for up to 40-50 years. Many of the resistant varieties are starch varieties, which may have a slightly lower yield potential compared to commonly grown varieties. The spores can spread with soil and tubers between fields.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases
Prevention Of Verticillium wilt (*Verticillium albo-atrum*, *V. dahliae*)

The fungal disease Verticillium wilt (*V. albo-atrum*/ *V. dahliae*) is soil-borne and a crop rotation disease (PED), but can also spread via infected tubers and infected soil on tubers. There should be at least 3-4 years between potatoes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

<https://potatoes.ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/verticillium-wilt>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photo: Symptoms of Verticillium wilt. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Economy In Crop Rotation With Potatoes

The crop rotation is of great importance for the prevention of a number of problems with pests like leaf fungi, cyst nematodes, wart, stem canker (*Rhizoctonia solani*), PED, etc. Results from experiments and key figures from BusinessCheck (Danish APP) show that there is a yield reduction of 7-10 percent with close rotations with potato. In some cases, the yield decline can be double. Basically, it should be preferred to have at least three potato-free years ahead of potatoes for both consumption or industry. In the case of basic seed potatoes, it is mandatory with three potato-free years and in the case of pre-basic four potato-free years between potatoes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	5
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Reduction And Prevention Of Early Blight (*Alternaria solani*)

Early blight (*Alternaria solani*) can be partially prevented by the use of longer crop rotations and cultivation of less susceptible varieties. A limited knowledge is available about the susceptibility of the cultivated varieties.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of Early blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases
Seed Tuber Treatment With Chemicals And Visual Assessment

There is great variation from batch to batch and from year to year on the degree of infestation of the tuber-borne black scurf (*Rhizoctonia solani*), therefore in some years no effect of the treatments is found in experiments or at field level, while in other years large additional yields are found. Average yield increase in trials is 3-4% over several years. Treatments of seed potatoes with products that protect against stem canker is recommended.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

https://projectbluearchive.blob.core.windows.net/media/Default/Imported%20Publication%20Docs/AHDB%20Potatoes/Diseases/TuberTreatmentsFactsheet2868%2019_9_20%20WEB.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

Pre-sprouting Seed Potatoes

Pre-sprouting seed potatoes evens out and accelerates the emergence of plants by 1-2 weeks, which is conducive to the so-called "escape from the late blight" and shifts the vegetation to a period of better protection to diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases****The Best Pre-Crop Is Cereals, Where Straw Is Removed**

Ploughed soil with non-degraded straw increases the risk of root rot (*Rhizoctonia solani sp.*). Grass and beets as pre-crop also increase the risk of stem canker (*Rhizoctonia solani sp.*) and wireworm infestation. Grass as a forcrop will also make stringing difficult due to clumps of grass.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases
Oil Radish (*Raphanus sativus L.*) As Cover Crop Prior To Potatoes

A well-established cover crop of oilseed can provide a reduction in rattle virus infestations due to a reduction in free-living nematodes (*Trichodorus*), but can multiply other free-living nematodes such as lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus*). Oil radish helps to loosen the soil.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of free-living nematodes, Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Other

Desiccation Of Infected Foliage

Whenever the potato foliage is infected by a disease it can be desiccated in order to prevent the spread to other plants or the tubers. It effectively kills the plant and stops the propagation of diseases.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Decision Support Systems

SIMBLIGHT/ SIMPHYT/Akkerweb late Blight APP and others are systems that give important support for successful late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) control. The most important factors are the correct start of spraying, the adjustment of spraying sequences to the infection pressure and the choice of fungicide.

IPM principles:

Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up

Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms of Potato late blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Peppermint Oil

Peppermint oil is only/mainly used in potato storage. Not as repellent for pests or diseases. A natural alternative to prevent potato sprouting by monthly thermal fogging.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer, Lars Bødker

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Proper Location

A proper field location prevents the spread of late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) and viral diseases (transmitted by aphids (*Aphididae*)). Spatial isolation of 100-150 m from other potato crops reduces the risk of these diseases. As a preventive measure, care should also be taken to limit massive aphid infestations by spatial isolation from their winter hosts and from greenhouses, where pests find optimal conditions for development. A crop in close proximity to bushes or woodlots and after grassland poses a threat from wireworms (*Agriotes sp.*) and grubs. On the other hand, the location near water reservoirs is conducive to the occurrence of morning dew and fog, and by maintaining high humidity in the canopy, it can intensify plant infestation by fungal pathogens.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Decision Support Systems

The use of chemical plant protection products must be preceded by an assessment of the risk of plant pathogens. The best tools for this purpose are systems supporting decision-making in plant protection, which, based on mathematical models, on the basis of meteorological parameters, allow to determine the optimal dates for the use of chemical plant protection products. Studies have shown that potato protection carried out with the use of these system allows, without limiting its effectiveness, to significantly reduce the number of treatments and the amount of plant protection products introduced into the environment. Public available data from e.g. Poland on the threat from pests in individual regions of the country is published by the Institute of Plant Protection - National Research Institute on the Internet Platform of Pest Signaling.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Clara Sciffer

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Biological Plant Protection Products

Plant protection products based on natural substances are recommended due to their safety for the environment. Various types of plant extracts, biostimulators, antagonistic fungi and bacteria are recommended for the biological protection of potatoes. Biological products contain e.g. humic acids, bacteria of the genus *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* and fungi of the genus *Trichoderma*. The action of these products consists mainly in reducing the occurrence of pathogens in the soil and improving the growth conditions and improving the plants resistance to pathogens. Bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* inhibit the development of the fungal pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani*, which causes root rot, damping off and wire stem. Currently, preparations based on spinosad, azadirachtin and pyrethroids are available in Poland to control the Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*). Only products with documented effect from field trials should be used.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Tom van der Meer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other****Fatty Acids And Potassium Salts**

Soaps are contact insecticides; to be effective, they must be sprayed directly on the pest and must get into them while still wet. Dried residues have no residual effect against pests. Soaps are most effective against insects with tarry bodies such as aphids (*Aphididae*), but can also kill ladybugs (*Coccinellidae*), lacewings (*Chrysopidae*) and other natural enemies.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other****Fertilising And Analysing**

Proper fertilisation is as key to the development of resilient plants. Proper fertilisation means having the right amount of macronutrients and trace elements.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer, Clara Sciffer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other

Plant Extracts

Plant extracts (Mintoil, lavenderoil, orangeoil, onionoil, rapeseedoil) can be applied for repelling of different insects. Not all extracts are allowed to be applied against all types of insects.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other

Priming

Priming using endogenous plant hormones such as jasmonic acid or beta-aminobutyric acid induces the systemic defense mechanisms of the plant which in turn makes them more resistant to insects and fungal and/or bacterial diseases. Priming is also possible using biostimulants containing fungi spores. Effect of the product should be provided from trials.

IPM principles:	Prevention Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other

Roguing Of Seed Potatoes

Roguing of seed potatoes is essential to plant pest and disease-free potatoes. Having the availability of clean starting material is necessary to ensure a proper yield for the current year as well as the years following.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other****Urtica Extract**

Nettles (*Urtica*) extracts have an effect on the fecundity and work as anti-feedent of aphids (*Aphididae*). (registered as basis agent in the Netherlands).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	0
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Other
Use Of Certified Seed Potatoes

Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).

To reduce the spread of pests and diseases, healthy seed potatoes are of great importance. In this way, pesticides can be saved post-emergence and good quality can be achieved with appropriate yields.

It is very important to use certified seed potatoes that are free from the important potato pests such as ring rot (*Clavibacter sepedonicus*), bacterial wilt (*Ralstonia solanacearum*), yellow potato cyst nematode (*Globodera rostochiensis*) and viruses.

From germination of a sound tuber, the plants are not in contact with possible pathogens, which gives a good youth development. Better establishment also helps competing with weeds and insects.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Lars Ole Hingst, Clara Sciffer, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker.

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Crop Rotation

Crop rotation of potatoes in a diverse system with different annual and perennial crops, and changes between autumn and spring sown crops will result in a more resilient system with reduced pressure from pest and diseases.

Common practice in crop rotations in potato for consumption is often 1:3 or 1:4 years 1:4 or 1:5 years in seed potatoes. The longer period between potatoes the better for plant health, but there is also a trade-off for the economy.

Avoiding potato cultivation after fallow or perennial crops prevents damage caused by dung beetle (*Scarabaeidae*) and click beetle (*Agriotes*) larvae.

Best4Soil provides information on the host status and damage sensitivity of crops for a large number of nematode species and soilborne pathogens. Based on this information you can determine the optimal order to grow the different crops.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

<https://ipm.ucanr.edu/agriculture/potato/crop-rotation/>, <https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Cordelia Kreft, Clara Sciffer, Lars-Ole Hingst, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker.

Photo: Wire worms (larvae of the click beetle). Ghita C. Nielsen, SEGES Innovation

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Extension Services, Experts

Crop protection decisions should be based on extension services and experts.

IPM principles:	Thresholds
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Monitoring In The Field

Monitoring is carried out mainly on the basis of visual inspections in the field. In the case of soil pests, soil sieving is used. In the case of aphids (*Aphididae*) yellow water traps are used. Information on the severity of the occurrence of pests is the basis for pesticide intervention and future decision-making in relation to the choice of potato variety, crop rotation and location of the crop field. The condition for the effectiveness of this method is systematic observations and knowledge about pests. The decision to perform chemical treatments should be based on information on exceeding the economic thresholds for specific pests. Annual observation of weed infestation on a potato field is very important, especially in post-emergence application of herbicides.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	1
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.knpv.org/db/upload/documents/Artikelen_Gewasbescherming/KNPV_Gewasbescherming_535_ICM.pdf

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Clara Sciffer, Tom van der Meer

Proper Pesticide Application Technique (Sprayer Calibration, Weather Conditions)

The effectiveness of the treatment is determined by the correct calibration of the sprayer and a properly performed spraying procedure. It requires the right selection of nozzles, liquid pressure, working speed and boom height, which result in a precise application and exact dose of plant protection. To control diseases and pests, sprayers are used which at a pressure of 2 to 3 bar allow to obtain fine spraying, while for weed control, medium or coarse spraying should be applied (pressure from 0.5 to 1.5 bar). Fine drops of the working liquid will cover the sprayed plant surface thoroughly only when the slots on the booms are evenly spaced. The boom must be 40-60 cm above the plant surface when spraying. When spraying, keep a constant driving speed, not more than 5 km/h. Spraying is carried out at a wind speed of not more than 3 m/s and an air temperature of 15 to 20 degrees celsius on dry plants.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds****Site Conditions: Machine & Material Hygiene**

Machine and material hygiene is important to avoid the contamination of new fields with nematodes, yellow nutsedge (*Cyperus esculentus*), Jimsonweed (*Datura stramonium*), wireworms (*Agriotes spp.*) and black scurf (*Rhizoctonia solani*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	5
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Hygiene

Hygiene must be observed throughout the production of potatoes. This starts with healthy seed potatoes and a clean seedbed. During harvesting and storage, care must also be taken to reduce the risk for pests and fungi to multiply. This is even more important in the production of seed potatoes.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Selection Of Varieties

In Poland, the Post-Registration Variety Experimentation is carried out, the purpose is to check the yield of varieties registered in the country and their resistance to diseases and pests in local conditions. Selection of cultivars allows to identify those with greater resistance to *Phytophthora infestans* infection (causing late blight) and viral infections (Y and PLRV viruses). It is recommended to select cultivars resistant to potato cyst nematodes (*Globodera rostochiensis*, *G. pallida*). It is recommended to choose varieties characterized by a quick emergence and a fast growth rate in the initial vegetation period, as well as varieties producing a larger biomass of leaves, that improve the soil coverage and thus prevent the development of weed infestation. Variety selection must also be based on information about its demand on the market and its agrotechnical and environmental requirements.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Photos: Symptoms of Virus Y. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds
Organic Fertilisers

Fertilisation should be based on the use of organic fertilisers supplemented with mineral fertilisation. Proper fertilisation with NPK increases the defensive capabilities against pests and regeneration in the event of mechanical damage. Fertilisation in the form of organic biomass improves the microbiological properties of the soil, increases the content of beneficial microorganisms, and reduces the occurrence of soil pathogens of the genus *Fusarium* and *Streptomyces*. Exceedingly high doses of nitrogen prolong the vegetation of plants, delay the skin set process, which contributes to the increase in mechanical damage during harvesting, and reduces the storage life of tubers. Large amounts of nitrogen also increase the number of weeds. Nitrophilic species include most weeds found on potato plantations (e.g. *Chenopodium album*, *Stellaria media*, *Capsella bursa-pastoris*). Furthermore, the use of poorly digested manure or compost can cause the appearance of a large number of weeds.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds

Site Conditions: Field Hygiene

Avoid, monitor and intervene: 'volunteer potato plants': infection source of *Phytophthora infectans* (potato late blight), (black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge (*Cyperus esculentus*); jimsonweed (*Datura stramonium*), cyst nematodes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases

BOS Alternaria

Recently a decision support tool (DSS) for Early blight (*Alternaria solani*) has been developed by Wageningen University. The DSS can help making a decision about the timing of pesticide application against Alternaria. With that the effectiveness of the pesticide can be achieved and result in a reduction in the total amount of pesticides applied.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Photos: Symptoms of Early blight. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds****Knowledge To Herbicides**

Use an effect assessment scheme that provides an overview of the effect of different agents on different plant protection products. Different products have their strengths and weaknesses, which make it essential to use the proper product to the proper target. Plant protection products have to be used in an environmentally safe manner, in accordance with the label.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/IWM_TS_29_Herbicide-use.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker; Clara Sciffer; Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Click Beetle Traps

The larva of click beetles are wire worms (*Agriotes* spp.). The wire worms can cause significant damage in a potato crop. The traps serve as a monitoring tool in order to monitor thresholds on which to start managing practices.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Photo: Click beetle trap. Mark Manshanden, WUR

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests
Colorado Beetle Catcher

Colorado beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) can cause serious damage in a potato crop. Mechanical removal of Colorado beetles is possible either by using the 'Beetle eater' that sucks beetles from the foliage or by using the 'Colorado Beetle Catcher', a machine that shakes the beetles from the leaves and collects them in collection trays. This is also a crude form of monitoring as it automatically collects the beetles as well. The selectivity of this method might be limited. These can be controlled chemically however there are mechanical alternatives.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

<https://potatoworld.eu/news/new-machine-for-sustainable-pest-control-in-potatoes-the-colorado-beetle-catcher/>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Tom van der Meer

Photo: Colorado beetle catcher. Mark Manshanden, WUR

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Prevention Of Potato Cyst Nematodes

Cyst nematodes (e.g. *Globodera/Pratylenchus*) should be prevented by use of crop rotation and resistant varieties. Assuming that the population increases by a factor of 25 by growing a susceptible variety and the population decreases by 35 percent in the potato-free years, potatoes must not be grown more often than every 8 years if the population is to be kept unchanged. When growing resistant varieties, the number of potato-free years can be reduced. Although there are several varieties with broad resistance to the different species and pathotypes, a crop rotation of at least three potato-free years should be held and the cultivation of a resistant variety every other time to maintain a low risk.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

<https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/factsheets/12.pdf>; <https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Cutworm Model

Cutworms (e.g. *Agriotes* species) may cut off the stems of young plants during stand establishment. Later in the season they go into the soil and feed on the tubers. The model predicts the number of batches of vulnerable larvae (instar 1-3) currently active, based on first appearance of adult moth and subsequent larval development. Significant rainfall events cause high levels of mortality in larvae, which is included in the model.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.platform.ipmdecisions.net/dss-info-list>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

**Grow Crops That Do Not Propagate Free-living Nematodes
(*Trichodorus*)**

Free-living nematodes can cause great yield losses. Lilies and spinach do not propagate free-living nematodes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Symptoms caused by free-living nematodes. Lars Bødker, SEGES Innovation

Inspect The Soil For Nematodes At The Right Time

When a spot with poor plant growth is discovered in the field, try to take a sample as soon as possible in order to find out if nematodes are causing the poor growth. The nematodes are mostly found in the beginning of the growing season. Later on, the nematodes that were the cause can be gone. Taking samples in the autumn to see which nematode caused the damage in the preceding spring is of little or no use.

IPM principles:	Monitoring
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/external_factsheets/38.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

NemaDecide

NemaDecide supports farmers with their nematode management in potato cultivation. NemaDecide converts sampling results into informative field infestation levels. The effect of decisions regarding crop rotation and control measures on nematode development and yield loss are presented in a user-friendly manner.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

<http://www.nemadecide.com/english/home.html>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Nematodes Support Tool

Plant parasitic nematodes pose a significant threat to crop yield and quality, with important groups including cyst, root-knot, root-lesion, stem, and free-living nematodes. The most effective way to manage nematodes is through healthy crop rotations, alternating between host and non-host crops or resistant varieties to reduce infestation rates in the soil. To support this, the model contains information about the susceptibility and tolerance of 70 crops to 32 nematodes, though the databases are not soil- or country-specific. The model provides risk information based on specific crops, including green manure crops, and crop rotation, with user-provided farm-specific input. Created by the H2020 project Best4Soil and based on the Dutch model www.aaltjesschema.nl developed by Wageningen University and Research, the model assumes that the user-selected plant parasitic nematodes are present in the field.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

<https://nematodes.soilhealthtool.eu/en-gb/Nematode-scheme>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Pay Attention To Grass In Crop Rotations With Potatoes

Wire worms (*Agriotes* spp.) have a 1-3 year life cycle and are harmful to potatoes.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Potato Leafhopper Nymph (*Empoasca* spp.): Monitoring And Warning

Use the newsletters from the extension services and monitoring options from e.g. glue plates to determine the need for control. Timing is important to achieve the best effect.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Registration Of Leaf Ticks**

Leaf ticks (*Lygocoris pabulinus*) are controlled by the beginning of entrance to the fields, often a marginal treatment is sufficient, as the ticks enter the field from hedgerows and thickets. There is no system for early warning. Control is seldom rentable.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Plan Renting/Leasing Of Fields For Seed Potatoes

Renting/leasing of fields for seed potatoes should always be planned well in advance so a thoroughly check for cyst nematodes (*Globodera*) can be carried out the year before. This also applies to own propagation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Nematode Resistant Cultivars

Choose resistant cultivars (against nematodes). Lists are provided by research stations. Cyst nematodes (e.g. *Globodera/Pratylenchus*) should be prevented by use of crop rotation and resistant varieties. When growing resistant varieties, the number of potato-free years can be reduced. Although there are several varieties with broad resistance to the different species and pathotypes, one should keep a crop rotation of at least three potato-free years and the cultivation of a resistant variety every other time to maintain a low risk.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Clara Sciffer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Soil Cultivation (Tillage, Loosening, Plowing)**

Timely treatments reduce the number of wireworms (*Limoniusspp.*) and grubs (*Scarabaeidae*).

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Soil pH

Ensure a soil pH that reduces the risk of nematodes and soil-borne diseases. Potato is also more affected by *Globodera rostochiensis* (Yellow potato cyst nematode) when pH becomes low.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/external_factsheets/36.pdf

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Tagetes For Nematode Control

When *Tagetes patula* is used for nematode control in the temperate zones like the Netherlands, after 3 months the tillage layer is fully rooted and the 99 % of the nematodes are killed. The decline is so strong that it takes more than four susceptible hosts to find higher levels of the nematodes again. Sowing 5-10 kg seed per ha is enough for a good coverage. From Mexico it was known that farmers growing tagetes flowers as chicken feed, had less problems with root-lesion nematode (*Pratylenchus penetrans*) in the next potato crop. In the early fifties it was tried to introduce this crop in rose plant production and potato production in the Netherlands. Farmers did not adopt this solution. In the nineties research showed the effectiveness both in apple, roses and potatoes. Nowadays large acreages of tagetes are grown in the Netherlands and Belgium with good results.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/external_factsheets/39.pdf

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests****Warning System For Aphids (*Aphididae*)**

Aphids (*Aphididae*) can transmit viruses to potatoes. It takes a very high number of aphids before it initiates spraying in consume and processing potatoes. When growing seed potatoes, it is different, since viruses in seed material must be avoided. Follow the local warnings for aphids to determine the need for control. In years with heavy infestations of aphids, it may be topical to desiccate the crop to avoid transmission of virus infection.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Pests; Other****Application Of Green Manure**

The application of the right species of green manure, together with non-inversion tillage, can effectively reduce the number of beetle larvae and slugs for example.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Pests; Other
Promotion Of Beneficial Insects

Promotion of beneficial insects by, for example, planting flowering strips, natural increase of the aphid (*Aphididae*), such as ladybugs (*Coccinellidae*), lacewings (*Chrysopidae*) and hoverflies (*Syrphidae*), can be encouraged. Other measures include the use of plant protection products that don't affect beneficial insects, or partial area treatments or intercropping. The sum of these measures can contribute to a natural regulation between beneficial insects and pests, which can lead to a reduced use of chemical pesticides. FAB (Functional agro biodiversity) or the use of biological defense by predatory insects or fungi can have several forms i.e. Bankerfields, consisting of flowermixtures including for example Japanese oats (*Avena strigosa*) and Indian cress (*Tropaeolum majus*), sown in strips within the potato fields instead of around the edges of the field. The FAB strips are aimed to attract beneficial insects and natural predators of for example aphids (*Aphididae*). Straw can also act as a breeding/survival area for beneficial insects.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Tom van der Meer, Cordelia Kreft

Take Economic Thresholds Into Account

The economic threshold determines when the use of chemical plant protection becomes economically viable, i.e. the number of harmful organisms where the losses exceed the costs of its chemical control. Setting a threshold is intended to reduce the use of chemical plant protection products to the absolute necessary minimum in order to achieve the maximum possible effect in the form of a healthy and uncontaminated crop.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Use Of Adjuvants

Good effects in the regulation of pest and weed infestations can be obtained by combining pesticides with adjuvants. Their main task is to improve the effectiveness of pesticides by increasing the retention and absorption of the plant protection product. This is possible due to the fact that adjuvants reduce the surface tension of spray liquid droplets and cover the sprayed surface more thoroughly. In addition, adjuvants prevent the crystallization of the working liquid on plants and delay its drying, increase the adhesion of the pesticide and better hydration of the cuticle. The use of protective agents together with adjuvants therefore reduces the risk of a decrease in effectiveness of the product used under unfavorable conditions, such as low air humidity or rainfall occurring after application of the pesticide. Only adjuvants tested and recommended with the product should be used.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Automatic Interrow Weed Control In Row Crops

New machines for automated intra-row weed control have revolutionised non-chemical weed management in transplanted vegetables and some direct-sown row crops. Thermal devices may also be used, they cause denaturation of proteins and rupturing of cellular tissue in weed plant tissue.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-automatic-intra-row-weed-control-in-row-crops/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photo: Farm droid operating. Sven Hermansen, ICOEL

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Inter-row Weeding And Band-spraying**

Inter-row spraying with e.g. glyphosate using shields for the crop is an option to control interrow weeds. Band spraying may be combined with inter-row cultivation.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-band-spraying/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Combination Of Chemical And Mechanical Weed Control

Chemical and mechanical weed control can be combined, e.g. glyphosate sprayed before emergence of potatoes and followed up by mechanical weed control.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Crop Rotation And Diverse Cropping Systems

A diverse cropping system with rotations of different annual and perennial crops, and changes between autumn and spring sown crops will result in a diversification of the weed population. A carefully planned crop rotation regenerates the biological soil environment and reduces excess weed growth. Furthermore, the variety of crops increases the spectrum of herbicides and control methods that can be used.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-crop-rotation-and-diverse-cropping-systems/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Finger Weeding In Row Crops

Finger-weeding is applicable in many agricultural and horticultural row crops. It controls intra-row weeds, which are those that grow in the crop line

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-finger-weeding-in-row-crops/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Finger weeding. Henning Thomsen & Bo Melander, Aarhus University

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Flame Weeding

Flame weeding for pre-emergence is a non-chemical method that can be used to control weeds in e.g. maize, sugar beets and vegetable crop

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-flame-weeding-pre-emergence-use/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photo: Flame weeder in action. Envo-dan.dk

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Hand Weed New Weed Species (Invasive Species)

New and small patches of weeds should be hand weeded (e.g. Thorn apple (*Datura stramonium*) and Apple of Peru (*Nicandra physalodes*). Metobromuron, clomazone and acifluorfen have some effect against these species.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Targeted use; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Control Dicotyledonous Weed Multiplication

Implement effective weed control in the years between potatoes to avoid dicotyledonous weed multiplication. This applies, for example, to Black Bindweed (*Polygonum convolvulus* L.) and Fat Hen (*Chenopodium album* L.). When choosing plant protection products, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that certain products have such a longivity effect that they can harm potatoes. This applies to products containing aminopyralid and clopyralid.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Fat hen. Aarhus University & SEGES Innovation

Effective Control Of Root Weeds

Implement effective weed control of root weeds in the years between potatoes. The best options for controlling root weeds are present in cereals, while there are few options for controlling root weeds in maize, potatoes, beets and several other crops. Couch grass (*Elymus repens*), Mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris* L.), Creeping Thistle (*Cirsium arvense*), Sows Thistle (*Sonchus* spp.) and other root weed species are best and cheapest controlled in cereal crops prior to potatoes. However, couch grass can be controlled when they have 3-4 leaves, and the potatoes still have not emerged.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photos: Sow thistle. SEGES Innovation

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Interrow Hoeing**

Interrow hoeing is a mechanical method that can be used to control weeds. Inter-row hoeing can be used separately or integrated with band spraying of herbicides. Hoeing can help controlling resistant weeds.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-inter-row-hoeing-sugar-beets-other-row-crops/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Destruction Of Volunteers

Leave as few potatoes as possible in the field when harvesting and cropping the field. Tubers left on the soil surface during winter may be destroyed by frost. Repeated harrowing and ploughing should be carried out in the spring. In row sown crops, row cleaning can effectively alleviate the problems of volunteer potatoes between rows. In crops where volunteer potatoes germinate before the crop, glyphosate can alleviate the problem to some extent. Before or after harvest of cereals, glyphosate applied to volunteer potato plants can destroy the daughter tubers and thus limit the increase in volunteers. Fluroxypyr agents can be used in the crop with volunteers. Finishing grass after potatoes is effective in ensuring that there is no waste during harvesting and combating regrowth, but on the other hand, grass in crop rotation with potatoes increases the risk of *Rhizoctonia sp.* and wire worms (*Agriotes spp.*) in a subsequent potato crop. Do not use beets or peas after potatoes, as they offer little competition against regrowth of potatoes.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Targeted use; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Mechanical Weeding On Potato Ridges

Mechanical weed control in potatoes has proven in experiments and practice as an effective method, but with a lower capacity is not quite on par with chemical control. Mechanical control is often used 2-4 times per season. The advantage of mechanical control is that it is possible to drive all day, even in windy weather. Mechanical control has a broad effect against most weed species. The method is less sensitive to the growth stage and species composition of weeds than chemical weed control. The use of mechanical cleaning requires continuous adjustment of the cleaner/hoe so that the mechanical treatment is neither too gentle nor too aggressive. In this way, root damages to the stolons with risk for yield losses are avoided.

There have been noticeable new developments in the field of mechanical weed control using tools such as harrows, hoes, hillers, and similar equipment in recent years. Modern harrows such as spring-tooth and tine harrows are well adjustable and cause little damage to emerging potato plants. Adequate depth and placement of seed potatoes in the row are essential for effective mechanical weed control. However, it should be noted that after tillage, the crop is more vulnerable to frost or wind erosion. Additionally, every tillage operation can cause moisture loss and/or root damage, which can slow down crop growth on drought-prone soils. To minimize these effects, tillage operations should be performed as shallow as possible. Successful mechanical weed control requires more agility than chemical weed control to take advantage of favorable weather and soil conditions. Potato ridges can be tilled intensively before crop emergence resulting in remarkable weed control efficacies (>95%), especially if the crop canopy can smother late emerging weeds.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Clara Sciffer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Weeds****Rental/leasing Of Soil Should Be Planned**

Rental/leasing of soil for seed potatoes should always be planned well in advance so that the areas can be thoroughly checked for volunteers the year before. Regrowth of waste potatoes can cause false crop rotation and increase the risk of mixing foreign varieties several years after the year of potato cultivation.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Spot Spraying Against Root Weeds

The total volume of applied pesticides is hereby significantly reduced. Many new sprayers have the ability to make precision spot spraying against selected weed species or volunteers. Spot spraying can be made from application maps based on drone photos. With precision spraying techniques higher accuracy and less off target spraying can be achieved.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

<https://iwmpraise.eu/tool-sheet-spot-spraying-patch-spraying-perennial-weeds/>

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Tom van der Meer

Photo: Thistle spot located with drone in cereal field. Rasmus Emil Jensen, SEGES Innovation

Increased Efficacy With Herbicide Mixtures

Mixing herbicides is a routine procedure used in agriculture that can reduce costs, increase the effectiveness of the crop protection product and extend the range of treatments in to a single treatment. The use of different mixtures of active substances allows reduction of the doses of herbicides, which increases the spectrum of controlled weed species. Herbicide rates in mixtures should typically be 20-50% less than the full recommended rates of individual herbicides. Mixing herbicides should be approached with care, as the use of inappropriate mixtures can reduce the effectiveness of the various ingredients or even damage the crop, as well as cause chemical reactions that damage the sprayer. Therefore, it is very important to know exactly which mixtures can be used, which products are not chemically mutually exclusive and how to minimize the possibility of failure during spraying.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Variable Rate Application For Soil-applied Herbicides

Many new sprayers are able to make precision spraying. Variable rate application maps can be made based on knowledge of weed occurrence in the field, EM38 or other tools for mapping texture.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Tom van der Meer

Photo: Variable rate application in Crop Manager, SEGES Innovation

Volunteer Potato Management

Volunteer potatoes are potatoes that are left in the field after harvest. These potatoes are hosts for pests and diseases and will transmit them to next season. With mild winters, volunteers from a previous potato crop can grow as weeds in other crops. The volunteers carry late blight inoculum (*Phytophthora infestans*) and can act as a primary infection source in the early spring. They are not protected by fungicide sprays and become a source of inoculum to nearby crops. Depending on the crop in which the volunteers occur, control is usually difficult and labour intensive. Eliminating volunteer potatoes is a very effective and important measure in IPM for potatoes. This can be done physically (machines or animals) or chemically.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

https://www.soilwealth.com.au/imagesDB/news/Volunteerpotatoesfactsheet_FINAL.pdf,
<http://www.endure-network.eu/content/download/4003/29720/file/Potato%20CS%20Guide%20Number%201%20LR.pdf>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds; Other

Intercropping

Cultivation of catch crops can have different effects depending on the time of sowing and the selected crop or mixture of crops. The most important aspects are the protection of soil erosion, the prevention of nutrient leaching and the improvement of soil structure.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Other****Anti-resistance: Correct Dosage**

Stick to recommended doses. The development of resistance may be promoted with both lower and higher doses than the recommended.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Anti-resistance: Different Modes Of Action

Alternate pesticides with different modes of action (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) should be used. When selecting plant protection products, pesticides used in previous years are taken into account. Long-term use of active substances from the same chemical group or products with a similar mechanism of action leads to resistance of pathogens and pests. The alternating use of herbicides, fungicides and insecticides from different chemical groups prevents or significantly delays the process of pests becoming resistant to the agents used. In e.g. Poland, it is allowed to use plant protection products that have valid permits issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and labels in Polish. The effectiveness of the treatment is determined by the correct dose of the product and the appropriate preparation of the tank mixture. Increasing the recommended dose of herbicides may cause phytotoxicity on the crop. An important element is to comply with the preharvest interval and the re-entry interval.

IPM principles:	Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer, Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento, Tom van der Meer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

Buffer zones

A minimal of 1-3 m 'crop protection free' buffer zones from water courses (this buffer zone can be larger depending on the PPP).

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

Soil type: Choice Of Location

The choice of the field and soil conditions are important. A well-aerated, light to medium-heavy soil warms up quickly and thus provides optimal conditions for rapid plant emergence. A good water permeability is important to avoid waterlogging.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Cultivation Technique: Irrigation

Irrigation is used to meet the crop's water needs and avoid run-off of nutrients and pesticides. Proper water management is a key factor for potato farming. 24 hours of water stress can be very detrimental to potato plants, effectively reducing a proper yield. Water management also determines the soil quality which in turn is essential for root development and organic matter content in the soil. Water has to be of good quality and applied in the right quantities on the right time. This is even more important than the method of water application.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	5
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer, Tom van der Meer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

Drift Reduction Techniques

Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ drift reduction).

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

Evaluation: Efficacy IPM Measures

Monitor infestation level before and after the measure; evaluation of the efficacy of the implemented IPM measures.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Potato**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Other****Evaluation: Register All Chemical Crop Protection Measures**

Register all chemical crop protection measures.

IPM principles:	Follow-up
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Clara Sciffer

Mechanical Haulming

Mechanical haulming/top-pulling can in some cases be practiced as an alternative to chemical desiccation, but can also lead to the spread of diseases. The basic condition for minimizing mechanical damage to tubers during harvesting is the destruction of haulm and weeds. It should take place about 3 weeks before the planned harvest using the mechanical method, i.e. using a haulm crusher. Mechanical damage to the tubers leads to bacterial infections, which causes further losses during storage. Rapid destruction of the haulm also limits the runoff of *Phytophthora infestans* spores (Late blight) from the above-ground part to the tubers, which prevents their infection and eliminates tuber infection with late blight during storage.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker, Tom van der Meer, Beata Wasilewska-Nascimento

Soil Structure

Soil structure and content is inevitably tied to proper development of resilient plants. This also has to do with proper watermanagement, organic matter content and proper fertilization, both in the off season and in the growing season. Especially on clay soils it is important to make sure to maintain a good soil quality, because it can take several years to restore it.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Tom van der Meer

Variable Rate Application Of Dessicants

Dutch studies have shown that there can be a great potential for variable rate application, using the highest dose where there is high leaf mass and low doses where there is low biomass. With the current availability of dessicants, VRA is not considered relevant, since doses and access to products are limited.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Marian D. Thorsted, Lars Bødker

Photo: Variable rate application in Crop Manager, SEGES Innovation

8. Onion

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Other

Appropriate Timing For harvest

The optimal date for harvesting onions for storage is considered to be when about 70-80% of the plants in the plantation have broken stems. A two-stage onion harvest is commonly used. The first stage is to dig up the onions and leave them in the field for initial drying. The second stage is to collect the onions in boxes and transport them to a warehouse for further drying and storage. The drying of onions in the field should not last longer than 7-10 days. If they are left longer, there is a risk of deterioration in the quality of the dry scales (uneven colouring, dark spots caused by the development of pest diseases, cracking of the scales), greening of the fleshy scales, secondary roots formation and severe grey mould (*Botrytis allii*) infections during further storage.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	1
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

Use Of Antagonists

In the biological protection of many vegetable plant species, including onions, it is recommended to use antagonistic organisms such as: *Pythium oligandrum*, *Trichoderma* spp., *Coniothyrium minitans*, or *Bacillus subtilis*, which inhibit the development of fungal pathogens.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Pathogen Effect And Host Plant Database

The pathogen database provides information on the impact of the pathogen on crops and how the crop effects pathogens, by e.g. reducing propagation. This allows for optimisation of the cropping plan. By setting up the cropping plan in a way that pathogen host plants are prevented or not in the rotation prior to a crop that is highly impacted by that pathogen.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

<https://www.best4soil.eu/database> <https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Photos: Leek rust, *Stemphylium vesicarium*. Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds
Crop Rotation

Use of crop rotation - not growing onions after crops of *Alliaceae* family in the same field more often than every 4 years. The best forecrop are plants of the families: *Brassicaceae*, *Cucurbitaceae*, *Fabaceae*, and tomato, carrot, beetroot, lettuce, maize, and wheat. A poor crop rotation results in a risk of multiplication of diseases and pests in the soil, especially white rot (*Stromatinia cepivora*) and onion smut (*Urocystis cepulae*), and pests like - nematodes (*Ditylenchus dipsaci*) and onion fly (*Delia antiqua*).

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Pulawska, Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Photos: Cabbage and cucumber as forecrops. Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion**Inventory of IPM tools****IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds****Application Of Chemical Plant Protection Products In Accordance With The Label**

Instructions for use like e.g. withdrawal periods must be respected when using plant protection products to avoid exceeding residue levels in the crop and final product. It is very important to respect the optimal climatic and environmental conditions under which plant protection treatments can be carried out, consider solar radiation, humidity and wind conditions.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Targeted use
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests
Monitoring

Pest monitoring provides the information required to make decisions on the timing of treatments. Pheromone traps, sticky traps or light traps can be used during the growing season. Most pests can be monitored by close inspection of the plants. Regular (weekly) monitoring, e.g. by visual checks, will allow growers to make informed management decisions. Accurate determination of the degree of plant infestation by individual pest species and comparison of the values obtained with action thresholds provide the basis for treatment decision. The development of forecasting models for diseases (e.g. rot or mold (*Botrytis*), Downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*) or pests (e.g. thrips (*Thysanoptera*)) combined with visual checks are desirable as important decision support systems.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

<http://www.endureinformationcentre.eu/>

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika, Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek, Mark Manshanden

Photo: Leek moth, Turnip moth damages, Downy Mildew. Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

The Action Threshold

The action threshold establishes the level of the pest population that causes economic losses. It is a point at which pest populations indicate that intervention is necessary to avoid economic losses. Considering the action threshold before deciding to carry out control treatments makes it possible to avoid unnecessary chemical treatments and to reduce the amount of pesticides used.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika

Photos: Adult of onion thrips and larvae of onion thrips. Grażyna Soika

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

The Use Of Adjuvants

The use of spray liquid adjuvants increases wetting, reduces the drift effect and thus can improve the efficacy of plant protection products while reducing application rates. The use of adjuvants is particularly important in onion crops whose leaves are very waxy. They should only be used if their efficacy is documented.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Weather Conditions For The Use Of Plant Protection Products

Optimal conditions for carrying out plant protection treatments are absence of rain and wind with air temperature around 10-20°C.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other

Green Manure And Organic Matter

The use of green manure within an appropriate crop rotation plan can improve soil functionality and biodiversity, with an effect on plant resilience to soil-borne diseases. The use of specific green manure plants has a good effect on nematode and disease control and reduces weed proliferation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Maria Grazia Tommasini

Mechanical Soil Cultivation As Pest Prevention

Timely agrotechnical work (such as ploughing or harrowing) is very important and has a limiting effect on pest numbers. Deep ploughing of crop residues reduces the abundance of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*), leafminers (*Agromyzidae*), leek moth (*Acrolepiopsis assectella*), and onion fly (*Delia antiqua*) which can overwinter on onion residues. Shallow soil tillage carried out in sunny and dry weather significantly reduces the number of grubs and wireworms (*Agriotes lineatus*) at the egg and young larvae stage, as they are sensitive to lack of moisture.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika

Onion Trips
Photos: Grażyna Soika

Caterpillar of leek moth on onion leaf

Proper Fertilisation

Fertilisation largely determines the growth and development of onions and has a significant impact on plant health and resilience. Optimal fertilisation, especially with nitrogen, contributes to healthy, well-maintained plants that are less susceptible to seasonal competition with weeds. However, it can also cause weeds to grow more intensively and influence the weed population structure, e.g. the proportion of nitrogen-loving species. Nutrient deficiency can cause physiological disorders and limit the uptake of other nutrients, resulting in reduced onion growth and resistance to stress factors. Fertilisation must be based on the results of soil and plant tissue analysis.

Spring fertilisation with poorly digested manure directly before onion cultivation should be avoided, as it may contain seeds of some weed species. It is preferable to apply manure or other organic soil amendments (e.g. compost) in autumn. Organic fertilisation with manure and composts increases the content of beneficial microorganisms that stabilize the microbial balance of the soil and reduce the occurrence of infectious soil pathogens of the genera *Fusarium* and *Pyrenochaeta*. Excessive nitrogen fertilisation leads to poor mechanical tissue development, which makes the succulent tissue more easily infested by pests (e.g. thrips (*Thysanoptera*)), as well as delaying the ripening with a consequent reduction in quality properties and shelf-life. Fertilization with phosphorus and potassium encourages strong development of the mechanical tissue and makes it more difficult for pests (e.g. thrips) to feed on it.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Photo: Onion fusarium rot, Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other
Site Conditions (Location Of Field)

Fields intended for onion cultivation should be in good condition, with low weed infestation, free of couch grass (*Elymus repens*) and other perennial weeds, e.g., field morning glory (*Convolvulus arvensis*), field horsetail (*Equisetum arvense*), yellow fieldcress (*Rorippa sylvestris*) and others. *E. arvense* is a very harmful weed because it has very deep rhizomes and there are no herbicides that effectively controls this species. Oilseed rape (*Brassica rapa*) should also be avoided as a forecrop for onion, because its seeds can fall on the soil during harvest and emerge in large numbers in onion. The seeds of oilseed rape remain viable for many years and can be a serious problem in onion plantations even several years after oilseed rape cultivation. It is important to avoid planting onions in the vicinity of other similar plantations (e.g. leek) or fields cultivated with these crops the previous year, in order to avoid the proliferation of pests (such as onion fly (*Delia antiqua*), onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*), leek moth (*Acrolepiopsis assectella*) or onion leaf miner (*Phytomyza gymnostoma*)) which can overwinter on the residues of the previous crop. Onion crops should also not be located in close proximity to perennial clover, alfalfa and other nectar-producing crops, including annuals, because nectariferous crops may attract some insects harmful to onions, or provide overwintering sites for soil-borne pathogens.

Choosing the correct planting location prevents the spread of many diseases that are a threat to onion crops, such as downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*). To reduce the risk of onion blight (*Botrytis squamosa*), for example, sites surrounded by shrubs and trees, near reservoirs and meadows, where there may be fog in the morning hours, should be avoided. In addition, prolonged wetting of the leaves favours the development of infections by most fungal and bacterial pathogens.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other
Sprayer Calibration

The correct application of plant protection products requires the determination of the correct amount of liquid to be sprayed per unit area, as well as the uniform flow of liquid from the individual nozzles. Calibration involves the regulation of the sprayer's operating parameters i.e., proper selection of nozzles, liquid pressure, working speed and boom height, so the crop protection products are applied precisely and with the least possible loss and drift, at the exact spray rate required. The application rate (L/ha) must be determined according to the plant protection product used, the pest to be controlled, the spraying technique and the development of the crop. In vegetable crop protection, field sprayers with a conventional boom or with an auxiliary air jet (PSP) are mainly used. PSP sprayers allow a uniform distribution of liquid on the plants with finer droplets and liquid doses reduced by half compared to a conventional boom, and is more robust to unfavorable weather condition. This creates the conditions to reduce the use of plant protection products by 20-30%. Proper conditions of e.g. wind and speed are still important to obtain the best result.

IPM principles:	Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Agnieszka Włodarek, Anna Jarecka, Magdalena Ptaszek

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other
Variety Selection

The choice of onion variety can make all the difference for integrated pest management. Varieties characterised by a short emergence period and a fast growth rate in the early vegetation period should be preferred, as well as varieties that produce a larger leaf mass will cover the ground better. However, the selection of crop varieties is of little importance for reducing weed infestation. The variety selection depends on the cultivation method and location. Varieties are classified according to the length of the growing season, the size, shape and color of the onion, its resistance/tolerance to the most dangerous diseases, e.g. Downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*), Fusarium basal rot (*Fusarium oxysporum*), Pink root (*Pyrenochaeta terrestris*), and its purpose. To avoid disease problems, it is suggested to rotate "long-day" and "short-day" varieties. Onion varieties should be characterized by low sensitivity to unfavorable climatic conditions, the formation a strong root system and they should also be robust for long-term storage. Properties of onion varieties for fresh market: delicate, sweet, mild and juicy flesh; for processing: easily detachable hulls and white flesh; for freezing: low dry matter content; for drying: high dry matter content; for canning: light hulls; for long-term storage: hard onions, not breaking out into chives; for winter cultivation: high frost-hardy, forming of onions at low temperatures, not breaking out into seed shoots.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other
Winter Ploughing

Winter ploughing, (25-30 cm or even up to 35 cm deep) is usually carried out in autumn, depending on weather and soil conditions. The depth of ploughing depends on soil characteristics, i.e. soil compactness and moisture content, and the crops to be grown. The goals of winter ploughing are as follows: 1) deep soil aeration, increasing the water capacity of the soil and extracting nutrients not available to plants from the deeper layers of soil; 2) reducing the presence of pathogens and pests overwintering in the soil and on plant residues, deep burial of weed seeds and adventitious roots (of e.g. *Elymus repens*), to hinder their germination and emergence; 3) burial of manure, green manure and mineral fertilisers (Ca, P and K); 4) make subsequent spring tillage easier and faster. A good and homogeneous preparation of the seedbed before sowing is essential to reduce water stagnation (to which onion is susceptible) and allow uniform sowing.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Other
Control of Weeds Reduces Diseases

Weed proliferation causes many infectious diseases, especially downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*) and alternariosis of onions (*Alternaria porri*). In addition, many weeds host pathogenic bacteria and viruses. It is therefore essential to keep onion plantations free of weeds. Weeds should be removed (by chemical or mechanical weeding) during the early stages of growth and must not be allowed to bloom and produce seeds, because the increased number of viable seeds in the soil results in greater weed infestation in the following years (methods: rotations, sowing and use of herbicides). Due to its upward growth habit, onion is not very competitive against weeds.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	5

Contributed by: Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Photo: Alternariosis. Agnieszka Włodarek

Nematode Support Tool

Plant parasitic nematodes pose a significant threat to crop yield and quality, with important groups including cyst, root-knot, root-lesion, stem, and free-living nematodes. The most effective way to manage nematodes is through healthy crop rotations, alternating between host and non-host crops or varieties to reduce infestation rates in the soil. To support this, the model contains information about the susceptibility and tolerance of 70 crops to 32 nematodes, though the databases are not soil- or country-specific. The model provides risk information based on specific crops, including green manure crops, and crop rotations, with user-provided farm-specific input. Created by the H2020 project Best4Soil and based on the Dutch model www.aaltjesschema.nl developed by Wageningen University and Research, the model assumes that the user-selected plant parasitic nematodes are present in the field.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

<https://nematodes.soilhealthtool.eu/en-gb/Nematode-scheme>

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Functional Agro Biodiversity (FAB)

This can have several forms i.e. Bankerfields, consisting of flowermixtures including for example Japanese oats (*Avena strigosa*) and Indian cress (*Tropaeolum majus*), sown in strips within e.g. potato fields instead of around the edges of the field. The FAB strips are aimed to attract beneficial insects and natural predators of for example aphids (*Aphididae*). Straw can also act as a breeding/survival area for beneficial insects. Protection of beneficial organisms (including parasitic and predatory insects, spiders and birds) by creating favourable conditions for their development, e.g. by providing biodiversity around the farm. Good results are achieved by creating environments called refuges with plant species that provide insects with nectar and pollen, which act as sources of sustenance for their development. The spread of natural enemies of pests is promoted by leaving refuges for entomophagous insects (e.g. trees, nectariferous plants) or hanging boxes for nesting birds.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika, Mark Manshanden

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Removal Of Plant Residues

Reduction of pests by removal (or burial) of plant residues which provide a wintering site for many pest species.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Diseases
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika

Rotation Of Active Ingredients

Pesticide rotation is the temporal alternation of pesticides with different modes of action. Repeated use of active substances with the same mode of action leads to an increase in selection pressure on the population of harmful arthropods, pathogens and weeds resulting in an increased rate of resistance development. The alternating use of fungicides of different chemical groups and with different active substances prevents or significantly delays the development of resistance in pathogens, pests and weeds. Consequently, reducing selection pressure by using pesticides with different modes of action can increase sustainability and preserve the effectiveness of pesticides.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika, Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek, Maria Grazia Tommasini, Sara Turci, Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Crop Density

Sowing uniformly and choosing the right plant density is important, also to reduce the proliferation of weeds. Too sparse seeding should be avoided and, if possible, missing plants should be supplemented.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion
Inventory of IPM tools
IPM tool for Weeds
Mechanical weeding

Mechanical weed control requires a wider distance between rows.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

<https://iwmpraise.eu/inspiration-sheet-automated-intra-row-weed-control-in-field-transplants/> ,
<http://www.endureinformationcentre.eu/>

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Photo: Modern weeder (with finger elements) removes weeds in inter-rows and near to onion plants and reduces manual weeding. Joanna Golian

Photo: Mechanical weeder with different elements. Joanna Golian

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Prevention of Seed Production By Weeds

Weeds should be removed (by chemical or mechanical weeding) during the early stages of growth and must not be allowed to bloom and produce seeds, because the increased number of viable seeds in the soil results in greater weed infestation in the following years (methods: rotations, sowing and use of herbicides). Due to its upward growth habit, onion is not very competitive against weeds.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka, Mark Manshanden

Photos: Barnyard grass, fan weed, Joanna Golian

The Use Of Split Application Methods

The use of split-dose herbicides makes it possible to reduce doses without losing efficacy, which reduces the risk for negative impact on the natural environment. To obtain good results many factors must be taken into account, first the type of herbicide and its dose, which must be selected on the basis of an analysis of the degree of infestation of weeds in the field. It is also important to adapt the timing of the application to the appropriate stages of weed development. In particular, herbicide applications are recommended during the early stages of weed growth. Other important factors are weather conditions, in particular temperature, air humidity and wind, as well as the efficiency of treatment equipment.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Dosage
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Weeds

Weed-Burning

It is possible to control weeds thermally with flame burners that burn gas from a propane-filled cylinder (pyro weed control). This treatment is recommended after weed emergence over the entire field area, before sowing of the onions or where onion rows are expected. In spring onion cultivation, weed burning can also be carried out after emergence in the inter-row, using covers to protect the crop from damage. Thermal destruction of the weeds delays the first weeding by approximately 10-14 days.

IPM principles:	Alternatives
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	5
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

https://iwmpraise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/WP7_IS_6_IWMPRAISE_eng.pdf

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Weed Monitoring

Weeds appear in all conditions and always require control. Weed monitoring in the early stages is important. The weed population in the field must be observed every year and the weed species present must be identified, as well as changes in weed structure. This is of great significance, especially in the case of post-emergence herbicide application. The appropriate decision on the use of herbicides should be made in relation to thresholds of harmfulness, but for onions there are no current threshold values. Therefore, the use of herbicide treatment should be based on the critical period, which for onions ranges from 1 true leaf to 4-5 leaves (usually 1/3-1/2 of the growing season). Monitoring and identification of weeds eliminate the possibility of unnecessary or inappropriate use of herbicides.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	5
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka

Photos: Shepard's purse, redroot amaranth, goosefoot, Joanna Golian

Onion

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Other

The Appropriate Use Of Irrigation

Irrigation after sowing is often necessary to facilitate seed germination, emergence and herbicide activation. Onions have shallow root system, and are at all stages of growth sensitive to soil water deficiency, but the greatest water requirement occurs during the intensive bulb formation period. Sufficient moisture is particularly important during the cultivation of winter onions, when sowing takes place in summer. Water shortages, especially in the most delicate phases of the crop cycle, must be supplemented with irrigation. The quality of the water used for irrigation (e.g. absence of chemical, biological contaminants and weed seeds) is also important. In Italy, years of cultivation experience with integrated production methods have shown that an adequate and careful application of irrigation and fertilisation practices makes it possible to significantly limit the damage caused by even high thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman) infestations. This makes it possible to raise the damage threshold and, consequently, to reduce, or eliminate, the number of insecticide interventions necessary to control the thrips.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	5
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Joanna Golian, Zbigniew Anyszka, Marian Grazie Tommasini, Sara Turci

Photo: Adult onion thrips, Grażyna Soika

Optimizing Sowing and Planting Dates

The selection of a suitable sowing date for crops helps to reduce damage caused by pests in the early stages of crop development, e.g. sowing winter onions on the last date allowed to reduce the degree of infestation of the crop by thrips (*Thysanoptera*). Sowing too early in spring prolongs the emergence period of the plants and exposes the delicate shoots to the attack of soil-borne pathogens that cause damping-off (*Pythium* spp., *Fusarium* spp.). Infection of seedlings by these pathogens can also be favoured by sowing too deep. The sowing time and correct plant density are important to reduce weed proliferation and ensure uniform emergence.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Grażyna Soika, Magdalena Ptaszek, Anna Jarecka, Agnieszka Włodarek

Photo: Larvae of onion thrips, Grażyna Soika

9. Non-crop specific

Non crop-specific tool

Plant Resilience

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests

This is a figure that explains the various mechanisms of plant resilience (=induced defenses + substrate resilience). If the grower knows to which category the product or cultivation measure belongs, this figure helps to understand what can be expected as result.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Johanna Molenaar

Verhoging substraatweerbaarheid

Verhoging plantweerbaarheid

Werken aan weerbaarheid - Mechanismen

Substraat(bodem)weerbaarheid: (Bodem)pathogeen is wel aanwezig, maar plant vertoont geen ziektesymptomen.

Plantweerbaarheid: De plant is voorbereid op een aanval van ziekten of plagen doordat zijn afweer is geactiveerd. Bij activatie verandert bijvoorbeeld de samenstelling van de plant- inhoudsstoffen, worden de celwanden verdikt en/of er worden meer bladharen gevormd.

1. Bevoordelen 'goede' micro-organismen door toevoegen organische (mest)stoffen. De groei en ontwikkeling van de niet-pathogene al aanwezige micro-organismen wordt bevoordeld, waardoor pathogenen minder kans hebben.

3. Toediening elicitor-stoffen. Elicitors zijn stoffen die de door de plant herkend worden en de natuurlijke afweer van de plant aanschakelen. De herkomst van deze stoffen is divers: chemische geproduceerd of natuurlijk uit algen-, plant- of schimmelextracten.

2. Tegenwerken 'slechte' micro-organismen door toevoegen antagonisten.

4. Toevoeging micro-organismen met elicitorwerking. Sommige micro-organismen scheiden elicitor-stoffen uit of hebben deze in de celwand. Deze micro-organismen kunnen zich op, in of bij de plant vestigen. Bij detectie van ziekte of plaag door de plant, kan hierdoor de weerbaarheid snel worden verhoogd.

1. Micro-organisme die stof produceert die schimmel/bacterie-groei remt (bijv. antibiotica-werking)
2. Micro-organismen bezetten wortelzone (biofilm) en geven pathogeen geen kans
3. Micro-organismen gaan competitie aan met pathogeen om voedsel

Begrippenlijst:

Organische (mest)stoffen: Deze stoffen kunnen niet alleen opgesomd worden door de plant, maar stimuleren ook de groei van micro-organismen. De juiste bemesting stimuleert het bodemleven in het algemeen, waardoor er meer competitie ontstaat voor de pathogenen.

Antagonisten: Antagonisten zijn micro-organismen die de pathogenen tegenwerken.

Biofilm: Laagje rondom een object (bijv zijwand pipleiding of wortel). Deze bestaat uit een matrix van suikers waarin micro-organismen gevestigd zijn.

Wortelzone: Deel bodem/substraat dicht bij de wortels. Er leven micro-organismen in deze zone, vaak als een biofilm rondom de wortels. Als een pathogeen een wortel wil binnendringen wordt deze gehinderd door micro-organismen die leven in de biofilm.

Competitie voedsel: Wortels scheiden stoffen uit (zo suikers, aminozuren, vetzuren) die als voedsel dienen voor micro-organismen. Pathogenen kunnen dit voedsel alleen bemachtigen als ze de competitie winnen met andere micro-organismen in het substraat/de bodem.

Elicitors: Stoffen die de door de plant herkend worden en de natuurlijke afweer van de plant aanschakelen.

Ontwerp door: Lucas Frantzen (Driehoek Research Support)

Ontwerp door: Lucas Frantzen (Driehoek Research Support)

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds; Others

Farmer access to expert advisory

The integrated pest management advisor is specialised in the control and efficient management of different types of pests. Their main objective is to prevent and minimise pest damage in safe and sustainable manner. These advisors have an extensive knowledge about life cycles, behaviour, and control methods for different pests and diseases. They are also aware of environmental and safety regulations and standards related to the use of chemical and biological products.

Moreover, the advisor is responsible for implementing and training clients in the use of physical, chemical, and biological control methods, always prioritising those that are least harmful for the environment and human health.

In Spain there are the Agrupación para Tratamientos Integrados en la agricultura (ATRIA), entities formed by farm owners with the aim of guaranteeing: the sustainable use of pest control, the promotion of integrated pest management of different crops, respect of environment and consumer safety.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Inspection and cleaning of treatment equipment before each application

The inspection and cleaning of equipment before each application in the integrated pest management is fundamental to ensure the pest control and avoid additional problems. This task is carried out to ensure that the equipment used is in optimal working condition and free of contaminant residues.

It is important to thoroughly inspect equipment such sprayers or atomisers for damage before each use. In addition, thorough cleaning of equipment should be carried out, which involves removing any residues or chemicals that may be left over from previous applications.

Currently, a closed transfer system is being implemented that allows chemical products to be transferred directly into the spray tank, which will reduce the risk of point source contamination at the time of tank filling and reduce the risk to the operator carry out the loading.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Correct and periodic machinery maintenance

Proper maintenance of application machinery in integrated pest management ensures optimal performance and efficient application. Some key aspects are presented below:

- Regular cleaning after each application. It is important to clean the machinery thoroughly to remove any residues or chemical products from previous applications, avoiding the cross-contamination and clogging of nozzles and filters.

Visual inspection of machinery to identify possible damage. Verification of nozzles, hoses, filters or tanks.

Regular calibration of equipment's to ensure correct dosing. Working pressure, forward speed and other relevant parameters should be checked according to the manufacturer's specifications.

In Spain there is a regulation certifying the good condition of machinery called "inspecciones obligatorias en los equipos de aplicacion de productos fitosanitarios" (ITEAF). New and individual equipment will be inspected every 5 years, the rest of equipment every 3 years.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Testing fields networks

Testing fields networks is an effective tool in the integrated pest management to promote sustainable practice and share knowledge between farmers, technicians and other actors involved in agricultural production. These networks consist of the creation of testing fields in different geographic areas, where different strategies of management are implemented and tested. In Spain, exactly in La Rioja, exists a network of 15 fields where more than 10 crops are tested. Their main objective is to show in a practical and visual way of the advantages and benefits of using a more sustainable and less chemical-dependent approach to pest control. Below are some key characteristics and benefits of testing fields networks.

- Information and experience exchanges between farmers, technicians, and pest management experts.
- Visits, workshops, or events to discuss and learn from each other's experience.

In addition, this allows farmers to know the effectiveness of these techniques in real fields conditions and take decision about their implementation on their own farms.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage; Anti-resistance; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Avoid the abusive use of phytosanitary treatments that may eliminate the natural enemies of pest

Avoidance of abusive use of phytosanitary treatments in integrated pest management is essential to preserve the natural enemies of pests. Natural enemies, like predators or parasitoids, play a crucial role in the biological control of pests as they feed on them and could help to keep their populations under control. In Spain, there are predators such as ants and ladybirds, and parasitoids like wasps.

Excessive or inadequate use of pesticides may have negative effects on natural enemies of pests. Some pesticides are toxic to these beneficial organisms and can drastically reduce their population and even eliminate them entirely. This can unbalance the agricultural ecosystem and lead to an increase in pest population.

To avoid this scenario, it is important to follow some key practices: monitoring and assessment, pest tolerance level, selective use of pesticides, precise application or refuges for natural enemies.

IPM principles:	Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	2
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Juan Sagarna

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds

Plowing

Plowing is an effective method of moving weeds, plant debris, and thus seeds or infested material from the surface to deeper layers. However, plowing can also destroy soil structure and promote erosion. Depending on soil conditions and crop rotation, the advantages and disadvantages of different tillage methods must be weighed and applied according to the situation.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Weeds

Hygiene measures

Hygiene measures are important to prevent the introduction and propagation of weeds or other pathogens. A distinction must be made between field hygiene and machine hygiene. For example, mulching or mowing the field margins can slow down the immigration of weeds or pests. However, field margins are also refuges for beneficial insects, so such measures must be weighed carefully. Cleaning the machines is important to prevent the spread of weeds. Especially when machines are used across farms.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Alternatives
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	2
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Change the mode of action

In a spray rotation as well as crop rotation it is of great importance to use pesticides with different modes of action. This minimizes the risk of possible resistance build-up and ensures that the pest can be controlled safely.

IPM principles:	Dosage; Anti-resistance
Efficacy*:	3
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	4
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	1
Current implementation*:	3

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Thresholds of damage

Not every infestation of weeds or pests is worthy of control. From an economic point of view, the cost of preventing damage must not be higher than the damage itself, i.e. it is cheaper to tolerate pests up to a certain limit than to control them. Accurate monitoring and assessment of damage is of particular importance.

IPM principles:	Prevention; Monitoring; Thresholds; Alternatives; Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	1
Cost (labour time)*:	4
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	2
Performance (standard quality)**:	2
Pesticide reduction*:	4
Current implementation*:	2

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests; Other

Beneficial insect-friendly management

Beneficial insect-friendly management can reduce the use of insecticides. This includes, among other things, the planting of flower strips and the use of bee-friendly insecticides. In addition, applying insecticides at times when beneficial insects are not flying can have a positive effect.

IPM principles:	Targeted use; Dosage
Efficacy*:	5
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	3
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	3
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Diseases; Pests; Weeds

Spot spraying

Spot-spraying requires special technology and special knowledge in its application. Used correctly, the same degree of effectiveness of a crop protection measure can be achieved with less quantity. However, this measure is not suitable for every pest or at every time.

IPM principles:	Monitoring; Thresholds; Targeted use; Dosage; Follow-up
Efficacy*:	4
Cost (labour time)*:	3
Cost (investments)*:	5
Performance (normal yield)**:	3
Performance (standard quality)**:	3
Pesticide reduction*:	5
Current implementation*:	1

Contributed by: Lars-Ole Hingst

Non crop-specific tool

Inventory of IPM tools

IPM tool for Pests

Nematode database

With the nematode tool you can create a crop plan and soil type specific scheme. This includes what crops are impacted by different nematodes and what crops effect the population of the nematodes. With this information one can optimize the cropping plan.

IPM principles:	Prevention
Efficacy*:	2
Cost (labour time)*:	1
Cost (investments)*:	1
Performance (normal yield)**:	4
Performance (standard quality)**:	4
Pesticide reduction*:	2
Current implementation*:	4

Contributed by: Mark Manshanden

Nematode scheme 2023

[Best4Soil Nematode scheme](#)

Date : Tuesday, August 29, 2023
 Country : Netherlands
 Description : Test
 Soil Type : sandy clay loam

Ctrl+Click on a cell for background information about the crop / nematode combination

	Root-knot nematodes					Root lesion nematodes					Free-living soil nematodes				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Potato	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●
Wheat	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	●●	?	i			
Rye	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	●●●●	?	i			

©2023. This nematode scheme is a product of Wageningen University & Research | Field Crops, Lelystad

Legend damage	
unknown	
none	
little (0-15%)	
medium (16-35%)	
serious (36-100%)	

Legend propagation	
--	active population decline
?	host plant susceptibility unknown
-	non host
●	poor
●●	moderate
●●●	strong
R	variety dependent
S	serotype dependent
i	some information

Legend soil type	
1	sandy soil
2	reclaimed peat soil
3	sandy clay loam
4	clay soil
5	silty soil (loess)

Figure: Best4Soil Nematode Scheme

2. Appendix

1. Form to fill in for inventory

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101084527

Form to fill in for: Inventory of IPM tools (WP1 in SUPPORT)

In the following you will find the form to use for adding and describing an IPM tool to be included in the Inventory of IPM tools. It is mandatory to use this form, and in English :-)

You can only add one IPM tool per form, at a time, but you can specify more crop categories, if relevant.

Answer the questions in the form and include a very short description of the IPM tool. At the end of the form, it is possible to add links. Upload a description about the tool, e.g., fact sheet in English. Pictures may also be uploaded.

In the form you will find questions where you must rate the IPM tool on a five-point scale according to the feasibility, time for implementation, costs and impact on reduction of pesticide use.

Notice! It is necessary to answer a question to continue to the next question in the form.

Remember to submit the form when you come to the end. And start a new session by activating the link, when you add the next IPM-tool

* Påkrævet

1. Country *

2. Title of IPM Tool (write the title below) *

3. Crop(s). Tool can be added to more than one crop category if relevant, choose 1 or more on the list *

- Apple
- Maize
- Olive
- Onion
- Potato
- Strawberry
- Wine grape
- Winter wheat
- Non crop-specific tool

4. Which pest group is the tool ment for (choose one or more) *

- Weeds
- Diseases
- Pests
- Other (virus, plant growth regulation, avoidance etc.)

5. IPM principles that are covered of the tool (choose 1 or more of the 8 principles) *

*

- 1. Prevention and/or suppression of harmful organisms should be achieved or supported among other options.
- 2. Harmful organisms must be monitored by adequate methods and tools, where available.
- 3. Based on the results of the monitoring the professional user has to decide whether and when to apply plant protection measures. Robust and scientifically sound threshold values are essential components for decision making.
- 4. Sustainable biological, physical and other non-chemical methods must be preferred to chemical methods if they provide satisfactory pest control.
- 5. The pesticides applied shall be as specific as possible for the target and shall have the least side effects on human health, non-target organisms and the environment.
- 6. The professional user should keep the use of pesticides and other forms of intervention to levels that are necessary, e.g. by reduced doses, reduced application frequency or partial applications, considering that the level of risk in vegetation is acceptable and they do not increase the risk for development of resistance in populations of harmful organisms.
- 7. Where the risk of resistance against a plant protection measure is known and where the level of harmful organisms requires repeated application of pesticides to the crops, available anti-resistance strategies should be applied to maintain the effectiveness of the products. This may include the use of multiple pesticides with different modes of action.
- 8. Based on the records on the use of pesticides and on the monitoring of harmful organisms the professional user should check the success of the applied plant protection measures.

6. Write a short description of the IPM tool. How is it used? Why is it recommended? (Do not use LINE CHANGES, maximum 1000 characters, space included) *

7. Efficacy of the IPM tool against the relevant pest group(s) (choose 1-5) *

1: Very low efficacy against the relevant pest group (0-5 %) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Very high efficacy against the relevant pest group (50 % or more)

8. Cost of implementation in labour time (choose 1-5) *

Indicate cost of applying the tool

1: Very little (0-0,5 hour per hectare) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Very much (10 hours or more per hectare)

9. Cost of implementation in investments (choose 1-5) *

Indicate the cost of applying this tool in your actual country

1: Very low price (1 % or less of the crop value per hectare) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Very high price (50 % or more of the crop value crop per hectare)

10. Here you upload the pdf document/fact sheet that describes the IPM tool (English only). Supplementary pictures can also be uploaded. You find the SharePoint link for upload below.

Please write the names of authors/photographers below (Do not use line changes).

<https://seges.sharepoint.com/:f:/s/EUSUPPORT/E5vqb2DMVhBBolKnh0h9rY08mPjEK80KsCMAIYM7xYVQTA>

11. Performance (normal yield) compared to pesticide use (choose 1-5) *

Indicate effect on normal yield in percent

1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

12. Performance (standard quality) compared to pesticide use (choose 1-5) *

Indicate effect on standard quality in percent

1: Negative impact (- 5 % or more) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Positive impact (+ 5 % or more)

13. Potential reduction of pesticide use (choose 1-5) *

1: Very low potential of reduction (almost 0 %) ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ 5: Very high potential of reduction (25 % or more)

14. Current level of implementation (choose 1-5) *

1: Very low level of implementation (used on up to 5 % of the area)

5: Very high level of implementation (used on 50 % or more of the cropped area)

15. If you have sent pictures by SharePoint please choose 'Yes', otherwise choose 'No' *

Yes

No

16. Here you can insert a link to the tool on a webpage, English only. (if there is no link, just write 'minus') *

17. Please write your e-mail address below. *

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